

ISSN 0975-4954
Vol. 10, January, 2018

Indian Journal of
Applied Hospitality
& **Tourism Research**

Banarsidas Chandiwala Institute of
Hotel Management & Catering Technology
New Delhi

Indian Journal of Applied Hospitality & Tourism Research

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Subscription fee for one year: ₹ 1000/- (Institution), ₹ 750/- (Individual) for India & \$75 for Overseas

To be paid by DD/Pay Order in Favour of: Banarsidas Chandiwala Institute of Hotel Management & Catering Technology, New Delhi

**Indian Journal of
Applied Hospitality and Tourism Research**

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Preface

We would like to present, with great pleasure, the 10th volume of Indian Journal of Applied Hospitality and Tourism Research, a scholarly journal. This journal is part of the Banarsidas Chandiwala Institute of Hotel Management and Catering Technology's series of India International Hotel Travel and Tourism Research Conference, and is devoted to the gamut of current and emerging trends, challenges and issues that are being faced by Hospitality and Tourism Operators in a high-growth business environment.

This journal was envisioned and published annually to represent the growing need of research in Hospitality and Tourism as an emerging and increasingly vital field in the economy of a Nation. Its mission is to become a voice of the Hospitality and Tourism community, addressing researchers and practitioners in areas ranging from Emerging Trends, Contemporary Issues, Natural Disaster, Climate Change & Crisis Management, Eco-Tourism, Green Practices & Sustaining Environment, Economics and Forecasting, Virtual Tourism, e-Tourism, ICT & Travel Technologies, Food Safety, Quality & Innovations, Marketing Strategies & Consumer Behavior, Education and Training, Human Resources and Business Strategies and Revenue Management in Hospitality and Tourism.

Indian Journal of Applied Hospitality and Tourism Research focuses on original high-quality research in Hospitality & Tourism in parallel and distributed environments, encompassing facilitation of the theoretical foundations and the applications for Industry Managers, Tourism and Hospitality Researchers together. The Journal is intended as a forum for practitioners and researchers to share the issues related to the Travel, Tourism and Hospitality business.

This volume is devoted to Hospitality and Tourism research and the application of such research, which naturally complement each other. This volume comprises Ten manuscripts, from various topics of Hospitality and Tourism Research & Education. These articles exemplify the analysis and exploration of complex issues & Challenges and Trends from various sections of Hospitality and tourism. They provide invaluable insights into the studied problems and offer convincing exploratory studies and primary data analysis. All the papers comprises original research work in the Tourism Economy in India, Contribution of Tourism facilities, Sustainable water management in Hotels, Comparison of Foreign Values to Indian Spiritual Values, Development in Indigenous Tourism, Destination Image, Job Satisfaction in Hotel & Tourism Industry, Border Tourism as a tool for Peace, Consumer Behaviors in Fast Food Industry and Reliability of Online Travel Portal and Travel Agencies. Many Hospitality and Tourism Managers, Researchers and Faculties have contributed to the creation and the success of the Hospitality and Tourism Industry. We are very thankful to everybody within our Industry who contributed and supported for the publication of this issue. We are certain that this support and participation in Research will be followed by many others, reporting new Trends, deliberating on existing Issues and Challenges in the Hospitality and Tourism field. This issue would not have been possible without the great support of the Editorial Board members, and we would like to express our sincere thanks to all of them. We would also like to express our gratitude to the IJAHR editorial staff of BCIHMCT, in particular our Patron of this Journal, Dr. Bhuwan Mohan, Secretary, SBCSSTS, who supported us at every stage of the project. It is our hope that this fine collection of articles will be a valuable resource for Indian Journal of Applied Hospitality and Tourism Research readers and will stimulate further research into the vibrant area of Hospitality and Tourism.

Dr. Bhupesh Kumar
Editor-in-Chief

The Economic Contribution of Tourism Industry in India: An Appraisal

Suneel Kumar¹, Shekhar² & Kamlesh Attri³

Abstract

Today, travel and tourism industry has grown into one of the prominent service sectors around the world and its growth is further boosted by the continuous infrastructural & technological advancements of the 21st century. Due to the impacts of globalization and India's increasing role in international organizations, its brand as a tourist hotspot has also strengthened and tourism sector has witnessed an extraordinary growth. The present paper attempts to analyze India's tourism sector from a financial viewpoint. India welcomed 8.80 million foreign tourists in 2016, which contributed around US\$ 22,923 million foreign exchange earnings. The rising foreign tourist arrivals and the substantial foreign exchange earnings contributed by this sector to the Indian economy are indicative of its significance. With the help of statistical tools, the paper tries to study key tourism indicators, their growth trends and understand the inter relationships among them. India's tourism development initiatives and budget allocation along with its impact on the FEEs is also studied. The paper throws light on the opportunities lying ahead for this growing industry and also lists some of the challenges faced by it. The opportunities and the challenges are assisted with quantitative data for better understanding. Based on the analyses of the key tourism indicators and the study of opportunities and challenges, suggestions are provided for the development of tourism industry.

Keywords: Foreign Exchange Earnings, Foreign Tourist Arrival, World Tourism Organization and GDP.

Introduction and Rationale of the Study

The Error! Bookmark not defined. (WTO) believes that tourism is not just limited to a mere holiday activity and defines it as people "traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes". With about 1,235 million international tourist arrivals around the world in 2016, tourism remains one of the fastest growing sectors of the 21st century at 4% annual growth rate. This enormous growth has supported about 292 million jobs i.e. 9.6% of total employment and contributed a total of US\$ 7613.3 billion (10.2% of GDP) around the world in the year 2016. People like to travel for a variety of reasons. Travelling to new lands help them discover new cultures, enjoy time with family and friends, seek inspiration or creativity, seek spirituality, connect with self, challenge themselves beyond their comfort zone, try different cuisines or simply relax and celebrate life. As the world tourism industry thrives, India is no exception. Whenever we talk about tourism in India, we come across the famous phrase from a Vedic era Sanskrit text, Taittiriya Upanishad, which is "Atithi Devo Bhava" meaning 'The guest should be treated equivalent to God.' This philosophy was ingrained in the Indian culture and is part of Indian society's 'Code of Conduct'. India may have witnessed innumerable changes over time, but treating guests in the highest regard similar to that of God is a custom still alive. For ages, India has been a top attraction for tourists. Accounts of famous travellers like Megasthenes, Fa-Hien and Hiuen Tsang who visited India during the medieval period, highlight that the Indians have always been hospitable to the foreign travellers. They have also praised the richness of India in term of flora and fauna. India is still a major tourist destination boasting a diversity of cultures, landscapes, food, architecture and many fascinating places to explore. As per the report published by Ministry of Tourism (June 2017), India welcomed about 8.80 million foreign tourists in 2016 as compared to 8.03 million in 2015, registering a growth of 9.7% (Tourism Report, 2017). The tourism industry has a vital role in India's economy. This industry contributed to about 9.6% in India's GDP in 2016. The industry generated earnings of US\$ 22,923 million in 2016 as compared to US\$ 21,071 million in 2015, with a growth rate of 8.8 % (WTTC, 2017). Tourism sector has also played a significant role in providing employment. The direct and indirect contribution of tourism sector in employment is around 9.3% of total employment. Six Indian cities- Delhi (28th), Mumbai (30th), Chennai (43rd), Agra (45th), Jaipur (52nd) and Kolkata (90th) have found a mention in Euromonitor's Top 100 City Destinations Ranking (2015), as the most visited cities by foreign tourists in the world. India has improved its ranking in the World Economic Forum's The Travel and Tourism Competitive Index 2017. India now ranks

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40th out of the 136 economies around the world, improving its ranking by 12 places over previous year. The report also acknowledges Indian tourism's price competitiveness and ranks it 10th globally. India is also ranked at 24th place for its natural resources and is placed 9th for its cultural resources. (The Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Report, 2017)

Review of Literature

Kaul and Gupta (2009) discussed the various aspects of sustainable tourism in India from the perspective of government and industry stakeholders. They recognised the need for sustainable tourism in India, the impediments involved and the paradox of public sector and private sector in Indian tourism sector. Nedžad (2011) talked about the need for building a crisis management team as well as other crisis management strategies to deal with the aftermaths of terrorists attack on a tourist place and major impacts of terrorism on tourism sector. He also recognizes the role and impact of media in rebuilding the image of tourism destination. Lok Sabha Report (2013) recognizes the reasons for emergence of new avenues such as eco-tourism, tiger tourism, wellness tourism, golf tourism in recent years. The report bats for development of tourism sector by the coordinated efforts of all the stakeholders and also mentioned that the several initiatives were taken by the government for promotion of tourism. Kaur and Sharma (2014) studied the impact of tourism sector on the Indian economy. They underlined the vast potential tourism sector offers in terms of generation of employment and earning foreign exchange. They concluded by acknowledging the role of tourism in socio-economic development of the country. Banerjee (2014) focused on the significance of human resource development in the context of Indian tourism. She believes that adequate steps should be taken to train the personnel so as to maintain high quality and efficiency in tourism services. Apart from developing the human resources, adequate funds should be allocated towards building a proper infrastructure for enhancing tourism services. Baker (2014) studied the negative impacts of terrorism on travel and tourism industry. He studies the perception of tourists on terrorism while selecting a destination. He studied the relationship between terrorism and tourists' behavior, economic effects of terrorism on tourism demand and on destination image. Mir (2014) studies the economic aspects of Indian tourism industry with the help of statistical tools and examined the growth trends of foreign tourists as well as domestic tourist visits in India. He concluded that tourism has limitless potential to serve as tool for economic and socio-cultural development of the economy. Subash (2015) highlighted the major challenges faced by the Indian tourism industry like the substandard quality of infrastructure, security concerns of tourists, shortage of trained personnel in this industry. Tran, (2016) argued for the need of sustainable tourism in Vietnam. He explored the potential of Vietnamese island culture and concluded that in order to grow efficiently there is a need to sustain the heritage and religious sites in the island so that the benefits can be reaped for a longer duration.

Research Objectives and Methodology

In this paper, attempt has been made to study the increasing demand and ballooning tourism sector in the country and the challenges faced to utilize its full potential with the existing literature, data, government reports and books as the secondary data sources. This paper seeks to address the following key objectives:

1. To know and analyze the economic contribution of Indian tourism sector.
2. To discuss the emerging prospects and problems of tourism sector in India.
3. To suggest measures that will help the Indian tourism industry to realize its full potential.

The data for the present study is collected from secondary sources such as reports by the Ministry of Tourism (Govt. of India), Indian Tourism Statistics of 2017, World Travel & Tourism Council's Report on India, World Economic Forum's Report 2017, Euromonitor's Research Reports and several other journal articles and newspaper reports. A review of the existing literature relevant to the tourism industry has also been taken in to consideration. For the accomplishment of research objective statistical tools like compound annual growth rate, correlation and regression analysis has been used. For the study, Foreign Tourist Arrival is taken as independent variable X and Foreign Exchange Earnings as dependent variable Y.

Economic Contribution of Indian Tourism Industry in India: An Appraisal

Tourism can be domestic tourism; when a citizen of a country travels to a different place within the same country or International Tourism; when people travel beyond their national boundaries to visit other countries. Inbound Tourism is said to be when people visit a country which is not their place of residence and such a travel is made for not less than 24 hours and not more than a year. International Tourist arrivals include foreign tourist arrivals (FTA) and the arrivals of non-resident nationals. Outbound tourists are those who leave their own country to visit foreign lands. India has witnessed an exceptional boom in the tourism industry in the 21st century. The economic scenario of tourism industry can be checked and analyzed with the help of following given below tabulated data.

Growth and Trend of Tourists Visited India

Table 1 shows the number of foreign tourists that visited India in a particular year and the domestic tourists visiting other states within India in last 15 years (2002-2016).

Table 1: Profile of Tourists in India

Years	Domestic Tourist Visits (in millions)	FTAs in India (in millions)
2002	269.6	2.38
2003	309.04	2.73
2004	366.27	3.46
2005	392.04	3.92
2006	462.44	4.45
2007	526.7	5.08
2008	563.03	5.28
2009	668.8	5.17
2010	747.7	5.78
2011	864.53	6.31
2012	1045.05	6.58
2013	1142.53	6.97
2014	1282.8	7.68
2015	1431.97	8.03
2016	1613.55	8.80
CAGR	13.63%	9.79%

Source: Indian Tourism Statistics 2017, Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India

Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) has been calculated by using the following formula:

$$CAGR = ((\text{End Value}/\text{Start Value})^{1/(\text{Periods} - 1)}) - 1$$

$$CAGR (\text{Domestic Tourist Visits}) = ((1613.55/269.6)^{1/(15-1)}) - 1 = 13.63\%$$

$$CAGR (\text{Foreign Tourist Arrivals}) = ((8.80/2.38)^{1/(15-1)}) - 1 = 9.79\%$$

Figure 1

The line chart depicts the percentage change over the previous year in the last decade. It is noticed that the figures rising from 2006 to 2007 but starts to decline in 2008 and hit rock bottom in 2009 with the country witnessing a fall in FTA in regard to year 2008. Tourism sector seems to revive itself in the

coming year i.e. in 2011 & 2012 FTAs in India were increasing at a decreasing rate, with growth percentages falling. The growth rate rose for the next two years declining again in 2015.

It is observed from the rapidly changing growth rates that it declines in three defined slots in the last decade, first during 2008-09, second during 2011-12 and lastly in 2015. The probable reasons of these could be that in 2008-09, the US sub prime crises slowed the US and European economy. As Indian foreign tourist comprises a major portion from these nations, so FTA took a huge hit. As this recession spread all across the globe, tourism industry in India took a huge blow. Another major reason that could be attributed to negative growth rate of FTAs in India was the infamous Mumbai attacks in November, 2008, that shook the nation. Attacks caused 164 deaths and left hundreds injured including many foreigners. Such attacks were seen as failure of security system and curbed the growth of foreign tourists visit in Mumbai. In 2011, although India hosted cricket world cup, still it could not manage to outgrow its previous year growth rate. This was mainly because of another terrorist attack on Mumbai. Frequent terrorist attacks damage the image of the country and halt the potential tourists. In 2015, attacks in Gurdaspur region bordering Pakistan, agitation during the Patidar Movement in Gujarat, Swine Flu affecting Rajasthan, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh severely and Earthquake causing enormous destruction in North India and Nepal caused troubles to Indian tourism industry.

Monthwise Distribution of FTAs

In order to find the periods of time when tourism industry enjoys its boom and to locate the months when business is in the bearish phase, we took out last 15 years' month wise average of FTAs in India. The following graph depicts the same.

The graph in figure 2 accommodates average monthwise data of 15 years from 2002 to 2016. It is observed that December is the most favourable month for the Indian Tourism industry. The main reasons can be: Westerners like celebrating the new year in the Eastern part of the world which experiences the new year earlier than in their home country. This is primarily the reason why many people visit countries like Australia and Japan for the new year celebrations. Goa, in recent times, has become a top destination in India for the foreigners to enjoy the last sunset of the foregone year. The extended holidays from Christmas to the new year opens up avenues for westerners to travel and explore different destinations. Since the weather in India in that time of the year closely matches with their usual climate, it makes their travel much more convenient. Another noticeable fact is that the month of May attracts least number of foreigners. The primary reason for this is the scorching heat and dry summer experienced in most parts of north India at that time. India also experiences droughts and water shortages which makes it a less lucrative option for the tourists.

Figure 2

Foreign Exchange Earnings

Tourism in India contributes 9.6% to the GDP of the country. As visitors spend money during their stay India's hospitality, transport, organized and unorganized businesses thrive. The following table depicts the foreign exchange earnings collected by India in a particular year during the last fifteen years.

Table 2: Growth and Trend of Foreign Exchange Earnings from Tourism Sector

Years	Foreign Exchange Earnings (US\$ millions)
2002	3103
2003	4463
2004	6170
2005	7493
2006	8634
2007	10729
2008	11832
2009	11136
2010	14193
2011	16564
2012	17737
2013	18445
2014	20236
2015	21071
2016	22923
CAGR	15%

Source: Indian Tourism Statistics 2017, Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India
CAGR (FEE) = ((22923/3103) ^ (1/(15-1)))-1 = 15%

Table 2 exhibits the foreign exchange earnings from tourism sector during the period of 2002-2016. The foreign exchange earned has multiplied approximately seven times during the period. Although the sector has normally experienced high growth in foreign exchange earnings but it dropped in year 2009. Since then foreign exchange earnings has shown a positive growth. The compound annual growth rate of FEE for the period 2002-2016 is exceptional i.e. 15%. It is evident from the data that FEE took a dip in 2009. The FEE dropped down to 11136 in 2009 from 11832 in year 2008. This could be attributed to the global economic crisis which caused a reduction in number of FTA in the country during that period. On comparing CAGR of FTA and FEE is found that FEE is increasing more than FTA. This is a positive sign for the economy as it shows that foreign tourists are spending more than they were before.

Relationship between FTA and FEE

The foreign exchange earnings (FEE) are believed to be rising in direct correlation with the rising FTAs over the last fifteen years. The table below shows that the coefficient of determination between the FTA and FEE is 0.988284. This means that 98.824% changes in the FEE can be attributed to the changes in FTA. The other change could be due to various reasons such as changes in the foreign exchange rate of rupees, shift in spending pattern of the tourists.

On carrying out regression analysis in MS-Excel using LINEST function, values in above table were determined. The slope of a regression line (b) represents the rate of change in variable Y as variable X changes. So the value determined here for the slope is 3272.002. This means that when variable X changes by 1, there is an average change of 3272.002 in variable Y. The term R² represents the coefficient of determination which shows how much change in value of variable Y is explained by change in variable X. The SSR is the amount of variance which can be explained through regression analysis. Intercept is the value of Y variable which would exist if the value of X variable becomes zero. The SSE is the sum which cannot be explained through regression analysis. It shows how much change is caused in variable Y by factors other than the independent variable X. The F statistic or the F-observed value is used to determine whether the observed relationship between the dependent and independent variables occurs by chance. The D.O.F or degrees of freedom are used to calculate the F value from the table. The standard error for the variable Y estimate is 709.795. The standard error for the slope is given by S (b) and the standard error for the intercept is given by S (a).

Table 3: Relationship Analysis of Foreign Tourist Arrival and Foreign Exchange Earnings

YEAR	FTA(X)	FEE(Y)	FEE*(Y _c)	(Y-Y) ²	(Y _c -Y) ²	(Y- Y _c) ²
2002	2.38	3103	2747.11	97593323.80	104751587.49	126656.96
2003	2.73	4463	3892.31	72572225.14	82621220.72	325685.09
2004	3.46	6170	6280.87	46402435.74	44904206.79	12292.87
2005	3.92	7493	7785.99	30128389.14	26997784.15	85845.56
2006	4.45	8634	9520.16	18904524.27	11983907.83	785271.04
2007	5.08	10729	11581.52	5075708.60	1961167.39	726784.33
2008	5.28	11832	12235.92	1322346.67	556540.56	163148.84
2009	5.17	11136	11876.00	3407469.87	1223095.94	547595.05
2010	5.78	14193	13871.92	1466682.47	792072.50	103093.73
2011	6.31	16564	15606.08	12831201.60	6886140.21	917612.74
2012	6.58	17737	16489.52	22610659.00	12303160.66	1556207.62
2013	6.97	18445	17765.60	29845097.40	22883469.43	461583.98
2014	7.68	20236	20088.72	52621483.20	50506440.99	21690.90
2015	8.03	21071	21233.92	65432999.54	68095323.75	26543.71
2016	8.8	22923	23753.36	98824806.47	116023717.80	689504.31
	Y	12982		559039353	552489836.2	6549516.73

Source: Indian Tourism Statistics 2017, Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India

FTA(X) =Dependent variable, **FEE(Y)** =Independent variable, **FEE (Y_c)** = Value of FEE as per Regression Equation, **(Y-Y)²**= Total Variance in FEE, **(Y_c-Y)²**= Explained Variance in FEE, **(Y- Y_c)²** = Unexplained variance in FEE

Table 4:Regression Analysis Values

SLOPE	S(b)	R ²	F	SSR	Intercept	S(a)	S _{yx}	D.O.F	SSE
3272.002	98.80624	0.988284	1096.626	552489836	-5040.25	574.2542	709.795	13	6549517

Figure 3 Comparison of Actual and Expected FEE

On performing the regression analysis on foreign exchange earning with foreign tourist's arrival, an expected foreign exchange earnings (on the basis of FTA) could be developed. It was observed that the actual and expected earnings follow each other closely. This confirms the cause and effect relationship and the extent of correlation between them. The noticeable thing in the graph is that the actual FEE exceeded expected FEE during the phase of 2011-2014. This was because of the international events that were organized in India. When a tourist visits for attending such events, he spends more than he normally would have. This is because his stay is affected by the duration of event, activities that require additional investment for participation in events etc.

Direct Contribution of Tourism Sector

According to the World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC) Report (2016), world tourism sector directly contributed about US\$ 2,306.0 billion i.e. 3.1% of the total world GDP. This sector globally supported 108,741,000 jobs directly i.e. 3.6% of the total employment. These figures signify the rising importance of the tourism sector and governments must take appropriate steps towards effective management of this sector. Some of the figures relating to the year 2016 have been listed in tabular form below for the developed European nation of France, the fastest growing economy of China and Tourism hub of Thailand along with India.

Table 5: Contribution of Tourism Sector

Country	International Tourist Arrivals (ITA) (in Millions)	Direct Contribution to GDP (% of total GDP)	Direct Contribution to Employment (% of total employment)
India	14.6	US\$ 71.7 billion (3.3%)	25,394,500 jobs (5.8%)
France	82.6	US\$ 90 billion (3.6%)	1,180,500 jobs (4.2%)
China	59.3	US\$ 275.2 billion (2.5%)	23,680,500 jobs (3.1%)
Thailand	32.6	US\$ 36.7 billion(9.2%)	2,313,500 jobs (6.1%)

Source: World Travel & Tourism Council Country Reports, 2016

We can observe (table 5) that France, the most visited country in the world attracted 82.6 million International tourists in 2016, which is 5.65 times as much of India. The direct contribution of this sector towards GDP includes the proceeds made by industries directly involved with providing services to tourists and is calculated by deducting the imports made by these industries from their total revenue. China clearly tops the chart with the Chinese tourism industry generating about 4 times revenue than their Indian counterpart contributing an enormous US\$ 275.2 billion in 2016. The maximum number of people employed directly within this industry was by India with 25,394,500 jobs. Thailand, another Asian country has sincerely worked towards developing its tourism sector which directly contributed 9.2% of its National GDP. The Ministry of Tourism is the nodal agency working towards the development and promotion of tourism in India. It launched its successful international marketing campaign “Incredible India” in 2002 to promote India as an attractive tourist destination. Another campaign “*Atithi Devo Bhava*” was launched in 2008 to complement the former. Apart from these, the Government of India also launched the “e-tourist visa” scheme in 2014 to speed up the visa process and grant electronic copies of visas to tourists visiting Indian subcontinent. This scheme facilitates foreign nationals at 24 airports and 3 seaports across the country.

Emerging Prospects and Problems in Tourism Sector

It is important to study the environment in which the Indian tourism sector operates and such analyses assist in formulating the right strategy both for the short and the long term having a keen eye for the favorable or unfavorable changes in the external environment that may impact the sector’s performance. Indian tourism sector enjoys the geographical advantage of the country, which is often called the subcontinent for the diversity of landforms it encompasses. The sector’s strength lies in its diversity of topography, climate, customs, festivals, attire and cuisines. On the other hand, it must also deal with the problems of Infrastructural loopholes, under promotion, terrorism and threat from rival developing Asian nations.

Emerging Prospects of Tourism Sector in India

India must identify the trends in the tourism industry, so that it can exploit these avenues to its advantage. Opportunities may be identified by studying the new reasons travel enthusiasts around the world are considering while choosing their next destination. A study of a few such emerging prospects is done in the following points:

- **Medical Tourism:** Health and Medical Tourism is a term used for people travelling across national boundaries for medical treatments. World medical tourism is a rapidly growing sector with medical patients flying to developing countries for treatment. India is ranked 5th in the world and 2nd in Asia behind Singapore. (Medical Tourism Index, 2016) According to the Medical Tourism Association (MTA), the approximate costs of some medical procedures are:

Table No 6: Comparison of Cost Approximates of Some Medical Procedures

Medical Procedure	USA	Singapore	India
Heart Bypass	US\$ 123,000	US\$ 17,200	US\$ 7,900
Cataract surgery	US\$ 3,500	US\$ 3,250	US\$ 1,500
Spinal fusion	US\$ 110,000	US\$ 12,800	US\$ 10,300

Source: Medical Tourism Association, Report 2016

Indian medical tourism is estimated to be worth around US\$ 3 billion. Facilities like Visa-on-Arrival for medical tourists; low cost advantage; negligible linguistic barriers attract lakhs of medical patients to India annually and also offers AYUSH, acronym for Ayurveda, Yoga and Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha and Homoeopathy.

- **Hosting International Sporting Events:** Developing countries like Brazil and South Africa have gained tourists as they gathered global attention for being the venues of the FIFA world cup editions. An increase in the number of foreign tourists has been recorded not just in the year of hosting the games, but the growth is likely to continue for the future. South Africa, which hosted the FIFA world cup 2010, is a fine example of gaining more tourists from the exposure it got due to hosting a mega event. The table 7 clearly shows the positive impact the sporting mega event had on South African Tourism.

Table 7: Impact of Hosting International Sporting Events

Years	Foreign Tourists Arrival in South Africa	Percentage Growth
2007	9,208,000	8.21%
2008	9,729,000	5.65%
2009	10,098,000	3.79%
2010	11,575,000	14.62%
2011	12,496,000	7.95%
2012	13,796,000	10.40%
2013	15,155,000	9.85%

Source: Ministry of Tourism South Africa, Report, 2015

India also hosted the Commonwealth Games in 2010, Cricket World Cup in 2011, South Asian Games in 2016, Kabaddi World Cup in 2016 and the FIFA Under -17 World Cup in 2017 among other events. Apart from these, Indian Premier League (Cricket), Indian Super League (Football), Hockey India League and Pro Wrestling League are organized annually which attract the sports lovers around the world. India is also bidding to host the 2032 Olympics and 2030 Asian Games which will be a huge boost for the tourism sector of the country.

- **Adventure Tourism:** India also caters the interests of those who travel to seek thrill and adventure. Biking on mountainous terrains, rafting, camping, visiting wildlife sanctuaries, India offers multiple options for adventure tourism, a rapidly growing segment of tourism in India. Nielsen Report (2016) submitted to Ministry of Tourism stated that as high as 4,58,273 adventure tourists visited different adventure sites in India that generated a total of Rs. 477.235 crores in the year 2015. Ministry of Tourism has also released guidelines for maintaining safety standards at places that offer adventure sports, water sports, skiing and mountaineering. (Adventure Tourism Market Study in India, 2016)
- **New Avenues for Tourism:** Educational tourism is an increasingly popular trend in global tourism industry. Educational tourism is defined as traveling for the purpose of acquiring knowledge and learning experience. India had been a center for learning since ancient times when scholars used to visit the universities of Nalanda and Taxila for study on Buddhism, medicine, economics and various other disciplines. Because of its quality education system, India attracts foreign student from different Asian as well as African countries. By developing world class educational institutions and infrastructure, India can become a major center for education around the world. Another avenue which is witnessing rapid growth globally is Culinary Tourism or Gastronomical Tourism. With food lovers ready to travel to new lands to satisfy their taste buds, culinary tourism offers a great opportunity for India to diversify its offering to tourists. Similar to its geographical diversity, India offers diversity in cuisines as well. Tourists travelling from East to West or North to South India can taste widely different cuisine. “Incredible Tiffin” campaign was launched by the Cuisine Society of India in 2012 is aimed at showcasing the food varieties offered in India and was promoted at a global stage by packaging food into common tiffin boxes. More campaigns like “Incredible tiffin” should be launched to promote local food in different parts of world.

Major Issues and Challenges of Tourism Sector in India

While Indian Tourism industry has enjoyed appreciative growth in the 21st century, there have been certain noticeable causes that have hindered its exceptional boom. These challenges must be identified and strongly dealt with so that they do not obstruct Indian tourism industry’s flourish. Some of these challenges are as follows:

- **Threat of Terrorism:** As major European cities of Barcelona, Brussels, Paris and London were recently targeted by the terrorists, terrorism has taken a center stage in global discussions. Tourist places have been attacked by terrorists across the globe. These attacks have impact which could last for years as they destabilize the system by terrorizing the general public. The impact is high on areas

which are tourism dependent. In India, Jammu and Kashmir, known as “Switzerland of east” is crippled by these terrorist attacks. Frequent attacks not only pose a serious security threats to the tourists but also destroy the beauty of the destination.

- **Over Tourism:** Indian monuments have also been suffering from the irresponsible behavior of visitors. Monuments have faced issues of vandalism, defacing walls, littering and spit marks around the heritage sites. At times, Over Tourism also hurts the natural and cultural heritage. The 2013 floods in North India had adverse effects on religious places like *Kedarnath* because of the over population and concentration of commercial activities around the shrine. The state of Uttarakhand, well known for the religious places and famous hill stations, was hit by severe floods in June 2013. The natural calamity that rocked the *Kedarnath* shrine also discouraged tourist arrivals in the beautiful states. The table 8 shows the tourist arrivals in Uttarakhand and how they still struggle to touch the 2012 mark of foreign tourist arrivals. This calls for Sustainable Tourism, which expects a more responsible behavior by the tourists so as to protect the heritage for future.

Table 8: Profile of Tourists invisited Uttarakhand

Year	Domestic Tourists	Foreign Tourists
2012	26,827,329	124,555
2013	19,941,128	97,683
2014	21,991,315	101,966
2015	29,496,938	105,882

Source: Indian Tourism Statistics, Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India

Security Concerns in India: According to Crime in India Report 2016, number of cases against foreign tourists was: 384 cases in the year 2014, 271 cases in the year 2015 and 284 cases in the year 2016. UK Government’s website cautions the British women travelling to India about the rising number of sexual attacks and harassment cases against female tourists in Delhi, Bangalore, Goa and Rajasthan. It also carries an advisory as to how women should follow the local dress code and how they must conduct so that they are safe on their journey to the Indian subcontinent. The cases of frauds and loot against foreigners have also surfaced recently.

Conclusions and Suggestions

Foreign Tourist Arrivals (FTA) in India, key indicator of tourism industry performance, has increased from 2.38 million in 2002 to 8.80 million in 2016 at a compounded annual average growth rate of 9.79%. The analysis of last 15 years show that the month of December attracts foreign tourists the most while May is the least favorable month for the tourism industry. The foreign exchange earnings (FEE) from the tourism sector rose from US\$ 3,103 million in 2002 to US\$ 22,923 million in 2016 at a compounded annual average growth rate of 15%. The coefficient of determination between FTA and FEE is 0.9882. Hosting mega sporting events has boosted the tourism industry in developing countries. The terrorism has negatively impacted the attraction of tourist destinations. There are no doubts that tourism industry plays a significant role in economic and social development of the country. Although we witness rising trends in the tourist arrival numbers, India is still away from cementing its position as top tourist destination in the world. The Government of India is focusing on its objectives and framing policies for the fulfillment of their goals, but external threats in form of terrorism and over tourism might act as hindrance in their future plans. Few suggestions that may help in overcoming these threats are:

1. Strict actions to put an end to the crimes against foreign nationals are in need. Due to the increase in number of crimes such as sexual assaults on women, India’s image has been tarnished. The frequency of such attacks increase during the peak season. For this some special arrangements must be made. The authorities must be trained to provide help to female foreign tourists. (Shekhar, Kumar, & Attri, 2017)
2. There is requirement of crisis management policy. It should include a guide for tourists as well as the authorities about the actions that should be taken in case of terrorist attacks. India should also identify the ethnicity of foreign tourists visiting and identify the probable communities which are most vulnerable. Special emphasis should be made to protect these communities.
3. New destinations must be explored so that the burden on some famous destinations could be reduced. There is a need to assess the “Carrying Capacity” of the famous tourist places.

4. If burden of the over exploited tourist spots should be shifted to unexplored places that could act as suitable alternative. The policymakers should utilize the economic and statistical methods such as “Destination Discontinuity Model”, “Destination Branding” for this purpose.(Rana & Nagar, 2015)
5. Sporting infrastructure should be developed and high capacity stadiums should be build in order to strengthen India’s bid to host International mega sporting events that have proven to be tourism boosters for developing economies.
6. India can brand itself as a cuisine tourism leader with such diverse food items prepared around the country. Strategies should be formulated to maintain the essence of the cuisines by marketing them in respect of their places of origin.
7. India must carefully study the policies and initiatives taken by countries who are optimally utilising their tourism industry’s potential and learn lessons from nations whose tourism markets have perished in due to their negligence.
8. India can also reap the early benefits of rising trends in the tourism sphere by investing in adventure, agro, eco tourism etc.

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Contribution of Beach Shacks to the Government Exchequer in Goa: An Empirical Study

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Abstract

Goa a tiny State on India's west coast with a population of 1.5 million as per the 2011 census attracts millions of tourists every year. Tourists get attracted towards the State as it offers several tourist attractions like beautiful white sandy beaches, historical churches, temples, waterfalls, wildlife sanctuaries, and its unique Portuguese influence culture. The inflow of tourists provides revenue to the government in the form of various fees and taxes and leads to the development of new tourist attractions such as the beach shacks. Shacks are temporary seasonal restaurants, erected on the beach, within zero to five hundred meters from the high tide line of the sea, serving mostly Goan food and beverages to the tourists. In this paper, an attempt has been made to find out the contribution of shacks to the State government exchequer as well as to other tourism-related departments in Goa over the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17. This paper is based on a study conducted during the months of March to June 2017. The data for the study was collected personally by preparing and serving a structured questionnaire to the Department of Tourism, Government of Goa, other tourism-related departments, and from ten selected shack owners in Goa. Statistical tools like simple regression analysis, and one-way ANOVA is used in this study. The results suggest that shacks located in government properties have not made any significant contribution to the State government exchequer over the last five years. However, shacks located in private properties have made a significant contribution to the State government exchequer in Goa. Also, shacks have made a significant contribution to the revenue generation efforts of various other tourism-related departments in the state.

Keywords: *Beach shacks, Revenue, Government Exchequer and Contribution.*

Introduction

Goa - a mini State on India's west coast with a population of 1.5 million as per the 2011 census attracts millions of tourists every year. In fact, during the year 2016, the State received 6330744 tourists including 680683 foreign (Department of Tourism, Government of Goa, Statistics). Tourists get attracted towards the State as it offers several tourist attractions like beautiful white sandy beaches, historical churches, temples, waterfalls, wildlife sanctuaries, and its unique Portuguese influenced culture. The inflow of tourists provides revenue to the government in the form of various fees and taxes, employment to the locals and it also leads to the development of new tourist attractions such as the beach shacks. Shacks in Goa had originated in the mid-sixties when the western hippies discovered the virgin beaches of Goa (Kazi, et al, 2004). Shacks are temporary seasonal restaurants, erected on the beach, within zero to five hundred meters from the high tide line of the sea, serving mostly Goan food and beverages to the tourists (Sathish et al., 2016). They are erected by using locally available eco-friendly materials and are open for business from September to May every year. Initially, they were licensed by the local village Panchayats and in most cases favored applications from the village itself (Noronha et al, 2003).

However, this system of allocation leads to conflicts and misunderstanding among the applicants (Kazi et al., 2004). Therefore, in the year 1997, the State government through the Department of Tourism came out with a 'Beach Shack Policy' and took over licensing of beach shacks in Goa. As per the beach shack policy, the government decides about the number of shacks to be permitted on various beach stretches in Goa every year based on its carrying capacities. It also controls and monitors the functioning of shacks in the State and ensures that they operate as per the rules and regulations as specified in the beach shack policy of the State government from time to time. Shacks in Goa are located both in government as well as in private properties and the later provide accommodation to the tourists close to the beach during the tourist season. In every society, government plays the role of an administrator and facilitator by providing people the basic infrastructure to carry on trade, business, and other activities. It also frames rules, regulations, guidelines, and procedures under which such activities are to be carried on. In return, the government collects fees and taxes from its people who have profited due to its work. Shack business in

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Goa is one such activity which is being effectively monitored, managed, and controlled by the government through the Department of Tourism and it contributes to the government exchequer in the form of various taxes and fees every year.

Review of Literature

Tourism the world over benefits people by providing employment to the locals, bringing in foreign exchange, improves terms of trade, boost domestic demand, improves social services, and contributes to higher economic growth (Andriotis, 2002, Kweka et al, 2003, Rajesh, 2009, Roy, 2011, Federico, 2015 & Mrema, 2015). It also contributes to the development of infrastructure, generates income, and leads to the appreciation of the value of local properties (Nayomi et al, 2015). The hospitality industry the world over is mostly managed by large international hospitality firms, which import managerial workers as well as cheaper food from neighboring countries whereas, the smaller hospitality firms employ more family members and purchases all their requirements locally (Andriotis, 2002). Therefore, the state governments must promote and encourage smaller hospitality firms for the benefit of its people as they help to develop the local economy. According to Mckercher (2010), tourism cannot be isolated from the local community as the local communities completely depend on it for its survival. In fact, the local community needs to be educated about the potential benefits of tourism to obtain their support and involvement (D’Mello et al., 2015). The purpose as to why tourists visit a destination varies from person to person. At times they visit a destination because they get attached to it due to several factors like its natural beauty, satisfactory past experiences and the propensity to explore new items at the destination (George et al, 2004). A satisfied tourist will talk positively about the destination to his colleagues, family, friends, and neighbors, whereas a highly satisfied tourist will visit the destination repeatedly irrespective of the cost (George et al, 2004). According to Menezes (2015), a large number of tourists prefer to visit Goa, including repeat tourists, in spite of higher airfares and hotel room rates because this is one place in India which is open-minded, tolerant and easy-going where everyone is respected.

However, the tourism sector has its own share of problems. The Major problems faced by developing countries in the tourism sector are seasonal employment, inflation, environmental pollution, crowding, traffic congestion, extinction of traditional occupations and limited foreign currency flows (Ardahaey, 2011, Diniz et al, 2014 & Styliadis et al., 2014). According to Noronha (1999), the problems faced by Goans due to tourism are, increase in coastal land prices, conversion of agricultural and forest land, drug abuse, drug trafficking, prostitution, and escalation in violence. The other problems of tourism seen in Goa are environmental degradation, urbanization of coastal villages, overcrowding of beaches, and issue of garbage (Solomon, 2009). Tourism is also responsible for destroying Goa’s sand dunes over the years (Mundy, 2017). According to Mundy (2017), sand dunes act as a beach first line of defense against the forces of the ocean like cyclones and tsunamis. However, it is possible to overcome all the above problems through proper short-term and long-term planning which is presently lacking in most of the tourist places including States like Goa.

Identification of the Research Problem

Literature survey conducted by the researcher so far throws light to the fact that, no substantial research has been conducted till date to study the contribution of beach shacks to the State government exchequer in Goa and this makes the present study significant. Every year, the state government in Goa gives permission to erect over three hundred shacks in government properties and over two hundred shacks in private properties during the tourist season (Department of Tourism – Government of Goa, Statistics). However, no major study has been conducted so far to find out the monetary contribution of shacks to the State government exchequer – Department of Tourism and to other tourism-related departments in Goa. Therefore, this paper tries to fill up the gap by finding out the contribution of shacks to the government exchequer as well as to other tourism-related departments in Goa over the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17. The paper also offers valuable inputs to the State Government - Department of Tourism, and other stakeholders in their areas of informational needs.

Research Questions

The following research questions emerge from the above objectives:

1. What is the revenue earned by the State government in Goa from shacks located both in government as well as in private properties?
2. Whether shacks located in government properties are contributing more to the government exchequer as compare to shacks located in private properties in Goa?
3. What is the average contribution of shacks to the total revenue earned by the Department of Tourism – Government of Goa, over the last five years till 2016-17?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the present study is to find out the monetary contribution of shacks, located both in government as well as in private properties, to the state government exchequer in Goa over the last five years till 2016-17. However, the specific objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To find out the monetary contribution of shacks, located both in government and private properties, to the State government exchequer over the last five years in Goa till 2016-17.
2. To find out the monetary contribution of shacks to other tourism-related departments in Goa over the last five years till 2016-17.
3. To compare the revenues earned by the government from shack business to that of the total revenues of the Department of Tourism in Goa so as to find out the importance of shack business in the State in terms of the revenues generated by it.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses of the study are as follows:

- H₀₁: Shacks located in government properties have not made any significant contribution to the State Government Exchequer over the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17.
- H₁₁: Shacks located in government properties have made a significant contribution to the State Government Exchequer over the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17.
- H₀₂: Shacks located in private properties have not made any significant contribution to the State Government Exchequer over the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17.
- H₁₂: Shacks located in private properties have made a significant contribution to the State Government Exchequer over the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17.

Research Methodology

The data for the study was collected by using primary as well as secondary sources. Primary data was collected from the Department of Tourism - Government of Goa by conducting a detailed interview of the Director of Tourism, two Assistant Directors of Tourism, two revenue officers, and one Officer-On-Special Duty (OSD) from the same department. Primary data was also collected from other tourism-related departments like Excise, Commercial Tax, Fire, and Health and also by interviewing ten selected shack owners doing business both in government as well as in private properties in Goa. The sampling method used was judgment sampling where the researcher has selected total ten shack owners from Goa including one female shack owner and conducted an in-depth interview with them to collect the required data. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaire was personally administered to the respondents at their place of work and office. Statistical tools like simple regression analysis and one-way ANOVA are used in this study to find out the contribution of shacks to the State government exchequer over the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17 in Goa. The researcher in this study has used only one independent variable to predict the value of the dependent variable, in both the regression tables; as such a simple regression analysis only has been used. The secondary data was collected from Travel and Tourism Hospitality Journals, newspaper articles, The Department of Tourism – Government of Goa, and other printed and online materials.

Shacks in Goa are temporary restaurants which are erected on the beach both in private as well as in Government properties every year. Usually, they cater to the tourists during the tourist season in the State which is from September to May. This study is an attempt to find out the importance of shack business in Goa in terms of the revenue generated by them to the State government exchequer over the last five years till 2016-17. The present study pertains to a period of five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17.

In this area of study, the researcher has two dependent variables as follows 1) Total revenue earned by the government from shacks located in government properties and 2) Total revenue earned by the government from shacks located in private properties. The independent variable for the first dependent variable is, the total number of shacks located in government properties during the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17 and for the second dependent variable it is, the total number of shacks located in private properties in Goa during the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17.

Results and Analysis

Table 1: Revenue earned per Shack from Government Property (in rupees)

Sr. No.	Particulars	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
1.	Application Form Fees	3,000	9,000	-	-	9,000
2.	License Fees: Category A	45,000	50,000	55,000	60,000	60,000
	Category B	30,000	35,000	40,000	45,000	45,000
3.	Sun Bed Fees	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000
4.	Fire Department Fees	500	500	500	500	500
5.	Food & Drugs Fees	150	300	300	300	500
6.	PWD Water Connection Fees	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,200
7.	Electricity Department Fees	300	300	300	300	390
8.	Health Dept. NOC Fees	300	300	300	300	300
9.	Excise License Fees	8,000	8,000	8,000	8,000	14,000
10.	Goa Air pollution board fees	1,200	1,200	1,200	1,200	1,500
11.	Commercial Tax	15,000	25,000	25,000	25,000	25,000
12.	Panchayat Trade License Fees	5,000	5,000	5,000	5,000	5,000
	Total: Category A	89,450	1,10,600	1,06,600	1,11,600	1,27,390
	Category B	74,450	95,600	91,600	96,600	1,12,390

Source: Compiled from primary data and the Beach Shack policy for years 2012-13, 2013-16 & 2016-19

Table no. 1 above shows that, over the last five years, 2012-13 to 2016-17, there has been a 42.42 percent and 50.96 percent increase in the fees paid by a shack located on government property and belonging to Category 'A' and 'B' respectively. It also shows the major sources of revenue to the government from shacks located in government properties and they are license fees, sun bed fees, excise license fees, commercial tax and Panchayat trade license fees. Also, as seen above, most of the fees paid by a shack to the government have remained fixed over the years. During the year 2013-14, the State government has introduced three years Beach Shack Policy. Accordingly, the shack owners have to deposit the entire three years application form fees to the government in advance during the first year itself resulting in a higher collection in the first year and zero collection during the next two subsequent years from this particular source.

Table no. 2 below shows that, there has been a 57.06 percent increase in the total revenue collected by the State government from shacks in government properties over the years 2012-13 to 2016-17. Among the various sources of revenue, the contribution from license fees is the highest over the years. However, even though the contribution from other sources to the state government exchequer is less, it is quite significant and important because it adds to the revenue generation efforts of the respective departments. Also, the Panchayats from the coastal areas of Goa earn substantial revenue every year from shacks in the form of trade license fees. However, the revenue collected from application form fees during the two years 2014-15 and 2015-16 is substantially low because this particular collection has come only from the additional shacks permitted by the Department of Tourism for the respective years.

Table no. 3 below shows that, there has been a 4.63 percent decline in the total revenue collected by the government from a shack doing business in private properties in Goa over the years 2012-13 to 2016-17. The main reason for the decline is the non-collection of license and sun bed fees by the department of tourism from shacks during the last three years from 2014-15 to 2016-17. In fact, the department of tourism has not permitted any shack operator to erect shack in private properties in Goa over the last three years, 2014-15 to 2016-17, due to an order from the Coastal Regulation Zone (CRZ) regarding the demolishing of illegal structures erected in violation of CRZ rules. However, in spite of the CRZ order, numbers of shacks were erected in private properties at Agonda, Palolem, Morjim, and Arambol during the above period, bypassing the department of tourism order, but with permission from the local village Panchayats, Goa Coastal Zone Management Authority (GCZMA), and Excise Department. Therefore,

due to the CRZ order, the Department of Tourism and the State government has lost substantial revenue from private shacks during the last three years in the form of license fees and sun bed fees. However, the GCZMA, on the other hand, has earned substantial revenue from shacks during the last three years by permitting them to do business and collecting restaurant and room license fees from them.

Table 2: Total revenue earned from shacks in government properties (in rupees)

Sr. No.	Particulars	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	Change last 5 years
1	Number of Shacks: Category A Category B Total	225 104 329	233 104 337	273 104 377	282 104 386	260 104 364	10.64%
2	Application Form Fees	9,87,000	30,33,000	2,40,000	27,000	32,76,000	
3	License Fees: Category A Category B Total(A + B)	101,25,000 31,20,000 132,45,000	116,50,000 36,40,000 152,90,000	150,15,000 41,60,000 191,75,000	169,20,000 46,80,000 216,00,000	156,00,000 46,80,000 202,80,000	53.11%
4	Sun Bed Fees	32,90,000	23,30,000	27,30,000	28,20,000	26,00,000	-20.97%
5	Total to Tourism Department	175,22,000	206,53,000	221,45,000	244,47,000	261,56,000	49.28%
6	Fire Department Fees	1,64,500	1,68,500	1,88,500	1,93,000	1,82,500	10.94%
7	Food & Drugs Fees	49,350	1,01,100	1,13,100	1,15,800	1,82,000	268.79%
8	PWD Water connection fees	3,29,000	3,37,000	3,77,000	3,86,000	4,36,800	32.77%
9	Electricity Department fees	98,700	1,01,100	1,13,100	1,15,800	1,41,960	43.79%
10	Health Department NOC fees	98,700	1,01,100	1,13,100	1,15,800	1,09,200	10.64%
11	Excise License Fees	26,32,000	26,96,000	30,16,000	30,88,000	50,96,000	93.62%
12	Goa air pollution board fees	3,94,800	4,04,400	4,52,400	4,63,200	5,46,000	38.30%
13	Commercial Tax	49,35,000	84,25,000	94,25,000	96,50,000	91,00,000	84.4%
14	Panchayat Trade License Fees	16,45,000	16,85,000	18,85,000	19,30,000	18,20,000	10.64%
15	Gross Total	2,78,69,050	3,46,72,200	3,78,28,200	4,05,04,600	4,37,70,460	57.06%

Source: Compiled from primary data and the Beach Shack Policy for the years 2012-13, 2013-16 & 2016-19.

Table 3: Revenue earned from one shack located in Private Properties (in rupees)

S. No.	Particulars	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
1.	License fees	20,000	20,000	-	-	-
2.	Sun bed fees	5,000	5,000	-	-	-
3.	Fire department fees	3,830	3,830	3,830	3,830	3,830
4.	Health department NOC fees	500	500	500	500	500
5.	Excise license fees	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000
6.	GCZMA fees a) restaurant b) Rooms	- - -	- - -	10,000 10,000	10,000 10,000	10,000 10,000
7.	Panchayat / Municipality NOC fees a) Restaurant b) Per Room *	10,500 870	10,500 870	10,500 1,800	10,500 2,500	10,500 3,500
8.	Garbage collection fees	500	500	500	500	500
	Total	51,200	51,200	47,130	47,830	48,830

Source: Compiled from primary data and the Beach Shack policy for the years 2012-13, 2013-16 & 2016-19.

Table 4: Total revenue collected from shacks in Private properties

Sr. No.	Particulars	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
1.	Number of shacks	286	120	08	171	113
2.	License fees	45,98,500	19,57,800	1,98,125	NIL	NIL
3.	Sun bed fees	14,30,000	6,00,000	40,000	NIL	NIL
4.	Fire department fees	10,95,380	4,59,600	30,640	6,54,930	4,32,790
5.	Health department NOC fees	1,43,000	60,000	4,000	85,500	56,500
6.	Excise license fees	28,60,000	12,00,000	80,000	17,10,000	11,30,000
7.	GCZMA Fees a) Restaurants b) Rooms	NIL NIL	NIL NIL	80,000 80,000	17,10,000 17,10,000	11,30,000 11,30,000
8.	Panchayat / Municipality NOC fees for Restaurant	30,03,000	12,60,000	84,000	17,95,500	11,86,500
9.	Panchayat / Municipality Garbage collection fees	1,43,000	60,000	4,000	85,500	56,500
	Total	132,72,880	55,97,400	6,00,765	77,51,430	51,22,290

Source: Compiled from primary data and the Beach Shack policy for the years 2012-13, 2013-16 & 2016-19.

In the above table no. 4 it is observed that the total revenue collected by the government from shacks doing business in private properties has gone down by 61.41 percent over the years 2012-13 to 2016-17. The reasons for the decline are, a drastic fall in the numbers of shacks permitted by the government in private properties, and also during the years 2014-15 to 2016-17 the government has not permitted any shack in private properties in Goa resulting in the Department of Tourism losing substantial revenue from shacks in the form of license fees and sun bed fees. However, even though the government has not collected license fees from shacks in private properties during the last three years, the shack operators have succeeded in doing business by paying fees to the GCZMA and the local Panchayats thereby providing them additional revenue as seen above.

Figure 1: Total Revenue earned from shacks located in government properties for the five years 2012-13 to 2016-17

Source: Drawn from Primary Data

In figure no. 1 it is observed that the license fees have contributed the maximum of 49 percent to the total revenue earned by the government – Department of Tourism from shacks located in government properties over the last five years till 2016-17. Shacks located in government properties also make a significant contribution to various other government departments such as commercial tax department 23 percent, excise department 9 percent, and to the Department of Tourism in the form of sun bed fees 7 percent. They also add to the revenue generation efforts of several other departments like the fire department, food & drugs, PWD, electricity, health, pollution, and Panchayats. However, the contribution from shacks to food & drugs, electricity department and health department is less than one percent each.

In figure 2 it is observed that the major sources of revenue to the government from shacks located on private properties during the last five years till 2016-17 are license fees 21 percent, excise fees 22 percent and sun bed fees 6 percent. However, it is the Village Panchayats located in the coastal areas who have gained more from these particular shacks. In fact, of the total revenue collected by the government from shacks located in private properties in Goa during the above period, the share of the Panchayats alone in the form of fees is 23 percent which is one among the highest. Besides this, the Panchayats also collect additional one percent in the form of garbage collection fees from shacks. The earnings of other government departments from private shacks include GCZMA 18 percent (in the form of restaurant and room fees), fire department 8 percent and health department one percent.

Table no. 5 below shows the result of simple regression analysis and the results are found to be not acceptable at a significance level of 0.05 ($P > 0.05$). The R square value of .604 indicates that there exists a relationship between the independent variables and the analysis is found to be acceptable. The adjusted R square value of .472 indicates that 47.2% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the regression analysis. It also means that 52.8% of the variation in the dependent variable is due to unknown factors. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{01} : “Shacks located in government properties have not made any

significant contribution to the State Government Exchequer over the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17” is accepted.

Figure2: Total Revenue earned from shacks in Private properties for the five years 2012-13 to 2016-17

Source: Drawn from Primary data

Table 5: Revenue earned from shacks in government properties

Table 5a: Simple Regression Analysis

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Sig.
.777	.604	.472	4413570.686	.122

Table 5b: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.914	1	8.914	4.576	.122
	Residual	5.844	3	1.948		
	Total	1.476	4			

Table 5 c: Unstandardized Coefficients

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	-31314957.35	31963662.88		-.980	.399
Total shacks in government properties	190306.356	88964.478	.777	2.139	.122

Table 6: Revenue earned from shacks in private properties

Table 6a: Simple Regression Analysis

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Sig.
1.000	.999	.999	157809.567	.000

Table 6b: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.487	1	8.487	3407.994	.000
	Residual	74711578059	3	24903859353		
	Total	8.495	4			

Table 6c: Unstandardized Coefficients

Independent variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	104183.225	129875.392		.802	.481
Total shacks in private properties	45592.907	780.994	1.000	58.378	.000

Table no. 6 above shows the result of simple regression analysis and the results are found to be acceptable at a significance level of 0.05 ($P < 0.05$). The R square value of .999 indicates that there exists a relationship between the independent variables and the analysis is found to be acceptable. The adjusted R square value of .999 indicates that 99.9% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the regression analysis. Hence, the null hypothesis $H0_2$: “Shacks located in private properties has not made any significant contribution to the State Government Exchequer over the last five years from 2012-13 to

2016-17” is not accepted. This also means that shacks located in private properties have made a significant contribution to the state government exchequer over the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17.

Table 7: Share of income from shacks to the total revenue earned by the Department of Tourism from 2012-13 to 2016-17

Year	Total Revenue	Revenue from Shacks (License Fees & Application Form Fees)	% of shack revenue to total revenue
2012-13	3,18,00,000	2,35,50,500	74.06%
2013-14	5,81,00,000	2,32,10,800	39.95%
2014-15	11,78,00,000	2,23,83,125	19%
2015-16	6,73,00,000	2,44,47,000	36.33%
2016-17	3,58,00,000	2,61,56,000	73.06%
Total	31,08,00,000	11,97,47,425	38.53%

Source: Compiled from primary data

As seen in table no. 7 above, beach shacks the temporary restaurants which operate only for nine months of the year, from September to May, have contributed to an average 38.53 percent to the total revenue earned by the Department of Tourism – Government of Goa during the years 2012-13 to 2016-17. The above contribution from shacks is quite substantial depending on the nature and type of the shack business in the State. Also, during the years 2012-13 and 2016-17, the contribution of shacks to the total revenue of the Department of Tourism is above 70 percent which signifies the importance of shack business to the government in Goa in terms of the revenue it generates. While calculating the revenue earned from shacks, the researcher has taken only license fees and application form fees as these two sources of income directly go to the Department of Tourism.

Conclusion

The State government collects every year a fixed amount of money from each shack in the form of fees depending upon their location. Shacks located in category ‘A’ pay higher fees as compare to category ‘B’ shacks because they have higher footfalls and are located at the most popular beaches in Goa. Therefore, higher the number of shacks more is the revenue generation for the government during the year. But, in order to generate higher revenues, the State government simply cannot permit more shacks beyond a particular limit. Also, during the last three years (2014-15 to 2016-17), the State government due to CRZ order has not permitted shacks to operate in private properties in Goa affecting the revenues of the Department of Tourism – Government of Goa during the above years. However, in spite of the order, shacks continued their business by taking permissions from GCZMA and the local Panchayats during the above three years. In Goa, shacks are located both in government as well as in private properties and they contribute to the government exchequer in the form of various taxes and fees like application form fees, license fees, sun bed fees, fire department fees, PWD fees for water connection, electricity fees, Panchayat fees, excise, and commercial tax. However, among all the above sources of revenue, the contribution from license fees to the State government exchequer is the highest.

In this study, it is observed that shacks located in government properties have not made any significant contribution to the state government exchequer over the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17 as its coefficient value is found to be non-significant at a significance level of 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). However, they have contributed higher revenues to the state government exchequer during each of the last five years as compared to private shacks. Shacks located in private properties have made a significant contribution to the state government exchequer during the last five years from 2012-13 to 2016-17 as its coefficient value is found to be significant at a significance level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). However, there is an overall drop in the total revenue collected by the government from these shacks over the last five years due to a decrease in their numbers and the CRZ order regarding the demolishing of illegal shacks erected in private properties. Due to CRZ order, the state government has not permitted shacks in private properties during the last three years from 2014-15 to 2016-17. But many shack operators by just applying for licenses to the Department of Tourism have erected shacks without paying any license fees to the government during the above three years but with the permission of the local Panchayats and GCZMA.

The researcher has also compared the total revenues of the Department of Tourism with that of its earnings from shacks over the last five years. In doing this comparison, it is observed that the average

contribution from shacks in the form of application form fees and license fees during the last five years till 2016-17 is 38.53% which is quite substantial depending upon the nature and type of shack business in Goa. Also, shacks have made a significant contribution to the revenue generation efforts of various other government departments in the State connected to tourism like Commercial Tax Department, Excise, Panchayats, Pollution Control Board, PWD, Electricity Department, Health Department, Food & Drugs, and Fire Department. Therefore, the government must protect and support the shack business in the State.

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Sustainable Water Management in Hotels: What Leadership Quality is Required?

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Abstract

Sustainable development is fast becoming a world order of today. Every sector, including business, is expected to play a role in addressing social and environmental issues. As tourism and environment are essentially intertwined in a mutually beneficial relationship, it is vital for all tourism players to take leadership role in environmental issues. This is especially true because of their potential to accumulatively add negative impacts on the environment. Within the context of water management, hotels play more important role because the availability of clean water is a global concern and its deficiency could threaten the sustainability of the hotel industry. This paper focuses on the issue of water management in the hotel sector with the ultimate aim to propose a leadership quality that could help the industry move closer towards sustainable water management. It discusses the outcomes of the authors' earlier empirical study, which pointed towards 'managerial will' as a crucial factor if the hotel industry were to become more environmentally friendly. The paper begins by describing the need for a positive role of hotels in environmental issues. Then it describes the said empirical work by explaining the problem it addresses, the objectives, the methodology and the results. The paper then highlights and discusses an important outcome of the said study i.e. the need for hotel managers to have managerial will in order to become more active in environmental management of their industry. The implications of the outcome as well as strategies or policy environment that could nurture it are discussed at the end of the paper.

Keywords: *Hotels, water management, corporate social responsibility, environmental management, resource consumption*

Introduction

In the quest towards sustainable tourism development, all businesses in the tourism and hospitality industry are expected to play a role in addressing social and environmental issues. As tourism growth is dependent on the aesthetics and functionality of the natural environment, it is vital for all tourism players to learn how to co-exist with their environment to ensure a sustainable future. Hotels as a key player in the industry, plays a pivotal role in environmental issues due to their potential to accumulatively affect the natural environment in adverse manner. This is especially true within the context of water management. With the recent one billionth international tourists recorded, tourism is without a doubt the largest and fastest growing industry in the world (UNWTO, 2013) with measureable economic, socio-cultural and ecological impacts. One of the ecological impacts will be hotels' increased water use. Growth in tourists' arrival in tourism destinations means growth in tourism amenities such as hotels and resorts, golf courses, water related recreation facilities and others. Unless hotels are committed to environmental management, they will contribute a massive amount of environmental impacts in the form of water consumption and water pollution. The responsibility is obvious especially among big hotels and resorts due to the obviously high amount of water required for their operation. However, smaller hotels and other accommodation providers can also collectively exert such impact. Hence, a more serious attention on sustainable water management is warranted. It is important to encourage as many hotels as possible to play bigger role ensuring sustainable water consumption and management.

However, despite the global concern about the availability of clean water and its possible negative implication to the sustainability of industry including hotels, the industry's response has been relatively slow due to barriers ranging from lack of awareness to lack of resources to implement responsible behaviours and practices (Hillary, 1999; Jenkins, 2006b; Kasim, 2006; Kasim, 2009). This is particularly true in the context of responsible water management. Availability of clean water is a global concern. It is a threat to the sustainability of industry including hotels. A more serious businesses' role in water management is warranted. Hotels are major water consumers because people tend to use more water when they stay at hotels. Thus it is important to encourage hotels to be more innovative in managing their water use.

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Objective

This paper is a position paper that draws from an empirical study that the authors had completed. Its objective is to highlight the kind of leadership/managerial quality required to drive hotels towards sustainable water management as well as some possible policy implications of it.

The main objectives of the empirical study were to uncover the influence of firm characteristics to hotels' environmental responsiveness, the influence of environmental knowledge level on environmental responsiveness, and the influence of financial resources to environmental commitment. It used mixed methodology but it was the qualitative data that highlighted the importance of one key leadership attribute for stronger hotel involvement in environmental management i.e. Managerial Will. Therefore, for the purpose of this paper, the focus will only be on the qualitative data, which was gathered to answer the following research questions:

- How important is water to a hotel's operation?
- How important is it to manage water use in a hotel's operation and why?
- Do you believe that hotel size (number of rooms, number of beds, number of employees) can influence how a hotel respond to water management?
- Do other hotel characteristics (hotel type, business type, location, ownership) influence a hotel response to water management?
- Does a manager's environmental awareness affect how a hotel respond to water management?
- Do managers' environmental knowledge affect how a hotel respond to water management?
- Do you believe that formal education in environment could influence how a hotel respond to water management?
- How important is money in innovatively addressing water management issues and why?
- Is there any water management innovation that does not require big capital investment?

Research Design and Methodology

The paper starts by reviewing the literature on the importance of water management before proceeding to explain the empirical study and summarize the empirical findings. The empirical study that this position paper relies on used an in-depth semi structured interview of selected hotel experts from hotel trade associations. This approach was found to be useful in trying to understand all of its objectives especially the influence of financial capability on innovative water management responsiveness due to the usual difficulty of soliciting potentially confidential information involving company dollars and expenditure.

Semi structured interviews were conducted to gather the qualitative data. The solicited information was developed based on the quantitative survey as well as other points of interests that the researchers found in the literature. Hotel managers or their appointed representatives were interviewed to understand further the relationship between firm characteristics, environmental knowledge and financial capability with innovative water management responsiveness. Some strategies were adopted and implemented during the research process to maintain trustworthiness of the qualitative inquiry, including; "confirming the results with the participants" (Morse et al., 2002), and "member checks" (Ratcliff, 1995). Lincoln and Guba (1985) describe member checks as "the most crucial technique for establishing credibility" in a study of qualitative research as it is increasingly seen as a way of demonstrating rigour. In order to fulfil this requirement, each research site was visited again to validate the accuracy of the findings. In addition, the original data have been utilised systematically in the presentation of results to show authentic interpretations of data. For this purpose, a range of quotations were selected from responses to illustrate key features such as, the strength of opinion or belief, similarities and differences between respondents, and the breadth of ideas expressed during the stage of the data collection. The interviews were recorded using a digital voice recorder. Hancock (1998) suggestion that it may not be essential to transcribe every interview was heeded. Hancock (1998) advocates applying "a technique known as tape analysis..." which, involves replaying the tape recording of an interview and making notes of relevant and interesting data. This tape analysis was performed for the unstructured interviews. While listening to the audio

tracks of those interviews, the notes were taken of the sections which contain particularly useful information and key quotations for the use of analysis.

The interview process was successfully completed with the participation of fourteen hotel managers from hotels of various characteristics and sizes (See Table 1). The interviews lasted between 40 to 60 minutes each. The interview data was transcribed and manually analyzed using thematic analysis i.e. establishing common themes under each major issue investigated.

Table 1: Sample Distribution / Background of the Hotel the Informants Represented

	Frequency
Hotel Rating	
No star	6
2 star	4
3 star	3
4 star	1
Type of Hotel	
Budget hotel in city area	4
Regular hotel in city area	3
Budget hotel in non-city area	5
Regular hotel in non-city area	2
No of Room	
Less than 50	6
50 -100	4
100-150	2
150-200	2
No of Employees	
<50	7
50 -100	5
100-150	2
Ownership	
Local	10
International	4
Type of Business	
Stand alone	12
Local Franchise	2
Location of Hotel	
In the coastal area	6
In the mountain or hilly areas	2
Others (urban areas)	6

The thematic analysis involved coding i.e. laboriously generating initial categories and the relationships among the categories (see: Strauss & Corbin, 1998). Coding is considered to be a dynamic and fluid process that can be broken down into three levels of activity: Open, Axial and Selective coding (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). As the goal of analysis is to generate meaning from data or the findings (Miles & Huberman, 1984), open coding is a process used to generate meaning by identifying concepts and their properties and dimensions from the data (LeCompte & Schensul, 1999). It begins with sifting and sorting through the transcriptions, comparing and contrasting the conversational comments as well as the themes within the data before putting together those items that were similar and separating out those that were different. In this process the researchers ran carefully through each transcript, and the notes written to explain what was captured from the hoteliers. Strauss & Corbin (1990) refer to open coding as the part of the analysis that pertains specifically to the naming and categorizing of phenomenon through close examination of the data. Using the constant comparison analysis method, the coded concepts were refined, extended and cross-referenced with the data as a whole and related to each other. Once the concepts began to accumulate, the process of grouping and categorizing them with more abstract explanatory terms called categories was conducted. Categories depict the problems, issues, concern, and matters that are important to this study. Once a category was identified, the researchers began to develop it in terms of its properties and dimensions and differentiating the subcategories. Subcategories answer questions about the phenomenon as when, how, and with what consequences (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). This process generated a number of different categories into which the data could be grouped.

In the second process i.e. Axial Coding, attempts were made to classify, illustrate, and connect these categories more closely to feel their importance in the general pattern of the data gained from the learners, and how these data interrelated. As themes and patterns began to emerge from the data, a pattern analysis was done. Strauss & Corbin (1990) describe as axial coding which they refer to as: a set of procedures whereby data are put back together in new ways after open coding by making connections between a category and its subcategories. A structural analysis involving linking together and finding consistent relationships among patterns and structure was completed. Throughout the analysis, some counting was done to give an idea of the density and frequency of the main categories and sub-categories. The reason was that this research found some of the informants interviewed more vocal and succinct than others. They were easy to engage in conversation. Some kept repeating the key word, and others expressed the same opinion just as strongly, only using the word or phrase once. However, the researchers were always cautious in making such counts especially in qualitative research. This research has to admit that it was a very imprecise activity, because sometimes the respondents expressed an opinion without using the key word that the researchers had chosen for counting. The research included this in the counting, but obviously this was a matter of the researcher's judgment. Despite some problems, the process of counting did generate some interesting and useful results that gave some broad indications rather than specific measurements. As time went by, it became clearer that the data was saturated, in the sense that Glaser & Strauss describe.

The final process i.e. Selective Coding is defined by Strauss & Corbin (1990) as a process of selecting the core category, systematically relating it to other categories, validating those relationships, and filling in categories that need further refinement and development. From the many categories uncovered throughout the analysis process, only the core category has the explanatory power. Therefore identifying the core category is crucial. Once identified, it was refined through reviewing for internal consistency and gaps in logic, supplementing any poorly developed categories, and reducing excess categories that do little to contribute to the understanding of the issue at hand (Strauss & Corbin, 1998).

The thematic analysis described above revealed the following findings. Under the first research question i.e. to establish the importance of water to a hotel operation, the word 'important' and 'very important' emerged because water is considered 'essential' to a hotel operation. Below are some excerpts on this:

"We need water every day for cleaning and the kitchen."

Informant M

"It is a basic necessity...especially for guest use and for cleaning the general areas..."

Informant C

"Of course it's important...we have swimming pools and gardens to take care of everyday..."

Informant E

"(Water) affect all of our operations – room, restaurants, garden...if no water the entire hotel will paralyze"

Informant G

As for the second question i.e. why is it important to manage water use in hotel operations, common themes that emerged from the informants' answers were 'cost', and 'common sense'. Some excerpts to show these are below:

"We run a big operation here...well managed water can save operation costs"

- Informant A

"Since we use water for everything, we need to curb wastage so that the (water) bill won't get too high"

- Informant C

"It makes common sense to ensure you don't waste water unnecessarily. Even though water in this country is still not expensive, (but when you are) running a business, every little bit of saving helps"

- Informant D

"Yes, but it should start with least costly practices and it could differ based on the organization..."

- Informant B

Some hotels mentioned guest comfort as a consideration when managing water. They emphasized that while managing water is an important activity to ensure no wastage, it should not be implemented at the expense of the paying customers. Some excerpts are below:

“Our hotel responds to (water) sustainability issues but guests comfort and organizational profitability is definitely the priority” - Informant H

“We manage our water use but we put priority of guest (comfort) first. But I think guest will support our environmental approaches and help market our organization if we inform them of our intention and initiatives to sustain the environment” - Informant G

For research question 3 i.e. on whether they believe that hotel size can influence how a hotel responds to water management, there were mixed reactions. Some managers did not believe that firm size plays an important role in innovative water management. Those who believed that it does, mentioned the words ‘approaches’ and ‘costs’. Some excerpts to show this are below:

“Yes, in terms of approach. Budget hotels use smaller and cheaper pipes to save cost and at the same time it also reduces the amount of water flow thus consumption. Bigger hotels use water strainer, smaller water container, well, etc.” - Informant G

“Yes. However, the willingness to spend time and money and going through all the hassle for sustaining the environment initiatives plays a more important role.” - Informant A

“Big hotels have more money (but) financial resources without willingness to spend for the environment will not lead to environmental commitment.” - Informant G

“All hotels can engage in environment sustainability effort, (but) it should not compromise guest comfort and there should be return on investment” - Informant H

“Sure but (for big hotels) environment sustainability effort should not compromise guest comfort and hotel’s luxury ambience and atmosphere.” - Informant A

“For budget hotels, it is important that they take environmental approach that support cost saving for profitability.” - Informant C

There was a consensus that hotel type and location play no role in determining how a hotel would respond to water management. However, there were mixed responses with no strong agreement on the issue of ownership. The opposing views are demonstrated below:

“Foreign owners do not care as much as expected. Worry how environmental measures will affect tourist experience. (They often) worry how environmental measures such as installing rain harvesting water tanks will affect the aesthetic of the resort.” - Informant G

“Ownership makes no difference. It depends on their (environmental) priorities. Many still think (in terms of) dollar and cents.” - Informant I

As for research question 4 i.e. on the importance of environmental awareness and knowledge to sustainable water management, there was a strong consensus that a manager’s environmental awareness can affect how a hotel responds to water management. Common themes that emerged here were ‘very important’ and ‘good starting point’. Some related excerpts are below:

“People in general including hotel guests are becoming more aware about environmental issues and tolerate/love to see environmentally friendly measures at their hotels. So managers must realize this and take appropriate action...” - Informant C

“Environmental awareness is there...this has started in the 80s and became stronger in the 90s. Many big hoteliers have standard SOP involving the engineering department to deal with water consumption as part of business sense to reduce operation costs. This shows how important awareness is.” - Informant D

“Awareness about environmental situation is more important than environmental knowledge...if you are not aware, you will not have any idea (about environmental issues)” - Informant A

“Of course money is important but willingness to spend for environmental sustainability is the most important... awareness may lead to willingness...”
- Informant B

On the question of whether managers’ environmental knowledge affects how a hotel respond to water management, the common themes that emerged were ‘limited effect’ and ‘to a certain extend’. Some excerpts are as the following:

“Yes to some extent. People with environmental knowledge and awareness know the current situation of the environment and how their action will affect the environment. So they will try to sustain the environment for the future.”
- Informant G

“It is important (but) knowledge without willingness will not lead to environment sustainability as there is no willingness to spend or sacrifice for the future generations. “
- Informant H

On the question if they believe that formal education to enhance environment knowledge is necessary to influence how a hotel respond to water management, one common theme that emerged was ‘no’. Below are some of the excerpts:

“No formal environmental knowledge required. It’s more common sense and a sense of care about the environment.”
- Informant A

“Understanding the importance of taking environmental measures is more important than environmental knowledge. Understanding will eventually lead to predisposition to embrace environmental management. Predisposition to embrace EMS will slowly lead to environmental commitment.”
- Informant E

“Not necessary. Hoteliers can compare notes and learn from each other”
- Informant H

“Authorities can advise hotels (to get more environmental education) but cannot mandate as they do not know the working of the industry”
- Informant J

“It’s better to use of coercion via indirect communication such as signage and hotel information.”
- Informant K

On the question of how financial capability influence sustainable water management, it was evident that finance is certainly one of the constraints because financial resources are required for initiatives such as installing rainwater harvesting system which requires infrastructural work. However, on the question of how important is money in innovatively addressing water management issues and why, common themes that emerged were ‘not always expensive’ to innovate and ‘good maintenance’. Below are some of the relevant excerpts:

“There are innovations that can be adopted immediately without necessarily costing too much financial investment”
- Informant K

“Financial capability is not an indicator (of innovative environmental management). This is especially in terms of water reduction measures (which can be achieved) through maintenance of existing facilities that would reduce leakage and overconsumption.”
- Informant M

“Teaching your staff to avoid water wastage is not expensive at all but if you do it right you will save”
- Informant B

When asked if there are any water management innovations that do not require big capital investment, the common themes were ‘yes’ and ‘basic maintenance measures’. Some excerpts are as below:

“There are many simple innovations that do not require big investment. Example – adding bricks in water tank, low flow showerheads and faucets...”
- Informant M

“Here we just put water strainer at every tap in bathroom to control water pressure regulate amount of water dispensed.”
- Informant C

“Yes, if we apply this to the housekeeping department, they can ask guests to reuse towels. This is very simple measure if guests want to comply.”
- Informant B

“Yes, we clean rooms only when requested by guests. But they can get clean towels (by calling) the reception anytime.”
- Informant M

“Most definitely, my staffs do daily practices of water saving, troubleshooting pipe leakage, effective management of sewerage plant treatment”

- Informant N

“Yes. I ask my engineering department to put meter on each tank so water use can be better monitored...”

- Informant A

“Yes. For example we use table salt instead of chemical to treat pool water and thus reducing (potential) negative effects on swimmers compared to chlorine while being environmental friendly due to the reduced usage of chemicals.”

- Informant K

Discussion of Findings and Research Implications

From the above it can be concluded water management is an important issue in the hotel sector because water is one of the basic operational requirements. Therefore, hotels perceived good water management to be a sensible management approach. In addition, there appeared to be consensus that knowledge, particularly formal environmental knowledge, is less important than awareness and willingness to change. This highlights the possibility that ‘the will to change’ is the key leadership quality that hotel management needs to head towards sustainable water management. Hotel management that is willing to change can make their hotel become more sustainable and can lead other hotels to become more sustainable as well through leadership demonstration during trade meetings etc. The fact that the perceived influence of financial capability on innovative water management seems low due to the availability of cheaper alternatives and the tendency among hoteliers to use the term ‘cost’ in water management to refer to ‘cost saving’ rather than ‘operational costs’ further indicate the lack of influence of financial capability on innovative water management. In other words, hotels can engage in sustainable water management practices as long as they are willing to make the change.

As can be deduced from the qualitative finding, hoteliers already consider the importance of water and water management in their operation. They believe that that ‘hotel type’ and ‘location’ do not determine whether a hotel will have green water management policy or not. Neither does the issue of ‘ownership’ because even foreign owners may not even care as much as local owners. They believe that financial capability is not always a factor when addressing water management innovatively, as there are many ways that simple, low cost ‘good maintenance’ can be utilized to save water. They also mentioned ‘cost savings’ as one strong factor for managing water innovatively. On the other hand, they believe that the ‘willingness to spend’ as a more important driver in green water management. However, they want to be motivated by government led training and motivation programs.

From the above, it can be concluded that an important parameter for innovative water management responses is ‘willingness’ of the managers– the willingness to change, to adopt environmentally friendly behavior and to allocate resources towards an innovative environmental management. As the findings have shown, environmental knowledge alone is insufficient to inculcate a ‘green’ behavioral tendency among hotel managers. There is a need to be ‘willing’ or ‘willful’ in addressing the water management issue in the respective organizations. Therefore ‘managerial will’ is proposed as a necessary antecedent in enhancing innovative environmental management responsiveness among hotel managers. Simply defined, ‘managerial will’ is the ‘strong determination’ of people in the managerial positions to ‘do something difficult’ (Merriam-Webster dictionary). Future researchers may need to inculcate a more proper definition and measurement for ‘managerial will’ before they could explore this new variable in greater depth.

The findings could have several managerial implications: Firstly, small and medium size hotels, despite being higher in numbers than big hotels in any given destination, are still not embracing the need to respond innovatively to environmental issues. Their lack of willingness to change demonstrates the lack of managerial will to change their ‘business as usual’ mindset. They need to have more leadership skill such as willingness to change and explore new management paradigm such as that offered in green water management. Only with a more widespread willingness to shoulder the environmental responsibility, will the move towards sustainability be possible for these hotels. Second and perhaps a more important implication of this study is from the management perspective. Since small and medium size hotels view innovative water management as costly despite believing that innovative management strategies can help

minimize water related costs, this brings up the question of how much they are willing to learn and understand the concept of ‘innovation’. As Kemp (2010) has said, innovation refers to any novel initiative that helps an organization handle its environmental externality. Therefore, cost is not necessarily a compounding factor as there are innovations that are not too costly (De Marchi, 2012; Kasim et al., 2014). What is crucial is hoteliers’ awareness of these possible innovations and their willingness to test those innovations in their daily operations. Saving water drip from air-conditioners for example, require only innovative collecting methods that channel the excess water to a holding tank. The accumulated water could later be useful for garden or landscape uses. From such basic activities, hotel management could widen their approach to other innovative measures such as using drought tolerant vegetation in places with little water access etc. One seemingly simple innovation i.e. “toilet tank water saving device (bricks)” also offers hotels an innovation that is simple and cheap to install.

Possible Policy Implications

By highlighting important antecedents of water-friendly measure adoption among hotels, the paper aims to provide ways and means for the government to ensure a more active private sector participation in Malaysia water policy. This is relevant because according to Mr. Lee Koon Yew, honorary secretary general, Malaysian Water Association, Malaysia currently "lack a legislatively mandated water policy to manage one of four most important resources -WATER" (Bulletin Ingenieur, Jan -Aug 2004). However, to attain sustainable tourism, then the mindset of all involved needs to change. As the data has suggested, awareness is a key ingredient to changing mindsets. Destination managers, themselves already enlightened, need to change hotels’ ‘business as usual’ mind set and create awareness on their role in water issues facing the destination. The environmental awareness campaign needs to be supported with guidelines, incentives and awards. Guidelines that are currently available online (for example from the Green Hotelier website) need to be translated to Bahasa Malaysia, Mandarin, Cantonese and Tamil to ensure that owners and managers of small and medium size hotels in Malaysia could better understand them. Incentives in the form of tax breaks, discount vouchers for the purchase of green products/supplies and free training on green measures could be offered to encourage more small and medium size hotels to participate. Finally, some form of award system that is based specifically on this hotel category’s achievement in environmental management should be created. It seems important that a separate set of indicators that account for hotels’ respective level of resources and capabilities, as well as an emphasis on innovation and creative measures that do not necessarily be too costly are called for. Only with a more widespread environmental awareness, and willingness to help shoulder the environmental responsibility, will the move towards sustainability be possible.

From the findings, it can also be proposed that it is necessary to support the influence of any form of environmental knowledge that could enhance hoteliers’ awareness and responsiveness towards innovative environmental management. To enhance ‘willingness’ among hotel managers, there is a need to change their perception about the economic or business value of innovative environmental management practices. There is a need to convince managers that taking innovative environmental management measures will greatly enhance their financial bottom lines. Savings from innovative environmental measures need to be clearly demonstrated to the hoteliers. There should also be a demand for environmentally friendly behaviors among hoteliers. This demand is could come from tourists and government. While the former type of demand can be difficult to inculcate, the second type of demand should be more feasible provided we have corresponding national policy. However, Pinget et al. (2014) conclusion to their research stating the importance of strategic goals and collective actions in enhancing adoption of environmental innovation is also of merit. To realize any environmental innovation effort, ‘managerial will’ must be supported by managerial strategies and teamwork from members of the business organization. This requires a change in business paradigm, which may be triggered if business is able to associate innovative environmental management with important business factors such as competitiveness, government support, market leadership and company positioning. It can be proposed that the government (Tourism Malaysia, state Tourism agencies) and trade associations (MAH, Malaysian Association of Business Owners, Malaysian Association of Budget Hotels) play a stronger role in convincing small and medium size hotels about the business value of practicing innovative water management.

As innovation can be one of the primary sources of competitive advantage for manufacturing industry to compete in global markets, it is important to encourage more service sectors to adopt innovative approaches in dealing with environmental issues so as to remain competitive as well. One important policy to consider is greater role of the public agencies in informing hotels especially the small and medium hotels yet to innovate their practices about the advantages and benefits of innovating as well as related public subsidies of incentives available to them. Higher exposure to information and knowledge about public subsidies and other form of incentives may encourage more hotels to innovate in their water management because as Horbach, Oltra & Belin (2013) have mentioned in their study, Eco innovation activities require more information and knowledge than non-environmental innovation.

Another important policy to consider is to involve hotels in some type of environmental cluster or association. In the US, the Green Hotel Association (GHA) has successfully attracted hotels to be members and guided them to become more environmentally friendly in their innovations. At present Malaysia has only Malaysia Association of Hotel Owners, Malaysia Association of Hotels and Malaysia Association of Budget Hotels, none of which are particularly prolific in championing green issues related to the sector. This gives the government more reason to coerce the industry to 'come together' as a strong team under the umbrella of an environment – championing trade association. Similar to the initiatives in the US, Malaysia can also develop schemes that focus on rewarding firms that participate in environmental programmes, activities or processes organized by governmental or non-governmental bodies. Awarding hotels based on several categories such as according to size, while laudable, could improve existing programmes such as the Hibiscus Award Programme.

Finally, there should be a policy to encourage an 'administrative incentives' culture among businesses. Administrative incentives are standards, practices and pressures in the supply chain for businesses to operate in environmentally sustainable manner. As found in a policy study by Rademaekers, Williams, Ellis, Smith, Svatikova, & Bilsen (2012), this form of incentives could be a strong driver because businesses, especially small and medium size ones that depend on order from bigger companies, would take this as a financial incentive to ensure continuous opportunities to secure contracts and tenders. In the UK, the UK Environment Agency developed OPRA (Operational Risk Appraisal) to monitor, among other, environmental performance of firms. If and when a firm is able to show its environmental initiatives, such as adopting environmental management system (EMS), its OPRA score will be updated and the firm will not be inspected as frequently as those that do not take environmental initiatives. In Italy, firms with EMS are charged less for their municipal waste and given higher threshold for environmental impact assessment (EIA) requirement. In short, policies that aim to encourage innovative environmental responses from businesses should focus more on encouraging and awarding businesses of all sizes and not just focus on big businesses only. Public subsidies must benefit all firms with environmental innovations and not focus only on those with intense innovation activities. Most importantly, government must utilize relevant agencies under its wings to educate and inform SMEs on environmental innovations. This policy can work because hotel owners and managers who believe that supplier's environmental concern will have an impact on their business will also realize the significant cost benefits associated with environmental issues and learn from their suppliers (Gadenne et al., 2009). Continuous learning from stakeholders will make hotel owners and managers adapt and effectively address their environmental responsibility (Lion, Donovan & Bedggood, 2013).

Conclusion, Limitation and Suggestion for Future Research

This paper aims to highlight the factors that could contribute towards a more definitive role of the private sector particularly hotels in legislatively mandated water policy. As it is one of several papers extracted from the primary investigator's research project, it may have some clarity issues that could only be resolved by looking at the project itself. Nevertheless, future researchers who aim to propose environmental policy from their empirical research project should continue to do so and are encouraged to find ways to present their position paper in a more clear and comprehensive manner so that empirical academic research can continue to provide meaningful contribution to the industry.

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Comparative Study of Foreign Values and Indian Spiritual Values - A Case Study of International Tourists Visiting Rishikesh

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Abstract

Foreigners prefer to travel to India and practice spirituality here rather than their own country because India is known for preserving its age-old tradition of spirituality for providing the authentic learnings in the field of spirituality whereas their respective countries are too materialistic and there is low quality of life in terms of inner peace. The values found out in the study shows that the spiritual people are more compassionate and delightful which contribute to improve not only their personal well-being but also their conduct to others and this will mark a positive impact on the overall civilization. The study is qualitative in nature and the data is gathered through personal interviews of the spiritual seekers who were practicing spirituality and staying in the Ashrams. The study uses the theoretical sampling. In theoretical sampling, the participants are not selected randomly but according to criteria specified by the researcher. The data has been analyzed by using grounded theory. The spiritual values explored in the study give testimony to the richness of Indian culture. The constructs identified as the selective coding can be a strong resource for branding strategies for India as a spiritual destination. It is important to retain and preserve Indian values as these are positively contributing not only in attracting but also making foreigners to revisit and even stay back in India. This study has both economic as well as social attributes which can positively influence people all over the world to visit India.

Keywords: *Spirituality, Spiritual, Values, Authentic, Transformation.*

Introduction

“Spirituality is a rational process of search and self-realization leading to the transformation of self for the better” (Zinnbauer & Pargament, 2010). Spirituality always offers the values such as contentment, forgiveness, harmony etc. but religion may foster superstitions, prejudices etc. (Zojanc, 2004; Sinha, 2014). “It is not related to any ritual or particular religious tradition. It implies developing a deep faith in God which will provide the guidance and energy needed to achieve spiritual perfection” (Elahi, 1997).

Understanding Spirituality and Religion

Spirituality and religion are two different philosophies but most of the times, spirituality is confused or misunderstood with religion. Krishnananda (2003) explains that every religion has its own rules and regulations which imposes various restrictions of do’s and don’ts on the followers in terms of personal conduct and social behavior in the form of rituals, traditions, worship, diet, pilgrimage etc. Spirituality on the other hand is extensive and does not have any set rules to oblige whereas it is understood as personal choice of setting inner connection to self and the higher self.

Khan (2015) makes it clear that both the concepts are interconnected but still distinct. Religion makes you follow a particular path whereas spirituality sets you free to follow your own path. Spirituality is to feel and create your own experiences whereas religion is following someone else’s experiences. Spirituality is to seek and discover the truth but religion has already carved truths which one have to follow. Spirituality does not confine from other religions rather it guides to be free and united. Spirituality applies the ultimate ‘Karma’ and lets you create your own journey.

Indian Spirituality – A Mystique to Spirituality Seekers from all over the World

Indian Spirituality being one of the oldest, always has an enigma to draw people from all over the world to India. Rishikesh being known as the Yoga capital of the world attracts a heavy number of foreign tourists and is the preferred seat of spirituality. Domestic as well as International seekers travel a way long to experience the spiritual *Ashram* life and follow spiritual practices to solve some unanswered questions of life. It is not wrong to say that people from all over the world are travelling to India to learn the spiritual ways of living.

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In the monotonous life of today, Spirituality is becoming the essential need of life style to have “me time” and to overcome stress. Western countries are following the concept of Yoga but mostly in the form of Yoga studios. It is trending at a fast pace in United States, UK and European countries but those who want to solve the bigger picture of life and are inquisitive about the connections with the universal self, do not want to practice it in confined space. That is the reason; they travel to India to have authentic experience in order to better understand the purpose and meaning of life. Technology has made our lives easier in many ways. But it has also increased the insecurities, complexities, competition, mad race, stress levels, and mental pressure. When a person realizes the adverse impacts of this lifestyle, he or she gets a feel to connect to the real self and wishes to have that time in routine which subsequently endeavor spirituality. Spirituality is a way to relax in the soothing yogic and meditation practices. People believe that these practices need complete devotion and exclusion from routine life but in reality, yoga and meditation are mystic arts and can be easily incorporated into our daily lives.

These days’ people are facing the downfall in their value system whether they are native values or spiritual values. Sooner or later they realize it and wish to mend the ways of living. Few people travel to the authentic places to seek spirituality and enhance their values, to make it part of their routine.

The one important factor which attracts the foreigners to India is the freedom to club their own religion with the Indian methods of spirituality without converting or disturbing the faith in their own respective religious beliefs. “The term, spiritual tourism is new, but the phenomenon itself is not. It is clear that there has been a shift from orthodox religious practice to a universal spiritual dimension of human psychology and it is also apparent that people from various religious backgrounds visit sacred sites to enjoy spiritual experiences rather than observing religious rituals” (Haq & Jackson, 2006). Thus, Spirituality makes a person to explore path of truth irrespective of his religion. Figure 1 shows the Hinduism in context of spirituality; we can see that all the sacred texts, falling under Purans, Mahakavyas and Vedas teach oneness of all creations. Most popular and accessible of all Hindu scriptures, ‘Bhagawad Gita’ “discuss selflessness, duty, devotion, and meditation, integrating many different threads of human philosophy” (Sarupananda, 1909). These teachings are aimed to build human capacity for self-actualization and self-realization.

Figure 1: Hindu philosophy in spiritual context

Source: Researcher's conceptualization

Values' Transformation through Spiritual Practices

Culture forms values and all the international tourists visiting India for spirituality, are already carry a baggage of their own native values. They may be British, French, Korean, etc. but all have the values of their own culture where they are born and brought up. Spiritual values are those human values which guide the principles, convictions and beliefs that people adopt for ethical conduct in life. “The values of truth, righteousness, peace, love and non-violence are found in all major spiritual paths. These spiritual values are also human values and are the fundamental roots of a healthy and vibrant life” (Global Dharma, 2006). Human beings are spiritual first and these human values are inherent in our spiritual nature so it is right to say “to be human is to be spiritual” (Global Dharma, 2006). These human values refine human behavior according to the ethical values and need to be evoked by following spiritual practices. Figure 2 represents how the values transform through spirituality without changing the religion or native values of a person.

Figure2: Values' Transformation through spiritual practices

Source: Researcher's conceptualization

The transformation to spiritual values ensures integrating the self to the whole. Interestingly, the foreigners who visit to India with spiritual motivations convert themselves spiritually not religiously, to seek experiences to understand the purpose of life. Due to the fast and materialistic lifestyle, human beings have become oblivious to these spiritual values.

Renowned examples of spiritual conversion

Mira Alfasa, a French tourist came to Sri Aurobindo Ashram in 1914 and became the devotee there. Later in 1920 she permanently settled down in India, resided in Sri Aurobindo Ashram, later came to known as 'The Mother' (Meier & Korpela, 2006)

The Beatles, music band of four persons came to India in 1967-68 to Maharaj Mahesh Yogi Ashram in Rishikesh for contemplation and meditation. They composed numerous songs while their stay at Rishikesh. Two of the band members, George Harrison and Jerry Garcia were so impressed by Indian spirituality that they made the wish to spread their ashes after their death in Holy River Ganga (Swanson, 2015).

Julia Roberts, a well renowned Hollywood actress converted to Hinduism in 2010 for spirituality, after acting in the movie 'Eat, Pray Love' in which she comes for a soul-searching mission to India (Anwasha, 2013).

Prince Charles and Camilla Parker Bowles visited Rishikesh in 2013, and participated in the Ganga arti. They also conducted a special havan for world peace at the Parmarth Niketan. Charles said: "I am amazed by the experience of sitting on the bank of one of the ancients' rivers of the world. It is the right time for us to rediscover our connection with nature" (Gusain, 2013).

The purpose of the study is to understand the different value systems and how these values transform over a period of time by practicing the spirituality.

Review of Literature

The word spirituality has been derived from the Latin word 'spiritus' which means 'breathe of life' (Suri, 2014; Principe, 1983) is related to spiritual practices for God. Spirituality is belief of supremacy of God, who controls the whole Universe (Suri, 2014; Hunsberger & Jackson, 2005; Mitroff & Dentan, 1999). The most accepted definition of "spirituality is an inner peace or experience of an individual that changes his/her conduct of life" (Suri, 2014; Clark, 1958).

Spiritual tourism is "secular travel which purposely or inadvertently includes an experience, beyond the norm for the individual traveler, which impacts the individual's belief system" (Chesworth, 2006)

whereas the “Spiritual tourist could be defined as someone who visits a place out of his/her usual environment, with the intention of spiritual growth (which could be religious, non-religious, sacred or experiential in nature)” (Haq and Jackson, 2006).

India as a Spiritual Destination

Hinduism is the oldest extant religion of the world which evolves around the truth of life and provides freedom of thought for spiritual development (Gandhi, 1987). As the religion of Sanatan Dharma, Hinduism is life itself and exists for humanity cherishing the ultimate salvation Sri Aurobindo (1909).

Religious tourism is one of the oldest and common forms of tourism because of its multifunctional element (Sharpley & Sundaram, 2005). But in modern societies, people are striving for transcendence rather than following the common set of beliefs. They started moving out of their religious background to find this transcending factor. As Strauss (1992) emphasized Yoga as one of the component of spirituality whereas Aggarwal, Guglani & Goel (2008) emphasized on the role of yoga and spirituality in Indian tourism highlighting the world-renowned age old spiritual practices of India. Rana (2015) focuses on the quest to find out the travel motives of foreign tourists visiting ashrams in Rishikesh and to analyze the satisfaction experience of foreigners while their stay in the Ashrams.

Medhekar & Haq, (2012) have called the Spiritual tourism a ‘multi faith based tourism’ because it attracts the people from all over the world irrespective of their different religious beliefs. Bhawuk (2011) has described the spirituality as “the science of the soul, a peculiarly Indian science” (Rolland, 1960, Cited in Bhawuk, 2011). Rao and Ramakrishna (2013) conclude that one should introspect the self and retrospect the world with the help of literature, for the spiritual growth and for the well-being of human race.

Norman (2004) has clarified that the tourists may travel to different settings to seek out the spiritual experiences irrespective of their religion. They have the different motivations to take out such journeys for spiritual exploration. Rogers (2005) has emphasized on the changing concept of spirituality as spirituality is no more traditionally attached to religion. There is no second thought that spirituality has its roots in religion but now-a-days, people are more interested in the development of their own i.e. self and there is a huge decrease in the number participating in the religious ceremonies or rituals. Ambroz and Ovsenik (2011) have emphasized that atheists and agnostics may also have deep spiritual experiences in relation to nature and their own self-consciousness without believing in god or any organized religious affiliation.

Objectives of the Study

1. To compare the Indian spiritual values to the corresponding native values of the foreign spiritual tourists.
2. To suggest for ways to develop and sustain Indian spiritual values as a resource for Spiritual tourism in India.

Research Methodology

The present study is qualitative in nature as we need to get deep insights from the subject such as what they think, why they think so, why it is important to them etc. Qualitative inquiry surpasses all other ways of learning when it is about “reaching the parts other methods cannot reach” (Berkwits & Inui, 1998).

The study has used Grounded theory based on thematic and content analysis, aims to explain phenomena based on theoretical saturation relying on people's words. As the data in this study encompasses open ended in-depth interviews, grounded theory provides guidelines for analyzing data consisting of coding, comparisons between data, memo writing and theoretical sampling.

The present study is exploratory in nature. Exploratory research is an initial research used to explore the theoretical idea and lays the ground work for future research (Kowalczyk, 2015). Present study is exploratory as it is carried out to explore the spiritual values considered important by foreigner visiting India. The study also explored how these identified values help the participants in transforming their

lives. These values were not earlier known and the researcher has identified them by interviews and has interpreted these values. The research thus aims to know about them by the process of exploration.

The sampling method used is *theoretical sampling*, a form of purposive sampling, where the participants are not selected randomly but according to criteria specified by the researcher which help select the participants from the research point of view.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is the most challenging part in qualitative study as we cannot treat the data same way as we do in quantitative studies. The researcher has all the information from respondents but cannot count these statements or put them in tabular form as in quantitative study. In addition to this, the results from qualitative studies cannot be generalized to whole population, but are suggestive in nature.

The analysis process here starts with the coding. The researcher has to write summaries from the raw data and take out the important statements from data in form of textual content which is called open coding; the next step is to generate categories and then themes.

In this research, 21 subcategories emerged, and these are later regrouped into 8 themes, namely Self Actualization, Self Realization, Love for humanity, Being Delighted, State of steadiness, Divine Environment, Sense of cultural belongingness and Spiritual roots.

Figure 3: Grounded theory based Schematic representation of Values' attracting International tourists to India for experiencing spirituality

Identified Spiritual values: Table 1 present the keywords on spiritual values that have been frequently used by the participants during the interviews. These keywords make the part of the statements in open coding which are later grouped into eight themes. The themes comprise of all the keywords and the statements grouped together to describe the spiritual values of India which attracts the foreign tourists to India.

Table 1: Frequently used Keywordson Spiritual Values

1. Acceptance (1)	26. Ethics (1)	51. Mercy (1)
2. Awareness (6)	27. Flexibility (1)	52. Music (1)
3. Back to roots (1)	28. Focused (3)	53. Nice (2)
4. Being yourself (1)	29. Freedom (1)	54. No thoughts (1)
5. Better living (3)	30. Friendly (1)	55. Noble (1)
6. Calm (4)	31. Generosity (1)	56. Oneness (2)
7. Care (2)	32. Graceful (2)	57. Openness (6)
8. Change (1)	33. Gratitude (1)	58. Patience (4)
9. Cherishing (1)	34. Guide (1)	59. Positive Vibrations (4)
10. Compassion (5)	35. Happiness (4)	60. Practice (1)
11. Connection with true self (5)	36. Happy (4)	61. Purity (1)
12. Conscious (1)	37. Harmony (3)	62. Reality of life (1)
13. Consistent (1)	38. Healthy (1)	63. Relaxed (2)
14. Contemplation (1)	39. Helpful (1)	64. Respect (1)
15. Contentment (1)	40. High Vibrations (3)	65. Secular (1)
16. Contrast (1)	41. Honest (2)	66. Self-Development (1)
17. Cool (2)	42. Humanity (2)	67. Selfless (1)
18. Culture (4)	43. Impermanence (1)	68. Stillness (1)
19. Devotion (1)	44. Inner Journey (8)	69. Traditional (1)
20. Discovery (1)	45. Inner Peace (7)	70. Transcendence (2)
21. Divine pleasure (2)	46. Inspiration (1)	71. Transformation (4)
22. Easy life (1)	47. Intense (1)	72. Union with self (1)
23. Energy (2)	48. Joy (1)	73. Vibrant (1)
24. Enjoy (1)	49. Kindness (5)	74. Younger (1)
25. Equality (1)	50. Love (6)	

Findings of the Study

When asked about the native values and the way of living in their country, and the questions like why did they not prefer their own country for practicing spirituality, why India? The following are the repeated answers:

Table 2: Represents the native values or lifestyle of the participants

<p>Materialism P1 - Everywhere there is story of materialism, people are materialistic in our country P15 - Our country has western / commercial culture. People are materialistic and money minded. P27 – We involved in material things P33 – Wests are capitalists. Working and making money only. P37 – No inner development, no awareness in our country. People are more materialistic</p>
<p>Monotonous life P2 – Busy life, work and commitments there. So, it also offers an experience to travel to new country P4 – Regular life does not offer ways and means P7 – Work and everything there. P27 – Escape from a monotonous life</p>
<p>Low quality of life P23 - Work, drink, survival, no energy and no meaning of life P36 – People are stronger and angry in Russia P17 – London is mad with stress, lack of time. Everybody is running</p>
<p>People are not aware about spirituality P16 – People know exercises but not Yoga P26 – In Italy, there are no practices to prepare mind. P38 – People are close minded to meditation and inner journey in our country. P28 – People are not exposed to spirituality.</p>

(P denotes to Participant)

Table 3: - Statements given by the participants supporting the Indian spiritual values

P7 - When I visit India...something in you...something good.... new people come in life...it means...I have more high vibrations.
P10 & 11 - Because in Chile... it's like we can't find. Here I think...yeah...it's like less restrictions...here no one to stop you...here in India...you know it's been the place known for years.
P17 - If I compare to live in London...you go and you will meet with stress and lack of time...always running after stuff...here is...Rishikesh you come outside and you meet with people smiling...the monkeys...peanuts...like whatever you do is of level of peace...there is underlying vibrational peace in Rishikesh...I have not found in England... I feel, its more Santosha here.
P18 - Because of my Guru...he is living here in India. On a spiritual path, India is the road. Don't miss the country.
P22 - Devotion or Bhakti to God. It's stronger here...in India...you are easy but in German it's difficult. Find more materialistic people....and I look here for other places.
P23 - It is like the roots of everything....that's a purpose of life...when you look outside to the towns in Germany, it is also everybody is working....comes home...have a drink.. Just surviving. Since no energy in life...no meaning....People come here to the place...the root of spirituality....holy persons and rishis....spiritual persons from the Himalaya....they are famous for it.
P32 - Actually in New Zealand, it's new but here, this spiritual motherland has given me the karmic connection. For me, India is a moving breathing mother of divine beauty....everywhere you look; it exudes spiritual qualities of knowing the fullness of wisdom.
P34 - India is so vibrant. As you have to go to France if you want to learn French in a right manner. In the same way, when you have to learn Yoga, you have to come to India. I have learned the way of life here.
P37 - Oooo...its very different...my country there is no inner development....inner awareness....here its everywhere. I think...before coming to India. I believed in making money and after coming to India...I stopped thinking and believing in making money....comes the values of compassion and equality.
P38 - People are so much into alcohol...I was a big...I partied a lot...I drunk a lot of alcohol..... Unhealthy relationship with men...it's just changed...it helps in the inner journey.

It is noticed that India is known as the spiritual capital of the world and has the potential to retain this spiritual charm as majority of the tourists are repeat visitors and those who come for the first time are quite impressed and interested to come again. These repeat visits contribute to the social and economic growth of the country as well as bring a Spiritual Brand to the Nation. The recommendations based on the study to retain the spiritual values which act as a resource of Spiritual tourism to India are given under *Recommendations of the study*.

Discussion of the Findings

The present section is a synthesis of the findings supporting the fulfillment of the research objectives. The study broadly aims to find out the spiritual values attracting foreign tourists to India and further comparative analysis of their native values with Indian spiritual values. Table 1 lists all the keywords repeatedly used by the participants and Figure 3 shows the themes / values identified by using grounded theory which attracts the foreign tourists to experience spirituality in India.

The first objective is to know about the native values of the foreign spiritual tourists to India and comparing them with the Indian spiritual values. Table 2 lists the details of the statements given by the participants about the native values of their respective countries which can be represented as materialism, monotonous life, low quality of life, and people are not aware about actual meaning of spirituality. Table 3 represents the statements supporting Indian spiritual values in comparison to native values which shows that they see India as a spiritual destination which is still culturally and traditionally rich. They are spiritually focused tourists who are well aware of the fact what exactly they are coming for and why they preferred India as a spiritual destination rather than their own country. The spiritual values which they think they have imbibed clearly indicate the positive changes, when compared to their native values or way of living.

The second objective is to suggest the ways to develop and retain the spiritual values which acts as a resource of Spiritual tourism to India. It is the known fact that India has retained its spiritual charm even

today and is a famous destination worldwide for spiritual tourism. Data also suggests that majority of the tourists who come for the first time is willing to visit again. These repeat visits contribute to the social and economic growth of the country and the specific purpose of spiritual travel brings the Spiritual Brand to the Nation.

Recommendations of the Study

India is known as the spiritual capital of the world and has the potential to retain its spiritual charm as majority of the tourists are repeat visitors and those who came for the first time are quite impressed and interested to come again. The study shows that the foreigners usually stay for a long period, sometimes for 4-6 months in Rishikesh only. Some of them also visit the nearby places of spiritual significance only like Bodhgaya and Varanasi but not as a leisure tourist. The repeat visits contribute to the social and economic growth of the country as well as build a Spiritual Brand for the country. Following are some recommendations and suggestions based on the study to retain the charisma of spiritual tourism of India:

1. The foremost recommendation of the study is to keep providing the authentic services to our foreign guests as they trust and respect the Indian spiritual practices and travel so long to experience this authenticity.
2. It is recommended that to keep the mystic aura intact, there needs measures to control the commercialization of the spiritual services.
3. In the study, it has been found that sometimes spiritual teachers force the foreign spiritual seekers to first take 'diksha' to proceed with the meditation and Yoga practices. 'Diksha' is a mantra given by a Guru to his disciple to initiate the spiritual discipline. It is given in Indian religions such as Hinduism, Buddhism and Jainism with the purpose of purifying the disciple. It is suggested that the seekers must not be compelled to take Diksha or follow some particular Guru or Ashram till the time he himself is not convinced to do the same.

Above recommendations are based on the statements extracted by one of the in-depth interview with a repeat tourist.

- P1- *"Sometimes they force you to take Diksha (name) to follow them. But it is always not comfortable. Sometimes it seems you can learn more from internet than coming here. If they will continue like this, in a long run place is going to lose its credibility, if they do not open up. I think the winner would be the one who will be sharing his knowledge openly without any strings attached to it. No dikshas. It's a long tradition of Diksha but still I hope people will open up and value practices and share else the fate would be different"*.
- *"We come here for sharing of knowledge but sometimes we encounter less exclusivity. They make you follow a group, a Guru, an organization.... In long run who will be sharing and not ask for anything in return would be a clear winner. Definitely a winner"*.

4. It is recommended to introduce the basics of spiritual values in the curriculum of the students at the initial level in order to assimilate these values in our people so that India develops as a holistic society and should be known for its high ethical standards.

It has been observed that "to click a picture with Goras/Firangi is quite a charm among domestic tourists as sometimes they do not even understand and respect their personal time". A statement from one of the female participants strengthens the fact.

P35- *"I was on the other side of Ram Jhoola and folding my yoga mat to go back to the Ashram. A turban guy approached me for a picture.. I said No..then he said some something in local language in very rude tone"*

5. The Government should promote and organize cultural/spiritual events such as World Yoga festival Rishikesh, World Culture Festival (Art of living) on regular basis to attract more and more spiritual seekers to India. It will also provide a comfortable platform to the beginners to engage themselves on the path of spirituality. While the author's stay in Parmarth Niketan ashram, it has come into knowledge that Parmarth Niketan is organizing International World Yoga Festival every year to attract and engage spiritual seekers from all over the world.

6. It is recommended on part of the Ashrams or Universities like Dev Sanskriti Vishwavidyalaya to arrange Cultural exchange programs / Student exchange program with other countries to invite their students and let them acquaint with the spiritual practices.

Above recommendation is based on an interview with a Chinese group.

P15- *“This year I went to Haridwar Shantikunj...I live there 1 week...I am a yoga teacher in China. This year in March and April... I went to Shantikunj...Dev Sanskriti University...and that time we talk about exchange programs between India and China....yoga programs...This month we organize first group to Shantikunj and university.. Yeah we learn yoga...Indian sanskriti and culture ... university Sanskrit teacher taught us a little Hindi ...and we have also learned Indian classical music”*.

7. It is appreciative of the Ashrams which provide free basic activities such as Satsang and mantra chanting sessions for the foreign tourists. It is suggested to continue with the same offerings at larger cultural programs to make the foreigner guests familiarize about the rich culture of India.

This recommendation is supported by the statement given by one of the participants as well as author's observation.

P26&27- *“I don't know ...he laughed and said.. Every time I come .. I think it is a last time but then again I come back to India ... I been to other countries too but it is very expensive there...in Italy its expensive.. anywhere else its expensive..here it is almost free and then the other one added... here its Satsang, meditation, classes...they teach free”*. (They were staying in Ved Niketan)

Being a regular traveler to Rishikesh, author has stayed many times in Parmarth Niketan Ashram and observed that they manage the daily evening Ganga Arti on the Ghats followed by the Satsang session for spiritual seekers.

Future Scope of the Research

The study can be extended further to several other directions.

1. The study can be extended to other spiritual destinations related to other religions to know the commonalities and differences.
2. A study can be conducted in context of sociology i.e. Spiritual tourism nurtures humanity and societal prosperity and celebrates cultural diversity.
3. A separate study can be conducted to explore the sustainable tourism practices as spiritual tourists compared to other tourist typologies are more aware towards nature and its resources.
4. A study can be extended to understand the cross-culture nature of spiritual tourism for reviving peace and harmony among the countries of the world.
5. A separate study can be conducted with respect to volunteer tourism, social work and NGO's as it has been observed that spiritual people are more compassionate towards other people and can contribute in the welfare and development of the communities.

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Progress in Indigenous Tourism: An Empirical Study into the Perception of Gujjar - Bakarwal Tribal Community

Ahsan-ul-Haq¹

Abstract

The tourism industry has faced an accelerated growth with holistic support from local communities who are involved directly and indirectly in this industry. Local residents' support is essential to ensure long-term success in tourism development, and without the support of the local community it is impossible to sustain tourism at any destination. Indigenous tourism can make substantial contribution to marginalized communities in developing countries like India. Tribal tourism is also a type of indigenous tourism concerned with a tribal community culture, especially its arts. The current study provided an insight about the historical background of Gujjar- Bakarwal tribe and their perception regarding tourism. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was carried out to explore the factors influencing the perception of community residents towards the impact of tourism development in tribal destinations; descriptive statistics was used to study the perception of community residents. Findings from data analysis identified three factors which explained 67.91% of the total variance. The result of the study revealed that the economic impact as the most imperative factor followed by social impact and environmental impact. The result of the study signifies that the Destination Community view tourism positively and agreed that tourism has a great potential to benefit their community in terms of employment opportunities, improvement in standard of living and in enhancement of economic situation of their tribe. However, they also acknowledged the negative impact of tourism on ecological environment of the destination.

Keywords: *Tribal Tourism, Gujjar - Bakarwal, Perception, Jammu & Kashmir*

Introduction

Globally tourism is known as the most significant source of employment and Gross Domestic Product (GDP). It particularly benefits the economies of developing countries, where most of the sector's tourism jobs and businesses are being created and it is most viable and sustainable economic development. Next to Africa, India has the largest concentration of tribal population, and has a great potential of Tribal tourism because, all these tribal groups are having different and varied culture. This diversity of culture provides an opportunity for the country to bring in tourists on a large scale. With the tourism sector showing tremendous growth, India can leverage its rich tribal culture to lure a sizeable proportion of domestic and international tourists and hasten its economic development. Factors like increasing propensity among tourists to see tribal and ethnic cultures from close quarters are also a plus point.

Tribal tourism has seen significant growth in recent years. It is the subset of tourism concerned with a tribal community culture, especially its arts. It is similar as cultural tourism which generally focuses on traditional communities who have diverse customs, unique forms of art and distinct social practices, which basically distinguishes it from other type of culture. This type of indigenous tourism is often seen as a way to promote and reinforce native culture and provide pro-poor benefits to the local community. It can also include tourism in rural areas showcasing the traditions of indigenous culture (i.e. festivals, rituals), and their values and lifestyle. It is generally agreed that cultural tourists spend substantially more than standard tourists do. The reasons are not so hard to find, because, cultural tourists not only spend on food and lodging but also on buying cultural artifacts and other cultural mementos which are costlier in comparison to the mementos other tourists buy. This form of tourism can also be self-sustaining with a far more carrying capacity in comparison to other forms of tourism like eco-tourism, adventure tourism, etc. In India, states of Madhya Pradesh, Jharkhand, Orissa, Nagaland, Himachal and Chhattisgarh see maximum tribal tourism. It has been influential in creating numerous financial opportunities for the tribes living in the hinterlands. It has helped to foster awareness about the indigenous people in India, many of whom face oppression, lack of opportunities and social exclusion.

In this paper, researcher analyzes the extent to which the strategies can be developed for tribal tourism that could generate economic benefit and create employment for the marginalized tribe. Gujjars numbering about 1.5 million constitute a major chunk of tribal population followed by Bakarwal (60,724)

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in Jammu and Kashmir. Gujjar-Bakarwals still live a nomadic or semi-nomadic existence perched along some of the remote pastures scattered along the higher reaches of the Himalayas. There are three major groups among the Gujjars of Jammu and Kashmir based on the type of animal they rear. The sedentary agriculturist group is called Muqami Gujjars. The second group is called Bakarwal Gujjars, because they rear Bakri (goat) in large numbers. The third group is Banihara Gujjars, who rear buffaloes and live in forests (Khattana, 1974).

The Bakarwals belong to the same ethnicity as the Gujjars, and inter-marriages take place among them. Bakarwals have same gotra or clan like Gujjars (so henceforth in this study they will be referred as Gujjar-Bakarwals). These Scheduled tribes are the third largest ethnic group in Jammu and Kashmir after Kashmiri and Ladakhi, constituting more than 20 per cent population of the State. They are the state's most populous Scheduled Tribe having a population of more than 20 lakh as per the 2011 census and one fourth of them are living nomadic life. Out of the total nomadic Gujjar-Bakarwals, 66 percent population in the state of Jammu & Kashmir are living Below Poverty Line, revealed a survey conducted by Tribal Research and Cultural Foundation (TRCF), a frontal organization working for the cause of Indian tribes. (Koundal 2012).

Literature Review

As tribal tourism is a type of tourism concerned with tribal community culture, values and life style. Among the elements of the tribal tourism development, the most important is the indigenous resources to provide the elements of tourism development. Johansena & Mehmetoglu (2011) empirical study indicate tribe, consisting of indigenous tourism products, mainly consists of four elements, habitat, handicrafts, heritage, and history, whereas these factors have influence for tourists' experiences and perceptions. Tourists visiting indigenous tourist attractions have a special interest in five central dimensions of a culture: gazing, lifestyle, authenticity, personal interaction, and informal learning (McIntosh & Ryan 2007).

Tribal tourism can also be considered a subset of "slow tourism". Slow tourism is an emerging concept that promotes a quality, meaningful and engaging experience which explores locations at a slower pace and in a manner, that supports the local and cultural environment (Dickinson & Lumsdon, 2010). Moreover, indigenous tourism development, in addition to attraction and cultural characteristics, the tribe to provide food, beverage and accommodation services; provide complementary and recreational facilities to meet the needs of tourists; integration of local tourism resources, a suite of travel products (Chang, Chang, & Wu, 2013; Chang & Chang Liao, 2014); convenient external transportation (Chang & Chang Liao, 2014); the tribe residents can friendly welcome outside visitors, and for the development of tourism has a positive attitude (Chang & Chang Liao, 2014; Lin & Chang, 2013).

The word 'Gujjar' is believed to have occurred in the 7th century AD literature of India; It was also traced in the works of famous poet Banabhatta especially in his book *Harshacharita* and the Chinese traveler Huentsang. As believed, word, 'Gujjar' is derivative of 'Gurujar' which is a Sanskrit word meaning "a valiant out to crush the enemies". With the constant usage the word got deformed in to "Gojjar" and then to Gujjar which further believed to have been derived from Gau-Char a cow and char (Charana) to graze (Shashi 1978). Gujjars are possibly the partial descendants of Eurasian people, including the Scythians, Georgians and Khazars of the Caspian Sea, who took part in the Scythian invasions of South Asia from 5th century BC to the 1st century AD, primarily settling in Gujarat, Punjab and Kashmir region. These Sun worshiping tribes ruled kingdoms covering much of the present-day Afghanistan, Punjab, Jammu & Kashmir, Gujarat, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Haryana, Orissa and Andhra Pradesh etc.

In Jammu and Kashmir, the population of Gujjar-Bakarwals, who move from place to place have certain characteristics, common with the Gujjars of Himachal Pradesh, Rajasthan and Punjab. Gujjars settled in northern Punjab have however left indelible mark in naming the localities like Gujarat or Gujranwala. Their emigration into Kashmir might have taken place from north Punjab, presumably during the Karkata period when parts of Punjab were included in Kashmir Empire. They disseminate almost in all parts of Jammu and Kashmir state such as Poonch, Rajouri, Jammu, Keller, Shopian, Tangdar, Karnah, Kulgam, Daksum, Pahalgam, Uri, etc.

On the cultural front they have adjusted themselves to different patterns of life and adjustment. Despite, Gujjar-Bakarwal in Jammu and Kashmir have taken to the Islamic faith and according to their dress, way of life, culture, customs and rituals are different as compared to their counterparts settled in other parts of the state. Moreover, they are closely associated with Kashmiris but they could not get influenced by their behavior and mode of living. Utender (1961) stated that “all Gujjar-Bakerwals possess a common speech (Gujari), which is a Hindi dialect quite distinct from the Punjabi or Pushto or Kashmiri. They wear very loose dress, (Shalwar) shirt (Kurta) waist coat and a special type of turban like that of Pathan’s called in their terminology (Pugg). The livelihood pattern, food and dietary practices and their attitude to various aspects of life, frequently differ from those of the non-tribal population (Sharma & Anita, 2009). Furthermore, many festivals celebrated by the Gujjars-Bakarwals are common among the Muslims of Kashmir but they also celebrate Baiskahi, lighting lamps on the graves and shrines which are very close to the festivals of Hindus of North India.

Impact of tourism on communities

The impacts of tourism development have historically been the most researched area of tourism and are thus considered to be an effective contributor of socio-economic development, particularly in less developed countries (Honey, 1999). Although the tourism has been adopted as a universal developmental option but it is still the subject of intense debate, the extent to which economic and social benefits inevitably follow the introduction and promotion of a tourism sector (Hall, 2007). To ensure the socio-cultural, political and economic sustainability of the industry, support from the local community is necessary. Their role in influencing the tourism development activities through working together with the government is vital (Jamaludin, et al., 2009). Hence, it is crucial to encourage affirmative perceptions among local residents as this affects their support on tourism.

Once a community becomes a tourism destination, the lives of the residents are influenced by that particular development; thus, effecting their Quality of Life (Gursoy, et al, 2002). Worldwide tourism has become one of the largest and fastest growing industries. However, the growth in the tourism industry does not occur without challenges. It brings both benefits and costs to the residents of a host community, consequently generating both positive and negative tourism impacts. However, tourism development generates many essential consequences that may have an effect on that specific area. Besides generating constructive impacts such as enhancing local economies, being a source of new employment opportunities, additional tax receipts, foreign exchange earnings and income, tourism development have the potential towards negative outcomes (Ko & Steward, 2002). Some residents expected to perceive tourism as having positive socio-cultural and environmental impacts and some inclined to see tourism as having negative economic, socio-cultural and environmental impacts as tourism lends itself to interaction between hosts and guests which can be catalyst for change in cultural and community life (Smith, 1998). Physical congestion experienced at the destination and increasing demand for natural resources contributes to the source of solid waste residual, thus creating the problem of air, water and noise pollution and degradation of environmental factors. Allen et al. (1993) argued that communities with low tourism and strong total economic activity will foresee tourism development more favourable than communities with low tourism and high economic activity and communities with high tourism development and weak economic activity. Meanwhile, few researchers found that besides economic development and job creation, tourism also brings infrastructural changes to destinations. The growth of tourism creates a need for an improved infrastructure in developing economies (WTO, 2002b); modernized transportation systems; water supplies and improvement in sanitation arrangements; and better access to roads, airports, telephone systems and other public utilities may have to be extended. Thus, it is worthwhile to examine the tourism industry as an agent of development, an anti-poverty tool, as well as the actions that need to be taken by governments to support the sustainable growth of this sector.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this research analysis will assist the Gujjar Bakarwal community to be involved in economic activities in developing the area into cultural tourism attractions. This outcome will benefit the state government, tourists and Gujjar-Bakarwals communities of J&K. The research study will focus on

community activities, cultural and heritage analysis. The aim of this research is that these Gujjar-Bakarwal community villages can boast their indigenous cultural heritage as a tourism attraction.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives have been formulated for the present study:

1. To study the historical background of Gujjar - Bakarwal tribe of J&K.
2. To explore the factors influencing the perception of tribal community residents towards tourism development.
3. To measure the perception of the tribal community towards tourism development impact in select destinations.
4. To suggest the strategies for Tribal Tourism Development in the state.

Research Methodology

The target population for the study were the tribal members of Gujjar- Bakarwal tribe residing at Pahalgam and Sonamarg; the two different tourist destinations of South and Central Kashmir. The proposed sample size for the study has been estimated on the basis of item to response ratio, it ranges from 1:4 to 1:10 (Hinkin, 2005) or even may range from 1:5 to 1:10 (Hair, et.al, 2006). The total number of item in the questionnaire was 17; therefore, the estimated sample size for the current study was 170.

The research design method in this study is a combination of exploratory, qualitative and descriptive design. The exploratory studies are done when the researcher is examining a new interest, or when the subject is relatively uncharted (Wagenaar & Babbie, 1998). The goal of this exploratory research is to formulate a problem area more precisely and clarifying research concepts of gathering explanations and insight. While descriptive research describes data and characteristics about the population or phenomenon being studied.

Both Primary and Secondary sources have been used for data collection. Primary data has been collected through structured questionnaire, the variables were adopted from Lankford & Howard (1994) and Latkova & Vogt (2012) as the standardized of measurement of resident attitudes towards tourism. For final data collection, the researcher approached 200 respondents through convenience sampling technique. This sampling technique implies that participants were chosen based on availability; therefore based on convenience (Tustin, 2005; Du Plooy, 2002). Out of which 172 (*Missing values, outliers, and unengaged responses were deleted*) were available for final analysis. Normality of data was checked by skewness & kurtosis measures of the entire construct used in the study. It resulted between -1.60 and +0.78 respectively, which established the normality of data.

Reliability and Validity

Reliability of the data was checked through Cronbach alpha ($\alpha = 0.805$) which indicates that the scale has internal consistency (i.e. each question within a measure is actually measuring the same phenomenon), hence no changes in the instruments was required. Variables for the study have been adopted from the Latkova & Vogt (2012) and Lankford & Howard (1994) based on a series of review on the existing literature dealing with local community attitudes toward tourism development, therefore, this did not involve a recheck of content validity.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was carried out through SPSS in order to identify the various factors that influence the tribal community in various ways at the selected destinations. It was carried out with principal component analysis along with the orthogonal rotation procedure of Varimax for summarizing the original information with minimum factors and optimal coverage (Table 1). Before conducting the exploratory factor analysis, Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity tests are confirmed, as these two tests are the prerequisites and indicate the suitability of the data for factor analysis. The KMO value is 0.82, greater than the threshold of 0.7; and the significance value of Bartlett's test of sphericity was .000, hence the data is considered to be appropriate for Factor Analysis.

Table 1: Factor Analysis and mean of Tourism Development Impact

Factors	Items	Rotated Factor loading	Mean	Eigen value	Variance extracted
Economic Impact from Tourism Development	The benefits of tourism to the community outweigh its costs.	.778	3.56	5.332	27.213
	Tourism creates desirable employment opportunity for the residents in the community	.731	3.48		
	Local businesses benefit the most from tourists	.776	3.59		
	Standard of living has increased due to tourist spending to the community	.779	3.96		
	Tourism helps improve the economic situation for many residents in the community	.723	3.76		
	The cost of living in the community was remained as low as before tourism was introduced	.602	2.14		
Environmental Impact from Tourism Development	Tourism contributes to the negative effects of vegetation and loss of meadows, and green space	.792	3.72	4.335	21.596
	Tourism produces large quantities of waste products	.761	3.68		
	Tourism has not improved the ecological environment of the community in many ways	.748	4.10		
	Tourism caused environmental pollution to the destination.	.658	3.72		
	Tourism development causes congestion.	.602	3.34		
	Local residents feel uncomfortable living in tourists' hotspot	.513	3.32		
Social Impact from Tourism Development	Increase tourism provides more recreational activities for residents	.788	4.06	3.982	19.104
	Tourism has increased residents pride in the area	.751	3.82		
	Tourism negatively contributes social problems such as crime, drug use, prostitution, and so forth to the community	.897	3.58		
	Tourism has not resulted unpleasant overcrowded situation for the community	.705	3.63		
	Tourism development does not modify/ change our culture.	.598	3.65		
Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings (Cumulative % of variance)					67.913

Perception of Tribal Community towards Tourism Development

- **Economic Impact from Tourism Development:** Factor-1, economic impact is the most important factor of tourism development impact in the region as 27.213 percent of variation is being explained by this factor and it is determined by the attributes like employment opportunity for the locals, business opportunities, increase in standard of living, improve economic situation etc. From analyzing the data, it is noted that the majority of the respondents agreed that standard of living increased due to tourist spending (M=3.96) the reason could be that tourism is the only economic source in the area; these findings are substantiated with the study of Hanafiah, et al. (2010) who state that tourism also becomes the symbol to support the communities especially in changing the economic atmosphere. This is because of the ability of the tourism industry to generate income, currency exchanges as well as provide the employment opportunity. Further, local business benefit most from the tourist (M=3.59) followed by the benefits of tourism to the community outweigh its costs (M=3.56). But on the other hand, the respondents perceived that cost of living in the community is increased due tourism, rise in real estate demand increase building costs and land values. Moreover, increasing demand for basic services and goods from tourists will often cause raised prices that negatively affect local residents whose income does not increase proportionately.
- **Environmental Impact from Tourism Development:** Environmental impact is the second essential component of the tourism impact and explained 21.596 % of the total variation in the current study. The majority agreed that, tourism brings negative effects on vegetation and loss of meadows, and green environment (M=3.72) also it caused environmental pollution to the destination (M=3.72). Further, majority perceived that tourism has not improved the ecological environment of the community in many ways. The findings of the study corroborate with the studies of Smith and Krannich (1998) and Pearce (1980), who argue that greater the density of tourists, the more environmentally aware are the residents, and the greater is their perception of the environmental costs resulting from tourism.

- ***Social Impact from Tourism Development:*** Tourism is a socio-cultural event for both the guest and host, if tourism is to merit its pseudonym of being 'the hospitality industry' it must look beyond its own doors and employees to consider the social and cultural impacts it is having on the host community at large (Murphy 1985). This factor explained 19.104% of the total variation in the present study. Majority of the respondent agreed that increase in tourism provides more recreational activities for residents (M=4.06). It lies in the fact that due to tourism development in the region causes the increase in recreational facilities which extend the benefit to locals as well. This is substantiated with some previous studies like, Kim (2002) & Deery et al, (2012) who acknowledge that due to tourism services and activities in a community, more recreational facilities may be provided for residents. According to Besculides, et al. (2002) there has been an increase in tourism for experiencing another culture. Therefore, tourism has become a major source of international cultural contact in the modern world. Tourism has increased residents pride in the area (M=3.82) is the second most contributing item. This result is in line with some previous studies conducted by Dogan (1989) who stated that presenting one's culture to tourists strengthens the idea of what it means to live within a community. Therefore, identity, pride, cohesion and support within a community are enhanced.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The current study provided an insight about the historical background of Gujjar - Bakarwal Tribe and their perception regarding tourism. The community is socially and economically deprived and is not being fully integrated in the main stream of regional culture and social status. The socio-economic profile of Gujjar-Bakerwal community in the State is changing with time but still it is not up to a satisfactory level. Their unique tribal culture and distinct heritage remain preserved which is rarely available elsewhere in the world, and having a great potential of development of indigenous tourism which can make a significant contribution to marginalized communities in developing countries and, where aligned to volunteer tourism, the potential for increased positive impacts on the host community can increase (Oppermann & Chon, 1997; Scheyvens, 2002).

During empirical investigation of the study, three factors were identified regarding the impact of tourism in the areas of tribal communities, among which the most important factor was the economic impact followed by environmental and social. The local indigenous community agrees that tourism has a great potential to benefit their community in term of employment opportunity, improvement of economic situation of their tribe and its influence on improvement of standard of living. On the other hand, they also acknowledge the negative impacts of tourism on ecological environment of the community in many ways. As the results of the study evidently signify that the destination community views a more positive side of tourism than negative aspect.

To develop tourism in destinations under study it is suggested that to identify cultural products of the indigenous community and how these can be commercialized as a tourism product; which will help in the economic development of the community, besides preservation of traditional culture; development of tourism in tribal destinations, the key components of which are tribal cultural, natural environment recourses and friendly inhabitants, destinations under consideration. Therefore, local community support is extremely important for successful functioning of tourism activities at the destination, as it is impossible to sustain tourism to a destination that is not supported by the local community.

Consequently, the local community should be involved in decision making process and should be given an influential voice rather than merely being a passive recipient. In the current study majority of respondents have a negative perception regarding the increase in social problems due to tourism, so there is need to take the cognizance of the matter and educate the community about the benefits of tourism. The government should promote home stay facilities and encourage tourists to visit these rural destinations. Moreover, there is also a need to examine the impact of tourism development on quality of life of inhabitants.

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The Influence of Event Image on the Destination Image and Behavioral Intentions of Event Participants - A Case Study of International Film Festival of India

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken to provide a theoretical understanding and empirical examination of influence of Event Image on Event Behavioral Intention, Destination Image and Destination Behavioral Intention of event participants, as well as to investigate whether Event participants relate Dimensions of Event Image with Destination Image. The Data was collected from 383 event participants of International Film Festival of India 2015 held in Goa from 20th November 2015 to 30th November 2015. The Statistical Package SPSS version 22 were used to perform various statistical tests. Analysis of the data revealed that Image of the International Film Festival of India plays an important Role in influencing the image of Goa. It also has an ability to influence Participants' Destination Behavioral Intentions as well as event Behavioral Intention.

Keywords: *Event Image, Destination Image, Event Behavioral Intention & Destination Behavioral Intention*

Introduction

Background: "Tourism is conceived as an easy means of boosting a national or regional economy, as it may bring investment, create jobs, and promote sales of crafts and local artifacts" (Pandey et al., 1995). "Increasingly, cities, and nations are turning to tourism as an important element in their economic portfolio. If it is handled appropriately, tourism can also become an important engine for achieving broader social goals." (Crouch & Ritchie, 1999) According to UNWTO 2015 report, "Tourism has evolved into a global phenomenon – one of the most important economic sectors and social activities of our time. Today, it contributes directly to 10% of the world's GDP; one in 11 jobs globally and contributes US \$ 1.5 trillion in world export." As per the projection of UNWTO (2015) "...international tourist arrivals worldwide by 2020 is expected to reach close to 1.4 billion. The 1.5 billion mark will be in sight by 2023 and 1.8 billion by 2030." This growth in tourism industry has attracted destination managers to develop new tourism destinations. However, "as a socio-economic activity, tourism does not occur randomly. Some destinations appear to be more successful than others in offering tourism activities and in attracting tourists." (Formica et al., 1998) Apart from this, "Today's tourist is facilitated by increased leisure time, rising level of disposable income and more efficient transportation network" (Echtner & Ritchie 1993). So on one side there are several choices available for the traveler and on the other side they have become quite selective in deciding which destination to travel, leading to increase in challenges before the destination marketers. "In order to remain competitive ...in today's world, destinations will have to design and implement strategies and marketing initiatives which addresses to achieve the desired product positions in the target markets" (Hawkes & Kwortnik 2010). "A key component of this positioning process is the creation and management of a distinctive and appealing perception or image of the destination" (Calantone et. al, 1989).

According to Crompton (1979) Destination Image is, "the sum of beliefs, ideas, and impressions that people have of a destination". The destination images held by consumers are so powerful that they can either benefit the country or have a negative impact. "In order to benefit the destination, images have to be distinctive, appealing, simple, and most importantly, believable and should be based on reality" (Kotler & Gartner 2002).

Image of the destination perceived by the tourist plays a crucial role in understanding the behavior of tourist as well as developing appropriate marketing strategies. Researchers in the past in travel and tourism have demonstrated that Destination Image plays a vital role in influencing the behavior of tourist. Tourist behavior is a Collective term, which includes pre-visit's decision making, attitude during the stay and post - visit behavioral intention i.e. Intention to revisit the destination and willingness to recommend the destination to others. "It is argued that image will influence a tourist in the process of choosing a stay, the

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subsequent evaluation of the stay and in his or her future intentions” (Bigne et al, 2001) this stimulated to investigate factors influencing Destination Image in the academic field. “Secondary & primary information sources, motivations ,experience of leisure travel and socio demographic characteristics related to gender, age, level of education, social class, and country of origin are some of the factors that determine the formation of post-visit image of the destination”. Beerli & Martin (2004).The studies of Richards & Wilson (2004), Dimeo & Kay (2004), Boo & Busser (2006) have identified Event as one of the factor which plays vital role in enhancing the image of the host destination and further to this researcher like Kaplanidou & Gibson (2010), Kaplanidou & Vogt (2007), Kim & Chalip (2004) demonstrated its influence on the tourist Behavioral Intentions. The successful hosting of mega-events has been purported to not only increase awareness and enhance the image of the host country, but to also create a stronger competitive position and greater benefits from tourists in the long-run” (Ritchie & Smith, 1991).

Donald Getz (2008) mentions that “Events are an important motivator of tourism, and figure prominently in the development and marketing plans of most Destinations. Destinations develop, facilitate and promote Events of all kinds to meet multiple goals: to attract tourists, to serve as a catalyst, to foster a positive Destination Image and contribute to general place marketing”. Kaplanidou & Vogt, (2007), Getz & Anderson, (2010) states that “Destination and Event Images have the potential to influence Behavioral Intentions to revisit the Destination for vacation or to participate in the Event again”. The phenomenon of hosting events for tourism has been extensively discussed in both the tourism and event fields. “The tourism literature concentrates on whether events can improve or otherwise change the image of the hosting destination”. (Deng & Li, 2013) “In the event field, related studies have focused on the economic, socio-cultural, and environmental effects of these events on the host city or country.” (Getz, 2008).However, Most of the researchers have focused their studies on assessing the relationship of Sports Events and Destination Image particularly Mega Sports events like Olympic, World Cup etc., Limited number of studies is found in the academic literature which assessed the contribution of recurring annual cultural or leisure events on the event participant’s image of the host Destination and Future Behavioral Intentions. Hence, the main purpose of the current study is to determine the role of event image in influencing event participant’s image of the host destination and their event and destination behavioral intention.

Literature Review

The processes of conceptualization of Destination Image have been started from 1970 onwards and it continues till date. The reason behind this could be destination image is a complex term to understand and to define. Hence, several researchers have made an attempt to understand the concept of Destination Image. Literature presents various definitions of the term destination image. However, the most commonly used definition is the definition of Crompton (1979), According to him, “Destination Image is the sum of beliefs, ideas and impressions that a person has of a destination.” Other researchers who have contributed in the field of Destination Image are Echtner & Ritchie who defines Destination Image as, “The perceptions of individual destination attributes and the holistic impression made by the destination”. In addition to this he also states that a destination image is processed in a three dimensional space: namely functional, psychological and holistic, whereas Baloglu & Brinberg, (1997) and Baloglu & McCleary, (1999a) states that Destination Image construct has at least two distinctive elements they are Cognitive and Affective. The Cognitive, element refers to all knowledge, perceptions, and beliefs that potential travelers hold about a destination and interprets image as a set of relevant attributes. Affective, element of Destination Image refers to consumers’ feelings about a destination, which can be favorable, unfavorable, or neutral. The association of Cognitive and Affective elements leads to a behavioral, or cognitive component of Destination Image (Gartner 1993).

Gartner 1993, states that, "Image formation is defined as a construction of a mental representation of a destination on the basis of information cues delivered by the image formation agents and selected by a person." Literature related to Destination image suggests three sources of image formation they are Destination promoters, autonomous and Image receiver himself. Balogu and McCleary (1999b) and Beerli and Martin (2004) states that “Destination Image is formed by two main factors i.e. stimulus factors (external factors) and traveler’s characteristics (internal factors)”. Stimulus factors are

information received from various sources which include organic, autonomous, induced, and modified induced sources (Echtner & Ritchie, 1991), whereas Internal Factors includes individual characteristics which are socio-demographic factors like age, gender, social class, level of education, country of origin, ethnicity/race etc. and Psychological characteristics like personal needs, preferences, interests, motivations, values, prior knowledge, personality, and lifestyle.

Literature reviews various stages of image formation. Gunn (1988) model of image formation is of seven stages:

1. Formation of mental image about holiday experiences
2. Modification of above images based on information search
3. Decision is taken about vacation based on Mental Image and Further Information
4. Actual Travel to the Destination
5. Experience the Destination during the trip
6. Return from the trip and
7. Further Modification of images depending on the vacation experience

The studies of Chon (1990), (1991), Chen and Tsai (2007), Fakeye and Crompton (1991), Lee, Lee, and Lee (2005) revealed the substantial influence of Destination Image on tourist behavior. Warshaw and Davis (1985) defined behavioral intentions as, “the degree to which a person has formulated conscious plans to perform or none perform some specified future behavior.” Future Behavior Intention means Intention to repeat visit/Purchase and Willingness to recommend. “Revisit intention refers to tourist willingness or plans to visit the same destination again” Cole & Scott, (2004). According to Zeithaml, Berry & Parasuraman (1996) “Revisit intentions can be defined as the intention of consumers to experience the same product, brand, place or region in the future”.

According to Reichheld & Sasser, (1990); Shoemaker & Lewis, (1999) “Repeat purchase has been accepted as one of the most important subjects in contemporary marketing. In many studies, benefits of repeat purchase are often noted as 1)attracting previous customers is more cost-effective than gaining new ones,(2) 5% increase in customer retention could increase profit by 25–85% and (3) customer retention tends to yield positive word-of-mouth.”“ This phenomenon of repeat visit is also accepted in the field of tourism, indeed, many travel destinations rely heavily on repeat visitors” (Darnell & Johnson, 2001).

Richins, (1984) states that, "Word-of-mouth is a form of interpersonal communication concerning a consumer's experience with an organization, product, or service". Mangold, Miller and Brockway (1999) described word-of-mouth as a “Dominant force in the marketplace”, while Bendapudi and Berry (1997) noted that word-of-mouth is the “Ultimate test of the customer's relationship and shows “.... whether the customer is willing to become an advocate” for a brand. According to Reichheld & Sasser, (1990), Word-of-mouth referrals account for up to 60% of sales to new customers. Researchers like Herr, Kardes, & Kim, (1991), in their studies discussed Image as an antecedent to word-of-mouth activity and is recognized as an indicator of consumer loyalty.

According to (Gunn, 1988; Fakeye & Crompton, 1991).Influence of Destination Image on tourists' behavior can be divided into four aspects:

1. Pre-visit decision-making
2. On-site experience
3. Impressions of their experience, and
4. Post-visit Intentions

Further, Chon (1990) & Echtner & Ritchie (1991) say that “Destination Image is strongly believed to influence a tourist's choice of Destination”. According to Bigne, Sanchez & Sanchez (1999), Weaver and Lawton, (2006), Tasci & Gartner (2007), “Destination Image appears to have the most important effect on post – visit behavior of the tourist i.e. the visitors judgment about the likeliness to revisit or to the willingness to recommend the Destinations to others. After the visit, a traveler recollects their experience and evaluates the good or bad aspects of the Destination against their pre-trip perception. Destination Image is refined and this Image has an impact on traveler's future purchasing behavior. A positive Image

may serve as a pull factor for the Destination and increase the likelihood of re-visitation and recommendation to others”.

Mendes, Valle, &Guerreiro, (2010) state that “Tourist nowadays seeks memorable experiences in memorable places and the participation in Events during their stay can contribute to these feelings & the process of Image formation”. According to Getz (1999)“A special Event is a onetime or infrequently occurring Event outside the normal program or activities of the sponsoring or organizing body. To the customer, a special Event is an opportunity for a leisure, social, or cultural experience outside the normal range of choices or beyond everyday experience”. Events provide a unique experience and create an Image which has a significant impact on the participants of the Event. Gwinner (1997), defines “an Event’s Image is a function of the type of Event (e.g., sports, festival, arts), Event characteristics (e.g., size, professional status, history, venue, promotional appearance), and individual factors (e.g., meanings associated with the Event, strength of meanings, and past history with the Event)”. According to Kaplanidou (2006) “Event Image could consist of similar components to those of the Destination’s Image”. On these lines of discussion we can say that Event Image is created by various Dimensions of the Event and hence identifying Dimensions having influence on Event Image is necessary. Demanche (2003) mentions that “Destinations are attracted to hosting sport Events to draw marketing benefits that will contribute to the success of the Destination in the long run by creating awareness, improving their Image with visitors, and attracting tourism business to generate future inbound travel”. Several studies have found the influence of event on the image of the destination (Mossberg & Hallberg (1999), Erfurt & Johnson (2003), Richards & Wilson (2004), Kim & Morrison (2005), Lee, Lee & Lee (2005),Lee, Taylor, McCartney (2005). Dai & Bao (2006), Boo & Busser (2006), Hede (2006), Florek, Breitbarth & Conejo (2008) etc), although limited but few researchers have also tested the influence of event image on the image of destination (Kaplanidou, 2007 & Deng and Li, 2013) and destination Behavioral Intentions, (Xing & Chalip , 2004, Kouthouris & Alexandris, 2005, Kaplanidou & Vogt, 2007, Kaplanidou & Gibson, 2010).

Research Objective

The study was undertaken with following objectives:

1. To assess the influence of International Film Festival of India on participants Event Image and Event Behavioural Intention.
2. To Study the influence of Event Image on Event participants Destination Image and Destination Behavioural Intention.

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study purpose.

Hypotheses H1: Event Image influences participant’s Behavioral Intention towards the Event, Destination image & Destination Behavioral Intentions.

H1a: Event Image will influence event participant’s intention to Re - participate in the event

H1b: Event image will influence event participant’s intention to recommend the event to others.

H1c: Event image will influence event participants Image of the host Destination.

H1d: Event Image will influence event participant’s intention to revisit the destination.

H1e: Event Image will influence event participant’s intention to recommend the destination to others.

Methodology

To achieve the research objectives, the present study adopted a mixed method approach i.e. qualitative as well as quantitative approach. The qualitative method was adopted to identify the dimensions of Event and Destination Image. The type of qualitative data that was used includes interviews with local tour operators and materials posted by the International, National and Local tour operators on their websites. The result of qualitative analyses was used to develop structured questionnaire to be used in quantitative research.

The questionnaire as a survey instrument for this research was designed after including all the constructs. The questions were framed based on literature review and specific Destination & Event characteristics. The survey instrument was revised and finalized based on feedback from four professors from the

Masters of Business Administration department of Goa University and one expert each from tourism and Event management field. A pilot study was conducted with 35 attendees of International Film Festival of India (IFFI) 2014. Hence, the content validity was assumed as adequate. The questionnaire was divided into five sections. Section I deals with 41 attributes of International film festival of India based on the observations of the researcher made during 2014 IFFI & discussion with IFFI management. Section II deals with two items of future Behavioral Intentions(likeliness to re - participate& recommending the Event to others).Section III deals with 26 attributes of Destination Image extracted from Beerli& Martin,2004 study, Content analyses of travel websites& a survey conducted on 67 tourist who visited Goa in the month of October 2014.Section IV deals with two item of future Behavioral Intentions(i.e. likeliness to revisit & recommending the Destination to others).Section V is related to Demographic characteristics of the respondent. For section I & section III Respondents were asked to indicate their experience on a five point Likert type scale “Very Good = 5, to Very Bad = 1”. For Section II & Section IV respondent are asked to indicate their agreement on a five – point Likert type scale “5 = Very likely to 1 = Very unlikely.

The Event selected for the purpose of study was International Film Festival of India 2015(IFFI). This annual Event is organized in Goa by the directorate of film festival of India in collaboration with Entertainment society of Goa for the last 10 years. The Event is attended by over 10,000 to 12,000International, National & Local delegates. The study was carried out in IFFI 2015, which was held from 20th November 2015 to 30th November 2015.International & National delegates were considered to be the target population. Total 325 usable samples were obtained at the end of the Event. The data was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. The techniques applied to determine the study findings are Descriptive statistics and Multiple Regression analyses. Respondents’ Demographic profile was analysed using descriptive statistics like frequency and the hypothesis was tested by using multiple regression analyses.

DATA ANALYSIS

Demographic profile of the respondent: The demographic profile of the 325 respondents is presented in Table 1 where gender, age group, level of education, occupation and visits to Goa are presented.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the respondents (N = 325)

Respondents Profile		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	224	68.92
	Female	101	31.08
	Total	325	100.00
Age Group	Less than 25	57	17.53
	26 – 40	141	43.38
	41 – 55	96	29.53
	55 & above	31	9.54
	Total	325	100.00
Level of Education	Up to high school	19	5.87
	Up to higher secondary	29	8.9
	Up to graduation	116	35.7
	Above graduation	161	49.5
	Total	325	100.00
Occupation	Employed	106	32.6
	Student	56	17.2
	Business	46	14.2
	Housewife	29	8.9
	Retired	27	8.3
	Others	61	18.70
	Total	325	100.00
Visits to Goa	First time	91	27.99
	Repeater	97	29.8
	Regular	137	42.2
	Total	325	100.00

The summary of demographic characteristics of respondents is reported in the Table 4.1. It was found that male respondents (n =224) were more than Female respondent (n= 101). Majority (43.38%) of the subjects were in the age group of 26 – 40 years followed by 29.53%, 17.53% and 9.54% between the age group 41 -55, up to 25 years and 55 and above. In regard to level of education 161 (49.5%) were having qualification above graduation 116(35.7%) respondents were graduates, 29(8.9%) respondents were studied up to Higher secondary School and 19(5.87%) pursued their education up to school level. Majority of the respondent were employed (32.6%). followed by (18.70%), (17.2%), (14.2%), (8.9%) and (8.3%) others, students, Business, Housewife and Retired. The majority of study sample were Regular visitor to Goa137 (42.2%) followed by Repeat visitors 97(29.8%) and First Time Visitors 91(27.99%).

Table 12: Influence of Event Image on participant's Event Behavioral Intention, Destination Image & Destination Behavioral Intentions (N = 325)

Influence of Event Image on participants:	R Square	F	Std beta	Sig.
Intention to re-participate in the Event	.075	26.237	.274	.000
Intention to recommend the Event to others	.102	36.654	.320	.000
Destination Image	.020	6.421	.141	.012*
Intention to revisit the Destination	.106	37.355	.326	.000
Intention to recommend the Destination to others	.080	27.358	.283	.000

Note: * $p < 0.05$

In the analyses intention to re participate in the Event, intention to recommend the Event to others, Destination Image, intention to revisit the Destination and intention to recommend the Destination were used as dependent variable and Event Image is treated as independent variable. Based on this the hypotheses H1 & sub hypotheses H1a to H1e were tested. The sub hypotheses tested were all supported. Showing support to hypotheses H1 i.e. Event Image influences participant's Behavioral Intention towards the Event, Destination image & Destination Behavioral Intentions. The R Square ranged from .075 to .106 in case of supported hypotheses. Event Image significantly influences participants intention to re participate in the Event (std beta = 0.27, $p < 0.000$), intention to recommend the Event to others (std beta = 0.32), $p < 0.000$, influence on Destination Image (std beta = 0.14), $p < 0.012$, intention to revisit the Destination (std beta = 0.32), $p < 0.000$ & intention to recommend the Destination to others (std beta = 0.28, $p < 0.000$). Hence, the findings showed a fairly strong support for H1a: Event Image will influence event participant's intention to Re participate in the event, H1b. Event image will influence event participant's intention to recommend the event to others, H1c. Event image will influence event participants Image of the host Destination, H1d. Event Image will influence event participant's intention to revisit the destination, H1e. Event Image will influence event participant's intention to recommend the destination to others.

Discussion

Influence of Event Image on Participants Event Behavioral Intentions: The result of the study shows that event image plays an important role in the participants' decision to re - participate in the event in future as well as their willingness to recommend the event to others. Specific studies which analyses the influence of event image on Intention to revisit the event in futures are scarce with two exceptions Hallmann, Kaplanidou & Breuer (2010) have shown positive influence of sport event image on indentation to revisit the event in future. However these studies have predicated the pre – event intention of those who had previous experience with the event. The present study has assessed the intentions during the event on first time, repeat and regular visitors. The other researchers like Kaplanidou, Jordan, Funk and Rindinger in (2012) who conducted study on active event sport tourists of a recurring marathon event shown that event behavioral intention is predicted by the convergence of destination characteristics and event characteristics. However the study of Kaplanidou and Gibson (2010) highlights the mediating effects of attitudes between satisfaction and intentions to re-participate in the event. There is paucity of research in assessing the intention of event participants to recommend the event to others. This study is one of its kinds which have made a contribution to the body of knowledge by bringing out evidence which indicates that event image also influences willingness to recommend the event to others. Recommendation intention is considered to be strength because new people can participate in the event which will increase the number of attendees in the event.

Influence of Event Image on Participants Destination Image: A remarkable number of studies have been conducted to assess the influence of event on Destination Image with varied approach but most of these studies have measured either the influence of event telecast, event media on the viewers Destination Image or Meier assessment of Destination Image before, during or after the event Like Rivenburgh (1992), Jaffe and Nebenzahl (1993), Rivenburgh, (1995), Chalip and Green (2003), Diemo & Kay (2004), Ritchie, Sanders, Mules (2007) assessed the Impact of media telecast of event on the potential visitors perception of destination Image. The studies of Jaffe and Nebenzahl (1993) & Chalip and Green (2003) and Ritchie, Sanders, Mules (2007) indicated positive result; study of Diemo & Key (2004) shows negative effect whereas no enhancement in destination image is noticed in the studies of Rivernburg (1992) & (1995). The research of Ritchie & Smith (1991); Mossberg & Hallberg (1999); Erfurt & Johnson (2003); Richards & Wilson (2004); Kim & Morrison (2005); Lee, Lee & Lee (2005); Lee and Taylor (2005); Dai & Bao (2006); Boo & Busser (2006); Florek, Breitbarth & Conejo (2008); measured the destination image of either the potential visitors or actual visitors either before ,after or during the event or together and provided sufficient evidence of positive effect on the Destination Image whereas the studies of Dai & Bao (2006), Boo & Busser (2006) noted negative effect of destination. However there are only two researchers who have measured the image of the event and its influence on the destination Image. The first contribution is made by Kaplanidou & Vogt (2007) who have shown positive effect of event on the Destination Image, There study is on the active Bicycle sport tourists emotional experience during the event and failed to cover other dimensions of the event. The other contributor in this field is the research of Deng and Li (2013) on the 2010 Shanghai World Expo which shows that the event image had a strong positive effect on the destination image; however the responses were taken from the foreign tourist who visited china during the event not with pure intention to participate in the event. The present study also is in consistent with the above two researchers and also supports the notion that event Image plays important role in enhancing the Destination Image of the event participants. But this study measures the responses of actual participants of event whose main intention is to participate in the event and have actually experienced various dimensions of event which gave them exposure to different attraction of Goa as well sufficient time to explore them and hence event image influences destination image.

Influence of Event Image on Participants Destination Behavioral Intentions: The study revealed the fact that Event Image has the capacity to singularly influence Event Participants Destination Behavioral Intentions. Earlier research of Chalip and Green (2003), Lee, Lee & Lee (2005), Xing and Chalip (2006), Kaplanidou & Vogt (2007), Kaplanidou & Gibson (2010), Deng & Li (2013) indicates a relational effect of Event Image on Destination Behavior Intention being moderated by Destination Image. However, the present Study proves that Event Image directly can have influence on Participants Destination Behavioral Intentions.

Conclusion

The study of Kaplanidou & C. Vogt (2007) suggested that the Image of the Event is a key factor in generating Destination Image and re-visitation behavior. This study also supports the notion that Event Image plays important role in creating Destination Image & revisit intention and also contributes by showing its impact on willingness to recommend the Destination to others

To the Destination marketers, the result of this study provides enough justification to use Events as one of the tools for Destination marketing. Destination Promoters & Suppliers of tourism experience can use this Event to promote Destinations' culture, leisure & recreation, social environment & Natural Resources of the place

Research has shown that Event Image predicts Destination future behavior intention of the participants i.e. revisit intention to the Destination & willingness to recommend the Destination to others. Hence, Destination attributes should include Event as one of the attributes of a place which has a significant impact on Image of the Destination. Similarly

Limitations & Future Research

The model suggested in the study is tested in one single Event & respondents were non local event participants and hence, the results cannot be generalized. This model needs to be tested in different types of events on participants as well as non-participants of the event including local as well as non-local respondents. Future research can also test the moderating effect of number of visits and demographic characteristics of the respondent.

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Job Satisfaction among Employees: A Need for the Emergent Hospitality Industry in India for Employee Retention

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to analyze the effect of level of job satisfaction among hotel employees on employee retention, since employee satisfaction is a reliable predictor of employee retention. It is seen that whenever employers focus more on employee centered policies the level of satisfaction improves amongst the workers and a satisfied worker stays longer with organization. Bundelkhand is the heartland of India rich in tourism potential but still is quite unexposed. This particular study has been restricted to the Bundelkhand region of Uttar Pradesh. Some of the hotels of this region have been taken into consideration. The sample size of the study is 100 employees who are selected through convenient sampling. Hypotheses of the job satisfaction study are investigated through appropriate statistical tools. For the purpose of this study the Short form of the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire has been used due to lack of time. The findings showed that both intrinsic & extrinsic forms of job satisfaction are indirectly proportional to turnover intention. Although intrinsic forms of job satisfaction have a stronger influence, the extrinsic factors of job satisfaction should also be considered in evaluation of employee retention. The study signifies that high level of job satisfaction among hotel employees is leading to retention & reduced turnover intention. Thus satisfaction level of employees influences to a large extent on their decision to continue to work or quit the organization. In conclusion, findings of the study suggest that there is a positive correlation between job satisfaction & employee retention.

Keywords: *Job satisfaction, Employee Retention, Hospitality, Extrinsic factors, Intrinsic factor sand Human Resource.*

Introduction

The term hospitality is derived from the Latin word “*Hospitalitem*” meaning friendliness. Hospitality is defined by the Oxford Dictionary as “The friendly & generous reception & entertainment of guests or strangers.” Hospitality is a component of any activity that entails treatment of customers as guests. Major segment of hospitality industry comprises of Hotel & Restaurants, Travel & Tourism. In India, hotel industry is moderately well developed and forms the crux of the hospitality business in the country. With a consistently growing middle class and increasing disposable income, the tourism and hospitality sector is witnessing a healthy growth and accounts for 7.5 percent of the country’s GDP. According to a report by KPMG, the hospitality sector in India is expected to grow at 16.1 percent CAGR to reach Rs. 2,796.9 thousand crore in 2022.

In today’s working environment, employee retention issues are increasing at an alarming rate. So the need for employee job satisfaction arises so that the hospitality employees intent to stay in the organization for long. Employee retention directly affects the human resource practices of the organization such as recruitment, selection, training, etc. Moreover, if the employees quit the organization quickly it would be very difficult to overcome the shortage of employees abruptly and further it will increase the workload on the existing employees. Due to augmented competition, globalization and need for competence, various hospitality organizations are adopting strategies such as organizational restructuring and downsizing thereby resulting in job insecurity, job dissatisfaction, low commitment and increased turnover rate among employees. Thus employee retention has a major impact on the organization’s productivity, efficiency and sustainability. Employee job satisfaction helps in ascertaining the contentment of employees and pleasing their desires & needs on work. Job satisfaction is regarded as a comprehensive paradigm that comprises of employee feelings about a multiplicity of both intrinsic and extrinsic variables. According to Vroom (1964), job satisfaction is an orientation of emotions that employees possess towards role they are performing at the work place. For motivation & support of employees towards better performance, job satisfaction is a vital component. Light (2004) & Clark (2001) argue that employee satisfaction has been found to be positively related to the intent to remain with the company and negatively related to intention to quit and turnover. According to Mitchell (2001) departing

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employees take away a great deal of accumulated knowledge with them. Hospitality organizations are now consciously thinking about ways and means of retaining competent employees. Consequently this research will refer to literature about employee job satisfaction and its factors responsible for employee retention. It also studies about the need for extrinsic & intrinsic factors in job satisfaction for employee retention.

Intrinsic Job Satisfaction Factors: Herzberg (Herzberg et al., 1959; Herzberg, 1966) termed these as motivating factors that centered on achievement, recognition, responsibility, advancement, growth, and the work itself. Although their absence was not necessarily dissatisfying, when present, they could be a motivational force (Herzberg et al., 1959; Herzberg, 1966).

Extrinsic Job Satisfaction Factors: The hygiene factors are supervision, working conditions, co-workers, pay, policies and procedures, job security, status, and personal life (Herzberg et al., 1959; Herzberg, 1966). They are not necessarily satisfying, but their absence could cause dissatisfaction.

Figure 1: Job Satisfaction & Employee Retention Model

Source: Author's creation

Job Satisfaction & Employee Retention Model

The above model apparently depicts a positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee retention. If these extrinsic and intrinsic job satisfaction factors exist in the organization then the propensity to quit the job decreases. Thus these factors also contribute to lower turnover rate and thereby increasing the retention of existing employees in the organization. According to Lee and Mowday (1987) and Tett & Meyer (1993) high job satisfaction leads to lower turnover, while low satisfaction leads to higher turnover. Harrington et al. (2001) observed the various predictors of intentions to leave a job and explored that emotional exhaustion; lower levels of intrinsic job satisfaction and dissatisfaction with salary and promotional opportunities were the main predictors. According to Randhawa (2007), a significant correlation between job satisfaction and turnover intentions exists and suggested that higher the job satisfaction, lower is the individual's intention to quit the job.

Objectives

1. To analyze the effect of level of job satisfaction among hotel employees on employee retention.
2. To examine the extrinsic and intrinsic factors of job satisfaction responsible for employee retention in hotels.
3. To suggest the need of job satisfaction for employee retention in hotels.

Review of Literature

Job Satisfaction: In an organization's success job satisfaction plays a crucial role. According to Osteraker (1999), the employee satisfaction and retention are the key factors for the success of an organization. George & Jones (2002) study elucidates that the level of job satisfaction in the work place is a factor that induce absenteeism which in turn leads to employee turnover and thereby influencing the employees to quit their jobs. Various researchers agree that the lack of job satisfaction among employees leads to high turnover intention, absenteeism and low organizational commitment. According to Alexander Lichtenstein & Hellman (1998) employee job satisfaction is a good predictor of retention of a highly skilled and experienced labor force in an organization. Hoppock defined job satisfaction as any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause a person truthfully, satisfied with his/her job (Hoppock, 1935). This definition of job satisfaction represents that

there are some factors both extrinsic & intrinsic that trigger the feeling of satisfaction. Carmeli (1991) & O'Reilly (2005) study suggested that the job satisfaction variable is negatively related to voluntary turnover intentions. According to Clarke (2001), Parker and Wright (2001) organization should utilize an extensive range of human resource management factors to influence employee commitment and retention. Locke (1976) identified job satisfaction as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experience.

Employee Retention: According to Bogdanowicz & Bailey (2002), retention activities are a sum of all those activities focused on increasing organizational commitment of employees, giving them an overall ambition and numerous opportunities where they can grow by outperforming others. In the words of Samuel & Chipunza (2009), the main purpose of retention is to prevent the loss of competent employees from the organization as this could have an adverse effect on productivity and service delivery. Keeping in mind the managerial implications, the retention of competent employees is more important than it was before. A number of factors such as globalization, competition, survival of the fittest organization, technological advancement, etc. make it important for an organization to retain competent and talented workforce. Thus, according to Lockwood (2006), retention is a critical element of an organization's approach to talent management.

Research Methodology

Data has been collected through primary and secondary sources. For the purpose of this study the Short form of the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire has been used as a primary source while published research papers, newspaper articles and information available on World Wide Web served as a source of secondary data. The population of the study comprised of employees working in the 4 operational areas (Front Office, Housekeeping, Food & Beverage and Food Production) of the hotels in the Bundelkhand region. The sample size of the study is 100 hotel employees who are selected through convenient sampling in the Bundelkhand region of Uttar Pradesh. The questionnaires were distributed through the drop-off and pick-up method with the help of the hotel executives. Respondents were given 1 week duration to fill up the questionnaire. A total of 83 responses were collected from 5 different hotels in the region. Respondents were asked to be realistic about the questionnaire and were assured for non-disclosure of the information and information acquired will be used for academic purpose only. Out of the total respondents 6% were female employees and 94% were male employees.

All the respondents were judged on the basis of 5 points Likert Scale ranging from 1 = not satisfied and 5 = extremely satisfied. The job satisfaction was judged using the Short form of the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into 2 sections. The 1st section comprised of the 20 questions from the Short form of the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale. The 2nd section comprised of the respondents demographic information such as age, gender, marital status, tenure, education and work department.

Limitations

Due to time and resource constraints, the geographical area is restricted to Bundelkhand region of Uttar Pradesh. Some of the hotel employees were found to be reluctant in providing information.

Data Analysis & Results

Table 1 depicts the section II of the questionnaire about the demographic profile of the respondents. From the table it is clear that out of the total respondents' i.e. 83, male respondents are 94% & female respondents are 6%. The respondents according to age category are as follows: 16-20 years 14.45% respondents which is the lowest category, 21-25 years which depicts the highest number 33.7% respondents, 26-30 years 27.7% respondents and 31 years and above 24.09% respondents. 44.57% respondents were married while 55.42% respondents were unmarried. Education status of respondents was – Matriculation/ Intermediate 37.34% respondents, diploma holders are highest i.e. 54.21% respondents and 8.43% respondents were degree holders which are the least. The job tenure of the respondents in the hotel- Less than 1 year was 61.44% respondents which are the highest while 1-5 years were 31.32% respondents and more than 5 years were only 7.22% which is the least. According to the

work departments, respondents from front office were 14.45% which depicts the lowest category while the highest category of respondents was from food & beverage department 31.32%.

Table 1: Respondent's profile on the basis of demographic factors

Demographic Factor	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	16-20 years	12	14.45
	21-25 years	28	33.7
	26-30 years	23	27.7
	31 years and above	20	24.09
Gender	Male	78	93.97
	Female	5	6.024
Marital Status	Married	37	44.57
	Single	46	55.42
Education	Matriculation/Intermediate	31	37.34
	Diploma	45	54.21
	Degree	7	8.433
Job Tenure	Less than 1 year	51	61.44
	1-5 years	26	31.32
	More than 5 years	6	7.228
Work Department	Front office	12	14.45
	Housekeeping	23	27.71
	Food & Beverage	26	31.32
	Food Production	22	26.5

Table 2: Minnesota Questionnaire

Variables (Short form of the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire)	Mean
Being able to keep busy all the time	3.87
The chance to work alone on the job	2.65
The chance to do different things from time to time	2.49
The chance to be "somebody" in the community	2.64
The way my boss handles his/her workers	3.07
The competence of my supervisor in making decisions	2.93
Being able to do things that don't go against my conscience	2.81
The way my job provides for steady employment	2.55
The chance to do things for other people	3.17
The chance to tell people what to do	2.66
The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities	3.12
The way company policies are put into practice	2.88
My pay and the amount of work I do	2.25
The chances for advancement on this job	2.55
The freedom to use my own judgment	2.52
The chance to try my own methods of doing the job	2.52
The working conditions	2.82
The way my co-workers get along with each other	2.96
The praise I get for doing a good job	3.11
The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job	2.88

Table 3: Response rate of various respondents on the various job satisfaction factors responsible for employee retention

Job satisfaction variables	Extremely Satisfied (5)	Very Satisfied (4)	Satisfied (3)	Somewhat Satisfied (2)	Not Satisfied (1)	Total Respondents
Job Security	10	14	17	13	29	83
Reward & Recognition	21	14	18	13	17	83
Responsibility	12	14	17	13	27	83
Advancement & Growth	8	14	18	19	24	83
Compensation	6	11	14	19	33	83
Working Conditions	12	13	22	20	16	83

Table 4: Job satisfaction variables and mean

Job satisfaction variables	Number of items	Mean	Mean Ranking
Job Security	6	2.55	4
Reward & Recognition	6	3.11	1
Responsibility	6	2.65	3
Advancement & Growth	6	2.55	4
Compensation	6	2.25	5
Working Conditions	6	2.82	2

Table 5: Job satisfaction factors leading to employee retention

Factor	Description
Job security	This factor involves assurance of job continuity in a particular organization which leads to retention of employee.
Reward & recognition	This is a positive factor which involves appreciation of employee's performance to cater job satisfaction needs.
Responsibility	This factor deals with obligation to complete a task allotted to an employee. This helps in building cordial superior-subordinate relationship and trust among them which thereby leads to job satisfaction.
Advancement & growth	This factor involves career development of employees to enhance employee retention.
Compensation	This factor involves giving salary and remuneration to individuals on the basis of type of work to cater job satisfaction needs.
Working conditions	This factor involves the conditions in which an individual works in an organization. It comprises creating a favorable work environment to cater job satisfaction needs.

The summated means for the six job satisfaction variables responsible for employee retention indicate average score that lie between extremely satisfied and not satisfied on the Likert scale for all six factors. Reward and recognition (mean = 3.11) was ranked highest, followed by working conditions (mean = 2.82), Responsibility (mean = 2.65), Job security (mean = 2.55), Advancement & growth (mean = 2.55) with Compensation (mean = 2.25) ranked lowest in the list. These findings denote that amongst these six factors, *Compensation* had the greatest impact on employee retention with *Reward & recognition* exerting the least impact.

Job satisfaction and employee retention relationship analysis

In order to establish the relationship between job satisfaction variables Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) is used for data calculation. To test the impact of one variable on another variable Pearson Correlation is used in the study. The result from Pearson correlation test could yield three values ranging from -1 (Highly negative correlation) to +1 (Highly positive correlation) and 0 depicts no correlation.

An analysis of the relationship reveals that there were strong positive relations between employee retention and all six job satisfaction factors. In terms of inter-factor relationship, it is interesting to note that there were strong positive relations among all six job satisfaction factors. As such, an increase in any one factor can trigger increases in any of the other job satisfaction factors. Conversely, any decrease in any job satisfaction factor may stimulate a decrease in any of the other factors as well. According to a study conducted by Samuel et al.,(2012) greater the job satisfaction less likely is the turnover intention, thus confirming previous literature that a person with a high level of job satisfaction holds positive attitude toward the job and conversely the person who is dissatisfied with the job holds negative attitude about the job. It means that employees who are satisfied on their job will retain their jobs and not quit.

Summary of Findings

According to Martin (2007), "Job satisfaction is seen to be the stronger predictor of turnover intention." According to Loveday (1996), "There is a close relationship between employee satisfaction and employee turnover. If the employees morale decrease and there is insecurity in a job, employees are likely to leave the organization and seek alternative employment."

In reviewing the findings of the study, the following observations were evident. Firstly, job satisfaction was encapsulated through six factors, namely job security, working conditions, responsibility,

compensation, advancement & growth and reward & recognition. The impact of job satisfaction on employee retention was established through mean score ranking technique. The findings of the study suggest that there is an association with the level of job satisfaction and employee retention. High level of job satisfaction leads to high employee retention. The more the employee is satisfied with his/her job the more he wants to stay in the organization. The findings of the study suggest that reward & recognition had the least impact on employee retention followed by working conditions, responsibility, job security, advancement & growth with compensation exerting the greatest impact. This also denotes that both extrinsic & intrinsic factors of job satisfaction have an impact on the employee intentions to quit the job. Thus the findings of the study are in line with the previous studies conducted on job satisfaction factors related to employee retention. According to a study conducted by Sangaran & Jeetesh (2015) of hotel employees in Kuala Lumpur City Center salaries are one of the main factors that would influence the decision for turnover. According to Issa et al., (2013) study pay satisfaction was the dominant dimension in turnover intentions. According to a study conducted by Chakravorty & Lakhawat (2016) on hotel employees in India it was found that better salary is the most important reason for job-switch.

Managerial Implications

Employee retention may be accelerated by positively adjusting the levels of job satisfaction factors such as job security, working conditions, responsibility, compensation, advancement & growth and reward & recognition, which are predictors of employee intentions to quit the job. Management practitioners would be able to address employee retention problems by checking to see if there are any pitfalls within any of the six job satisfaction factors used in the study.

Conclusion

The purpose of the study was to establish a relationship between job satisfaction and employee retention in hospitality industry. The study employed a quantitative design in which a survey questionnaire was administered to employees of five different hotels in the Bundelkhand region of Uttar Pradesh state. Using a combination of summated mean scores, positive and significant relationships were observed between employee retention and six job satisfaction factors namely, job security, working conditions, responsibility, compensation, advancement & growth and reward & recognition. These results suggest that the increment in employee retention may be achieved by increasing each of the six job satisfaction factors. Using, the findings of the study, managers in hotel industry may be able to improve employee retention by optimizing job satisfaction along the dimensions proposed in this study.

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Border Tourism as a Tool to Bring Peace for Border Residents: A Case of Suchetgarh Border of Jammu

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Abstract

Many peace processes have been undertaken by both government and private agencies to combat with the issues of conflicts and disturbances in the state of Jammu and Kashmir. But lasting peace is yet in offing. The borders of Jammu and Kashmir are very sensitive and even at the times of peace guns have never fallen down on the borders with Pakistan. There is an urgent need for effective border related peace initiatives which should have a lasting positive impact on the borders benefitting the communities living on the borders. Border tourism can be one of the best alternatives through which lasting positive peace can be attained. Border tourism can be an effective means to bring peace both economically and socially for the people of border areas. Moreover, the touristic interactions between the locals and the tourists can be helpful for positive intercultural encounters i.e. respect for each other's culture, traditions and heritage. In J&K, there are at present open borders for the purpose of trade and movement of people for meeting relatives, if any. There is however no border for promoting border tourism. Suchetgarh Border in the state of Jammu and Kashmir falls in R S Pura Tehsil of Jammu district has good potential to be developed for border tourism. The border is 11 kms away from Sialkot in Pakistan. The Suchetgarh border can be built on the lines of Wagah border in Amritsar, Punjab. Historically there are places of religious importance that can also attract people. The research paper takes into consideration the case of Suchetgarh border to explore the potential of border tourism in Suchetgarh. The study also focuses on finding the determinants that ensure peace probabilities due to the border tourism. The study is qualitative in nature based on descriptive and exploratory research design. The research findings help to develop framework for border tourism.

Keywords: *Tourism, Border, Peace, Social and Interaction.*

Introduction

Rattling of guns on the borders of Jammu and Kashmir seems to be never being replaced by the exciting voices of the tourists chanting "Bharat Mata ki Jai" as in the case of Wagah Border. The borders of Jammu and Kashmir are very sensitive due to the hostility between India and Pakistan. The false propaganda by Pakistan against India is being continuously abetted. There is no mutual trust from either sides or the peace processes undertaken so far by both the countries have so far impacted positively in creating lasting peace. People of Jammu and Kashmir had not only faced atrocities during and after partition of India and Pakistan but now even after so many years the people living along the borders suffer alot due to the regular cease fire violations. The loss of life, property, the displacement to safer places away from homes interrupts the normal and peaceful functioning of life. The opportunities for a better future stand to halt both for the youth and for the economic development of the region. It is not that initiatives have not been taken by the governments for peace. There are few initiatives like cross-border trade as part of Confidence Building Measures (CBM) by both the governments to ease tensions and bring peace, specifically for the border areas connecting Jammu and Kashmir with Pakistan. The Line of Control (LoC) was softened partially with the opening of cross-LoC bus services between Srinagar-Muzaffarabad and Poonch-Rawalakote routes for meeting relatives and trade purposes (Chandran, 2009). There are recommendations for opening of more routes like the Jammu-Sialkot, Kargil-Skardu, Chahamb-Jorian to Mirpur, Turtuk-Khapulu, Jhangar (Nowshera) – Mirpur and Kotli, etc for travel as well as for trade (Padder, 2014). However, these initiatives have not been so successful in improving the bilateral ties between the two countries. The border areas due to their peripheral geographical location are mostly underdeveloped in terms of infrastructure, transportation, education, etc. There are less job opportunities and people of border areas migrate to the closest urban areas in search of a better future. These all setbacks interrupt the inner peace of the people living in border areas. In such scenario, tourism industry can be a better instrument to deal with these challenges (Agnese, Peroni and Perelli, 2010). According to

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the International Institute of Peace Through Tourism (IIPT), tourism has the capacity to bring peace by contributing to cooperation, mutual understanding, heritage preservation and quality environment. 'Peace through Tourism refers to the reduction and hopeful elimination of conditions that lead to violence' (Jimenez and Kloeze, 2014; Kelly, 2006). Since tourism inherently involves the movement of people from one place to other inducing interactions, these interactions between hosts and guests bring exchange of opinions, ideas, thoughts, knowledge, and respect for each other's traditions and culture. These characteristics of tourism can help on borders in eliminating structural violence and spread positive peace for the people of border areas (Moufakkir and Kelly, 2014; Neupane, 2013; Wohlmuther and Wintersteiner, 2013).

Figure 1: The Concept of Peace and Violence

Source: Johan Galtung, (1969).

The above figure shows that violence and peace may be of two types, negative and positive. This concept was given by Johan Galtung in 1969. A common understanding of violence is mostly about direct violence that is related to injury, riot, terrorism, etc. However, violence means indirect violence too. Indirect violence may include lack of jobs, social inequality, human rights exploitation, political inequality, personal biasness, hunger, poverty, diseases etc. The indirect violence is referred as the structural violence. Alike violence, the word 'peace' has different meanings to different people. It may be freedom from war, calmness of mind, freedom from social injustice, freedom from gender biasness, freedom from human rights violation, freedom from political instability, security of human life, harmony in human relations, etc. As per Galtung (1969), peace can be either negative peace or positive peace. Negative peace' implies absence of war or direct violence whereas 'positive peace' implies the absence of indirect violence or structural violence. This study is about positive peace that emphasizes tourism as a tool for bringing positive peace and for eliminating structural violence for the people living in the border area of Suchetgarh border in Jammu.

Border Tourism is the movement of people towards country's border. 'Border tourism is the temporary displacement of people to the dividing line between two countries contiguous areas (Rio, et al., 2017). Border tourism can help in strengthening the border regions by enhancing quality of life of border people, preservation of heritage and culture of border areas, better opportunities for education, employment generation, etc. Suchetgarh border which falls in R S Pura Tehsil of Jammu district has good potential to be developed for border tourism. The border is 11 kms away from Sialkot in Pakistan and 27 kms away from Jammu. Prior to 1947, there was a rail link connecting Suchetgarh to Sialkot and Suchetgarh used to be a railway station. During the British period, the main train link between Delhi to Jammu went through Sialkot and Lahore. Here, there are places of historical importance that can also attract people There is a banyan tree known to be 100 years old which functions as a border pillar that is half on the Indian side and half on the Pakistani side. The present BSF office is at place where there was once the old railway station. There are bullet marks on the wall facing the border, the last bullet marks are from the time of Kargil war in 1999. There is an old Hindu temple known to be the original Raghunath temple which was later shifted to Jammu. There is also a Muslim shrine of 'Baba Neeli Tali Walla'. The Suchetgarh border

can be developed and promoted for border tourism as on the lines of Wagah border in Amritsar, Punjab. Near Suchetgarh border, the other peripheral potential touristic place is Gharana Wetland where migratory birds come in large numbers during the winter season. The world famous Basmati rice belt is also found here in R.S Pura sector.

Review of Literature

Agnese, Peroni & Perelli (2010) examine the role of European Union in the promotion of tourism in border areas through cross-border cooperation measures, taking a case of Lapland district. It discusses the role of tourism in border areas and the steps taken by the union to develop sustainable tourism in Lapland area. The results of the study show that the European Union has made many efforts by establishing many cross-cooperation programmes that has helped to develop sustainable tourism in border areas i.e. increase in the number of tourists and development of the tourism in the destination.

Chowdhary (2012) elaborates the life of the people living in the borders of Jammu particularly Arnia sector of Jammu. The paper highlights the problems faced by them due to hostility between India and Pakistan and their stories before and after partition. The results of the study show that people have suffered a lot during and after the partition and there are government related issues concerning safety of their lives and lands. Despite problems and hostility between both the countries, people still have empathy for the people on other side of the border due to the same cultural background.

Del Rio, Aguera, Cuadra and Morales (2017) analyse the visitors visiting Dominican Republic and Haiti border. The study is empirically conducted which shows the correlations between the attitude factor towards border tourism, value factors perceived by the tourist, loyalty and satisfaction of the visitors for the destination. The results highlighted the relationship, influence and positive and direct impact of the visitor's attitude, knowledge, perceived value, loyalty and satisfaction towards Dominican Republic and Haiti border destination. Grewal (2003) discusses the difference between positive and negative peace and different types of violence cultural and structural violence given by Johan Galtung.

Askjellerud (2003) discusses if a tourist is a messenger for peace or not. It enlists various arguments in favour and against the motion and at last it comes to the conclusion that a tourist is a messenger of peace in a destination he/she visits and there is peace through tourism. Shin (2008) highlights the connection between peace and tourism. The paper argues on the reality that tourism is not necessarily a force for peace and may not lead to improvement of relations between divided nations. D'Amore (2014) emphasizes on the development of the peace through tourism concept. He has listed a series of events of the emergence of the peace through tourism concept in detail.

Research Gap: No prior descriptive and exploratory study has been done on border tourism in Suchetgarh border.

Research Question: What are the potentials of border tourism in Suchetgarh border area of R.S Pura Sector of Jammu from the perspective of locals?

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the potential of border tourism in Suchetgarh border.
2. To find the determinants that ensures positive peace probabilities for the dwellers of border areas due to the border tourism.
3. To investigate the perception of the respondents for the development and promotion of border tourism in the Suchetgarh border.

Research Methodology

Qualitative research approach is concerned with the opinions, experiences and feeling of individuals producing subjective data. It describes social phenomenon as it unfolds naturally. No attempt is made to manipulate the situation under study as is the case with experimental quantitative research. This study aims to get insights of the respondents' opinions and thoughts towards the potential development of border tourism in Suchetgarh border and to find out whether border tourism ensures positive peace probabilities for the dwellers of border areas or not? The research approach of this study is exploratory in

nature. The study is exploratory in nature when a problem has small amount of information and no research work has already been done on it (Bricki and Green, 2007 & Hancock, 1998).

Interviews are an effective way to collect data from individuals on their personal histories, experiences, perspectives especially when the topic being explored is very sensitive (Berg, 2004; Thomas, 2010). The study attempts to get detailed information about respondent's views and perceptions about border tourism in Suchetgarh border and how it can help in bringing peace in the life of border residents. For the interviews, semi-structured questionnaire was prepared and the local residents of the Suchetgarh village were chosen as respondents depending on the criteria of being native of the place for more than fifty years. Saturation sampling has been used in this study for determining the sample size. In saturation sampling, in the course of data collection process, when a point is reached where a researcher feels that no new information is obtained from new respondents then the sampling process is stopped up to the current sample size. In this study, twelve interviews were conducted, as the saturation point was reached up to the sample size of twelve.

Findings of the Study

Thematic Analysis and Coding – In this study one interview was videotaped and eleven were audio taped. Later the interviews were transcript and systematically analyzed using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis categorizes the verbal and behavioral data for summarization, classification and tabulation. Thematic analysis involves coding of data, which is basically an analysis technique used in this study to derive results which are in the form of themes and the main aim is making sense out of the data collected. Thematic analysis is a process of "encoding qualitative information" (Boyatzis, 1998). The study undertakes it manual coding process with the purpose to create sense out of the data collected. The manual process of coding involves three steps namely open codes, axial codes and selective codes, which give results of the study. In open codes, the interview transcripts are analyzed where interactions, actions or events are compared with others for similarities and differences. And then the similar ones are grouped together as open codes which are normally the actual phrases or words of the respondents. The open coding further leads to axial codes where the researcher re-groups the data, generating sub-categories having an interpretive value for the common pattern found in open codes. The sub categories which emerge from the axial codes are correlated to give a meaningful understanding in the form of final themes. The themes so found are called as selective codes. Following this process, three themes were derived by the researcher also called as selective codes which depict the results of the study (Boyatzis, 1998; Douglas, 2003; Hancock, 1998; Flick, 2009; Khandkar, 2009; Saldana, 2015; Strauss and Corbin, 1990). (Refer Table 1)

Theme 1: Government's Apathy: This theme contains six sub categories namely, non- fulfillment of promises; poor infrastructure development; poor promotion or marketing; poor fund management; no community involvement; and unfulfilled basic needs. These sub categories clearly point out to the government's casual attitude towards the people and least concern about the development of the Suchetgarh border and adjoining villages. The locals are unhappy and highly dissatisfied with the role of government in their areas. They said that no help whether monetary or non-monetary, is being given to them by the government during and after firing. Promises are made but are never fulfilled whether in respect to rescuing them during firing to getting jobs to the injured and compensation for losses. Like one of the respondents stated, *"People arrange by their own, there is no help from the government. Once the firing stops, the ministers just visit for formality. Appropriate compensation should be given for losses. Jobs should be given to people who have lost their family members. Handicapped people should be given jobs or pension, like a boy here, he was a carpenter but he had lost his leg during firing."* The other respondent says, *"There are all fake promises of the government during firing but once firing is finished, everything goes in vain, no one asks us."*

They told that many years have passed but roads have not been constructed and there has been no development in the villages. A respondent said, *"Many promises are made by the government and they had decided and promised us to make road. The roads are in very bad condition, the road is broken. It is said that Suchetgarh border will be a big spot for tourism, the CM has also visited here three times and our Tourism Minister of Jammu and Kashmir has visited here eight times. See the condition of the roads;*

tourists who come here face problems due to poor accessibility. There is no repairing of the roads.” “Even the basic necessities like water and electricity are not in place.” A respondent told, “There is well here but it is so dirty that we cannot use water from there, the well is not covered and there is a lot of risk to life of small children. The street lights do not work properly and no connection is given to the transformer which was set up years back by the tourism department”.

Table 1: Thematic Analysis and Coding

OPEN CODES (Generated from Data)	AXIAL CODES (Sub-Categories)	SELECTIVE CODES (Themes/Categories)
Fake promises by government	Non- Fulfillment of Promises	Government's Apathy
No compensation for losses		
No jobs for injured during firing		
No help during firing		
Roads are broken	Poor Infrastructure Development	
No development of Suchetgarh Border		
No development of adjoining areas		
No efforts for promotions	Poor Promotion/Marketing	
Conducts Baishakhi Mela once in a year	Poor Fund Management	
Allotted funds not utilised in properly		
Uneven Development	No Community Involvement	
No one to one interactions		
Do not involve villagers and Sarpanch into planning and decision-making		
No cleanliness	Unfulfilled Basic Needs	
Water shortage		
Electricity shortage		
Education suffers during firing	Education Apprehensions	Career Consciousness
Unable to get good education		
Children's future is in danger	Career Building	
Quota for jobs of border youth		
Urge from both sides to meet and interact	Positivity for Neighbour Country	Positive Disposition of Local Community for Tourism
No negative feelings for people of Pakistan		
Border should open for trade	Positivity for Tourism	
Lot of potential to attract tourists		
Promotion and maintenance of spot		
Peace talks between countries		
Pakistan should support for opening border		
Create employment		
Economic Development		
Development of villages		
Benefits to both sides of the border		
Interactions among tourists and guests		
Love and Peace		

The researcher observed lack of maintenance of the present infrastructure by the tourism department and lack of cleanliness on the spot. One respondent said, “There are no garbage bins here and nobody has ever made efforts to look into this matter. We cannot say that it is the fault of tourists, obviously when they will not find any bin to put waste; they will obviously throw them here and there only. What is the purpose of the ‘Swachh Bharat Abhiyaan’ by the government, when the government has not even taken care of cleanliness? You must have seen here that there is no cleanliness on the spot and no proper place to sit. The temple inside the spot is not maintained properly, the tourism department had spent money on it but then it came under Dharmarth trust. We were told that the tourism department will take over it again and maintain it but now many years have passed, nothing has been done. The Peer Baba is also in same condition as the temple.”

There are less promotional efforts by the tourism department and if something is conducted by the tourism department in the area, the promotion of the event is not done properly. For instance, a respondent said, “tourism department conducts one day Baishakhi Mela once in a year, leaving that aside no efforts are done by the government for the promotion of this spot.” Another respondent told, “There are no proper promotions, I think while coming from Jammu Airport till here, there is only on e flex of this

spot put up by JKTDC. Only taxi drivers know this spot and they bring the tourists here but mostly people do not know about this spot. 3Kms away from here is Gharana Wetland where migratory birds come where you should also visit”.

The local people were also angry of the fact that they are not included in the planning and decision making processes by the government and this is the reason why there is uneven development of the spot and adjoining areas. A respondent said, *“Tell me how will tourism flourish here, the government allots so much money but when the roads are not constructed how tourists will come. They are not utilising money in a proper way. They should take into consideration the people of the village and the Sarpanch of the village to have interactions so as to deliberate on how and where the money should be spent for the development of the villages. This way money can be utilised in a proper manner.”*

Theme 2: Career Consciousness: The two sub categories, education apprehensions; and career building, clearly point out to the worries of the youth towards their education or the worries of the people towards the education of their children living in the border area. Education is in the constant state of fluctuation due to the disturbances caused by unprovoked firing by Pakistan. The border people said that their education suffers a lot during disturbances as the schools are closed for months together. Completing their education schedule on time is a real challenge. Moreover, the disturbance in border areas do not help prepare youth in availing the opportunities with respect to their careers as compared to the youth studying in cities. And this is the reason why their quality of life remains low and in the end they have to settle down for working in the fields like their parents and therefore lead a life full of struggles for money and status. They also suggested that there should be a prescribed quota system by the government for jobs to the youth of the border areas; and for border people, the qualification requirement should be reduced to some extent in various recruitments by army, BSF or police. For example, one of the respondents said, *“here the children are unable to get good education and are even unable to complete their education due to disturbances; in this case there should be a quota for under metrics (8th class pass instead of 10th or 12th class pass) for them in BSF and army recruitments. The youth of urban areas take this opportunity as they are well educated than our village children. Our children can only do job in BSF, Army or JKP (Jammu and Kashmir Police), there should be special quotas for children of border belt areas specially in the case of JKP recruitment.”*

Theme 3: Positive Disposition of Local Community for Tourism: The theme depicts positivity of the local community or villagers for tourism as they consider tourism to be a great beneficiary for the development of the border area and as a means to bring peace in Jammu and Kashmir. This theme is made up of two sub categories, the first sub category namely, positivity for neighbour country; shows that the people of border areas have no bitterness for the people living on the other side of the border (Pakistan). They said that people on the other side of the border are also farmers like them and they want to visit and interact with them and they think that the people of Pakistan also have same feelings for them. A respondent said, *“When tourists from Pakistan come on their border, we feel like talking to them, the feeling is mutual and there is an urge on both the sides to interact.”* Another respondent says, *“Yes, they are farmers like us. It is not like that they live in Pakistan so that’s why they are wrong.”*

Whereas the second sub category, namely, positivity for tourism; implies that people had a strong desire and concerns that Suchetgarh border should be open for tourism on the lines of Wagah Border in Amritsar, Punjab. They said that this spot can attract tourists in large numbers if it is promoted as border tourism, as it shall facilitate economic and social development of their villages and will add to the economy of the state and there shall be a positive cultural exchange between tourists and hosts in the form of interactions. A respondent told, *“We want that border should be open for tourism and there should be Parade like Wagah Border so that we people can gain something out of it and show our culture. If the spot is maintained well for tourism, the villages will also develop.”* The other respondent said, *“If the infrastructure is developed here properly, there is lot of potential for tourism at this spot. We village people can earn money and earn our livelihood.”*

Another respondent said, *“With tourism there should be events and different tourist activities so that tourists are attracted to the spot. We should be able to portray our Dogra culture. Through tourism there*

will be overall development; and at least the domestic tourists can come and it will add to the economy of the place". The respondents were of the opinion that there should be discussions with Pakistan in the form of peace talks to open border for tourism on the lines of Wagah border, so that both countries mutually agree to put a halt to cease fire violation. Through mutual initiative, the environment can be peaceful for both the counties on this border as in the case of Wagah Border.

A respondent told, "Whenever there is firing, we people who are farmers have to bear the losses. Like few days ago there was firing due to which the people could not get labour for their fields and the effect is that wages of labour gets increased. I think there should be peace talks between both the countries so that there should be no firing, because on the other side of the border (Pakistani side) are also farmer. So the loss is on both sides. The army people get their salary but what about us, we people are farmers we earn by harvesting on our lands, if there will be peace talks we all can benefit in every aspect. The loss is only to local people living on borders."

Another respondent said, "Jammu and Kashmir Tourism Department Corporation (JKTDC) is developing this spot, you can see a building under construction and funds are being allocated for its development. Pakistan should also be ready to open their border for tourism. This place has a lot of potential with respect to tourism. If there is mutual support, this spot can become a big tourism attraction."

Discussion and Conclusion

The results of the study show us that tourism can bring positive peace for the residents of border areas, as the theme; 'Positive Disposition of Local Community for Tourism' depicts that the local people keep lot of hopes from tourism. They are of opinion that Suchetgarh border should be opened for tourism on the lines of Wagah border. They strongly believe that tourism can be a source of employment, development of villages, preservation and maintenance of the heritage, enhanced quality of life, positive cultural exchange between tourists and hosts as well as a source for overall peace and prosperity in the border area. In brief, these feelings of the residents show that the locals have a positive outlook for tourism.

Figure 2: Concept of Border Tourism to bring Positive Peace

Source: Author's Conceptualisation

The study came up with many factors that were responsible for the underdevelopment of the Suchetgarh border. The respondents came up with various problems they had with the government's casual behavior towards the development of their border area of Suchetgarh. They said that there is non- fulfilment of promises made by the government. There is no infrastructure development e.g., roads are not in good condition, no maintenance of the heritage, shortage of water and electricity, no cleanliness, etc. No efforts are made for the promotion of the spot as there is lack of effective marketing strategies, and there is lack of planning for the right utilisation of the allotted funds by the tourism department. They were even angry

that there is no community involvement by the government into the planning and development of their areas as no suggestions are taken from them during execution of any development plans for Suchetgarh border and the adjoining villages. They were very sad of the fact that the education of their children suffers a lot during disturbances and they are unable to grab good opportunities for a better future as compared to the youth of the urban areas. They even suggested that there should be a quota for the youth of border areas so that they could get jobs and not end up working in fields like their parents and living a poor life. So, the government's lack of concern is one of the main setbacks for the underdevelopment of the people and the area. Looking at the broader picture, from the perspective of the locals, the study reveals that border tourism ensures positive peace probabilities for the residents because they think that border tourism can be a catalyst to the overall development and therefore for positive peace.

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A Study on the Consumers' Preferences and Spending Pattern Towards Fast Food Restaurants - With Reference to Haldwani City

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Abstract

The Restaurant industry in India has witnessed tremendous growth over few years in which Fast Food Industry has played a major role. Globalization, increase in disposable income, rise in number of nuclear families, exposure to western cuisine and increase in the number of people working in multinational companies in metro cities living far from their families has resulted in the tendency to eating out thus increase in the growth of fast food industries in India. The paper aims to analyze the various factors affecting the choice of fast food by the consumers. The paper also tries to analyze the consumers' preferences and spending patterns towards fast food menu. The study applies various statistical tools such as percentage and factors analysis, for the same primary data was collected with the help of structured questionnaire through field visits whereas, secondary data was gathered by various research journals and food and beverage magazines. The study reveals that taste, hygiene, ambience and affordability are the major factors which influence the consumers' preferences towards fast food.

Keywords: *Restaurant, Fast food, Globalization, Cuisine, Preferences*

Introduction

Fast food refers to the processed food with general emphasis on speed, uniformity and low cost along with focus on certain flavors and consistency by the addition of some specified ingredients which are typically high in fat, sugar, salt and calories. Bender and Bender (1995) mentioned fast food has a limited menu of food that lend themselves to production-line techniques; suppliers tend to specialize in products such as burgers, hamburgers, pizzas, wraps, fried chicken, sandwiches and more. These foods are generally high in protein, fats and calories but less in vitamins, fiber and minerals. Fast food outlets offering various fast foods have minimal table service and focus more on self-service or take out operations and try to lure the customers with the help of their tangy foods, low price menu and an eye appealing ambience.

The Food and beverage service in India has seen the tremendous growth and is still expanding rapidly. This can be due to globalization, increase in disposable income, rise in number of nuclear families, exposure to western cuisine, increase in the number of people working in multinational companies in metro cities living far from their families and changing demographic profiles. As per the Grant Thornton analysis by FICCI (2015), the F&B service market was worth 2,47,680 crore and is expected to reach INR 4,08,040 crore by the year 2018. Within the restaurant industry the fast food industry constitutes 45% of the overall market and is a key segment. Besides the metro cities, the fast food industry has flourished in the smaller cities, as well as numerous fast food brands have come up with a varieties of cuisines and take away and is projected to increase with a rate of 16%.

Both International and national brands can be seen in smaller cities apart from metro cities offering both vegetarian and non-vegetarian menu however, local standalone fast food outlets are the major ones which influence the customers with their taste, localization, preferences and uniqueness. The market of fast food industry is projected to grow at a rate of 16% annually from INR 92,018 crore in the year 2013 to INR 198,284 crore in the year 2017. As per the findings of the survey conducted by Grant Thornton in collaboration with FICCI (2015), it shows that 63% of Indian fast food industry is captured by foreign fast food brands and 37% is captured by Indian fast food brands. In the modern India, fast food has become a part of life style and is accepted by every youth and new generations in one form or another as the presence of fast food can be found in office complexes, malls, super markets, streets, railway station, roadways station, airports, highways and hospitals.

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Objectives of the Study

1. To find out consumer behavior towards fast food outlets with respect to timing of visits, preference of a particular fast food outlet, purpose of visit and factors influencing the visits.
2. To find out the consumer preference and spending pattern towards fast food restaurants in Haldwani city of the state Uttarakhand.

Literature Review

With changing life style and aggressive marketing by fast food outlets, fast food is also becoming popular in small towns; therefore, success of existing fast food outlets and entry of more is inevitable. Consumers patronize fast food to save time, satisfy their hunger, for pleasure and for social interactions. People used to purchase ingredients for cooking food which is hectic and take lots of time; however introduction of fast food has replaced such activity which is time consuming. (Park, C. 2004). Change of consumer behavior and favorable demographics led India to witness a tremendous growth in fast food restaurant industry. The food habits of youngsters are influenced by many factors such as environment at home, educational environment, availability and accessibility to fast food providers, and social environment in their surroundings (Goyal & Singh, 2007). Anand (2011), in a study of determinants impacting consumers' food choice with reference to the fast food consumption in India, explored the impact of demographics and psychographics on young consumers' food choice towards fast food in Delhi, India and the key determinants impacting consumers food choice were found out to be passion for eating out, to socialize, ambience, taste of fast food and convenience for dual-income families in urban India. However, in a separate study on eating out habits of consumers 'search for variety' was a motivator for eating outside the home. The desire for 'convenience' was an important element on many occasions of consumption (Rezende and Avelar, 2012). A study undertaken by Simpson and Dore (2008) to explore the factors that drive and motivate food consumer' preferences in South Africa noted that the improved economic climate made customers frequently dine out of their homes. Erasmus (2008) also agreed that the changes in spending patterns of consumers in the emerging economy demands new restaurant format, food quality and timing which could ultimately satisfy them.

Research Methodology

The study is exploratory in nature and is carried upon the customers visiting various fast food outlets. A set of structured questionnaires were developed having the dimensions: demographics of the respondent such as age, gender, educational qualification and occupation; behavior of visiting fast food outlets such as preferred time for visiting fast food, factors affecting visiting the fast food outlet such as pressure from friends, influenced by nutritional values etc. Data collected was analyzed using factor analysis and some of the results are shown in percentage with the help of bar chart. A random sampling was done from a large number of customers visiting fast food outlets and malls. Mostly youth and adults between the age group of 18 years to 41 years were selected on the line of Erikson (1963, 1968), Theory on Psychosocial Development, for filling questionnaires as these are more prone to eating out and having a modern lifestyle. They were asked to fill the questionnaire (having multiple choice, single response) on the spot after asking few questions from them regarding their lifestyle, eating habits and demographic features so that biasness can be reduced, besides a thorough analysis was also done for the filled in questionnaires to see the consistency of data for the customers who filled the questionnaires when they were with peers.

The study is conducted at Haldwani city in the state of Uttarakhand. Haldwani is one of the major cities of the state and is a hub of many schools, colleges and government offices. It also acts as a gateway to enter the fascinating Kumaun hills. As the city is near to the world famous hill station Nainital and is a nearest railway station to major hill stations of Kumaun, therefore movement of tourists takes place here round the year. From lodging to shopping, the city provides a wide range of options for the tourists, locals and the youth. Due to this many domestic and international fast food chains have marked their presence here. For the study Dominos, Pizza Hut, KFC and Brownies were selected as they are very famous among the locals and youth. Sample size of 230 was thought to be appropriate as the study is exploratory and circulated to the customers outside these four outlets mentioned above and in the only shopping mall Walk Way located here, out of which only 180 questionnaires were returned and 171 were analysed. The response rate was 74.34 % is deemed to be sufficient and representative as Mugenda and Mugenda (1999) stipulated that a response rate of 70% and above is representative.

Table 1-Sample distribution of respondents

Distribution of sample (N=171)		
Gender	Number	Percentage
Male	98	57.30
Female	73	42.69

Analysis and Interpretations

This section presents analysis, findings and discussion of the study in line with objectives. As per the gathered data following are the findings of the study conducted: As mentioned earlier the youth and adults between the age group of 18 years to 41 years were selected on the line of Erikson (1963, 1968), Theory on Psychosocial Development, for filling questionnaires as they are more prone to eat out and have a modern lifestyle.

Table 2- Gender classification of the respondents(N=171)

Age Group	Male	Female	Total
18-23	45	30	75
24-29	34	24	58
30-35	11	15	26
36-41	8	4	12

Table3-Educational background of the respondents(N=171)

Age Group	Graduate	Undergraduate
18-23	50	25
24-29	48	10
30-35	23	3
36-41	09	3

Table 4-Occupation of the respondents (N=171)

Age Group	Student	Private Employee	Govt. Employee	Self Employed	Others	Total
18-23	45	15	6	7	2	75
24-29	03	34	02	13	6	58
30-35	0	09	11	4	2	26
36-41	0	06	3	2	1	12

Consumer behavior with respect to timing of visits, preference of a particular fast food outlet, purpose of visit and factors influencing the visits: As per the frequency distribution shown in table No. 5, it indicates that customers tends to prefer a fast food outlet generally for snacks followed by lunch and dinner in Haldwani and most of the customers visit 1-2 times in a week whereas, only few people visit the fast food outlet rarely. Table No. 6 indicates that Brownies is the most preferred outlet followed by Pizza Hut in the city and KFC is the least preferred fast food outlet. The result shows that 35.67 % respondents preferred Brownies, 26.90% preferred Pizza Hut, 19.29 % preferred Dominos and 18.12 % preferred KFC. Further, based on multiple answer questions it is inferred in the table no. 8 that their preference to visit a particular fast food outlet is influenced by friends in 93 % of cases followed by relatives and other factors.

Table 5 - Frequency distribution of the respondent visit fast food outlets for snacks, lunch and dinner

No. of Times	Snacks		Lunch		Dinner	
	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age
Most of the time	33	19.29	31	18.12	29	16.95
>3 times a week	18	10.52	11	6.43	19	11.11
1-2 times a week	94	54.97	83	48.53	93	54.38
Once a month	17	9.94	39	22.80	24	14.03
Rarely	9	5.26	7	4.09	6	3.50
Total	171	100	171	100	171	100

Table 6 - Frequency distribution of respondents visiting and preferring a particular fast food outlet

Fast food outlet	No. of respondents
Dominos	33
Pizza Hut	46
KFC	31
Brownies	61
Total	171

Table 7-Factors influencing the decision regarding selection of fast food outlets

Individual Influencing decision	Frequency	%age
Spouse	13	7.60
Children	4	2.33
Friends	107	62.57
Relatives	43	25.14
Others	4	2.33
Total	171	100

Consumer's Preference towards Fast Food Restaurants: To analyze the preference towards fast food restaurants by the respondents, factor analysis was used. For the same, ten variables were developed and to identify the most important factors which influence the respondents to prefer the fast food restaurants from large number of variables identified, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed using Varimax Rotation method. Variable having factor loading more than 0.50 has more influence among all the variables, therefore variables with factor loading more than 0.50 were grouped into four composite factors: Affordability and Social Influence, Health and Service Quality, Taste and Location-orientation and Ambience. It is shown in the table 8 that Eigen values of Affordability and Social Influence is 1.557, Health and Service Quality 1.401, Taste and Location-orientation 1.237 and Ambience is 1.158. As the Eigen values of these four factors are more than one, these four factors were considered to be the most important factors influencing the consumer's preferences towards fast food restaurants. These four composite factors constitute 53.52 per cent of the total variance therefore; it is being observed that Affordability and Social Influence was found to be the most important factor which influenced the young consumers to prefer fast food restaurants followed by Health and Service Quality, Taste and Location-orientation and Ambience.

Table 8-An analysis on Consumer's Preference towards Fast Food Restaurant Factor Analysis

Particulars	Factors	Variables	Factor Loading	Eigen Value	% Variance	Cumulative % Variation
Factor 1	Affordability and Social Influence	Price	.596	1.557	15.567	15.567
		Choice in Menu	.561			
		Influence by Friends	.524			
		Delivery Time	.523			
Factor 2	Health and Service Quality	Hygienic condition of fast food outlet	.797	1.401	14.013	29.580
		Service offered	.718			
Factor 3	Taste and Location	Taste	.673	1.237	12.365	41.966
		Location and accessibility	.564			
Factor 4	Ambience	Restaurant environment	.735	1.158	11.575	53.521

Consumption Expenditure on Fast Food

Table no 9 shows the per capita monthly expenditure on fast food by the respondents which is analyzed and mean value is calculated. The results shows that the 71 respondents spend between one thousand to fifteen hundred monthly in fast food restaurants whereas 54 respondents tends to spend 500 - 1000 rupees per month followed by 33 respondents spending 1501- 2000 and 13 respondents spending 2001- 2500. The average expenditure as calculated is Rs. 1264.61. Therefore it can be said that the consumers spend a considerable amount on a monthly basis during their visit to the fast food outlet.

Table 9_Per capita (monthly) expenditure by respondents on fast food outlet

Monthly Expenditure (Rs)	No. Of Respondents (<i>f</i>)	Mid Value (<i>x</i>)	<i>fx</i>
500 – 1000	54	750	40500
1001-1500	71	1250	88750
1501-2000	33	1750	57750
2001-2500	13	2250	29250
N= <i>f</i> =171			<i>fx</i> 216250
Mean = $\frac{fx}{f}$ = Rs 1264.61			

Conclusion

The fast food industry is projected to grow at a rate of 16% annually from the year 2013 to 2017 in the India. Now a days fast food has become a part of life style and is accepted by every youth and new generations in one form or another in metro cities and other towns. Consumers in today's market are fascinated towards western culture and increase in the facilities offered by fast food services driving the growth of the industry. The frequency of visiting the fast food outlets relates with the ages of the consumers as well as the income affects the spending habits of an individual. The present study shows that the customers prefer fast food outlet to consume majorly snacks followed by lunch and dinner. Most of them visit fast food outlets one or two times in a week whereas only few people visit the fast food outlet rarely which indicates that menu should be customized according to the meal of the day and bite size menu items should be included in their menu. The study also shows that the friends are the major factor which influences the individual decision to visit any fast food outlet showing that people have more influence of friends rather than family and relatives and they preferably visit fast outlets along with their friends. Customers give more preference to the affordability of the fast food outlet as the study signifies that Affordability and Social Influence are the most important factors which influenced the young consumers to prefer fast food restaurants followed by Health and Service Quality, Taste & Location-orientation and Ambience which clearly indicates that information about hygiene and nutrition value of the fast food must also be communicated to the consumers.. The study also calculated an average expenditure per month of an individual while visiting fast food outlet to be Rs. 1264.61, this may be due to the increase in disposable income of an individual along with changing life styles and social affluence. The direct benefit for restaurants from more people dining out is in its revenue generation. It only makes sense for them to offer more and better what customers want. If they are already doing so, then they need to keep reinventing so that customers continue their patronage towards Fast food outlets, keeping in mind the average spending power of a customer while designing the price of their menu and this will also help to expand their business in terms of number of outlets. Fast Restaurants who can understand this need of their consumers and cater to their choices will go a long way in satisfying their customers and improve their cash registers.

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An Assessment of the Reliability gap between Online Travel Portals and Travel Agencies with reference to Delhi and NCR

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Abstract

The main aim of this paper is to analyze the reliability gap between online travel portals and travel agencies. Travel bookings and arrangements through online travel portals in India are becoming popular day by day. The conventional means of obtaining airline tickets and related travel arrangements are rapidly changing. These changes have become possible due to attractive offerings by online travel portals and also less expensive and multiple options of getting travel arrangements in budgeted manner. Customers also feel that there is reliability service gap between travel agencies and online travel portals. This study is an attempt to find out the variables where reliability gap was felt. Further the study deals with analysis and interpretation of the data. On basis of research findings, suggestion and conclusion are given.

Keywords: *Online travel portals, Travel agency, Reliability and Consumer behavior.*

Introduction

An advancement of information technology, internet and computer knowledge brings the revolution in travel and tourism industry. This revolution has gained the momentum in India but still the percentage is quite nominal than the developed countries. A lot of people have been encouraged and motivated to use online booking services. It is believed that the goal of every organization is to meet the needs and the requirements of its consumers. Meeting the needs and the requirements of the consumers will not only ensure the survival of the organization but also help them to flourish it. Repeated clients are the key success of any business model. According to World travel and tourism council, India in Travel and Tourism generated INR14.1 trillion (USD208.9 billion) in year 2016, the sum is equivalent to 9.6% of India's GDP. It also supported 40.3 million jobs in 2016. The sector accounts for 9.3% of the country's total jobs in India. India's travel & Tourism sector is also the fastest growing and moving amongst the G20 countries. It has grown by 8.5% in 2016. A further 6.7% growth is forecasted in year 2017 (WTTC, 2017). Success of any service organization depends upon the service quality of the organization. It has become more important to achieve the customer satisfaction and also to relate the feeling and expectations from the services for which the customer is spending the money. To know about expectation and level of satisfaction a reliability study is necessary. "**Reliability** is the ability to be relied on or depended on, as for accuracy, honesty, or achievement or the quality of being trustworthy or of performing consistently well (wikipedia). Different service quality dimensions are mentioned here. These are as follows:

Table 1: RATER Dimensions of Service Quality

Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Empathy	Tangibles
All the promised tasks well performed, Convenient and flexible working hours, Right service at first time, Sincere interest to solve customer problem.	Employees understand the specific needs of the customer, Prompt service, Employees behavior, Employees are willing to help, Employees are courteous with customers	Competent employees, Employees have sufficient knowledge about the service, reputation	Personal attention by employees. Cultivation of friendly relationship, Learning the customers' special needs, Allocating required time to deliver each service	Modern and technologically relevant equipment, Other material elements and documents, Appearance of personnel

Source: Rosha & Kaur (2015)

As this study is focused about Reliability dimension so only reliability variables are studied and evaluated.

Literature Review

The literature review is based on the different studies done on travel agencies and online travel portals. In the first few paragraphs it depicts about travel agencies and online travel portal further it is continuing with emergence and impact of the internet and information technology in travel trade followed by studies on service quality. According to Bennett (1993) traditional travel agencies need to upgrade themselves

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and further strengthen their role as advice giving; otherwise online travel agencies will threaten their future. Lang (2000) asserted that traditional travel agencies may disappear from the market in future because travelers will prefer to buy their trips through online travel agencies also gives the same argument in his study that the main reason for choosing a traditional travel agency is they provide a greater security and have a human touch .

Andersson (2010) views that buying of online trips has grown into gigantic market nowadays and there is an obvious competition between traditional and online travel agencies. Werthner & Ricci (2004) assert that E-commerce in travel and tourism industries is continuously emerging despite of tough economic problems. Industry is adopting application of both B2B (business to business) and B2C (business to consumer). This industry has changed the ways of conducting the business from traditional way to modern way. As per Kim (2004), there are main two factors for conducting successful e-commerce which is security and user-friendly web interface. He highlighted few benefits of using e-commerce in tourism industry which are easy access to information, providing better information, improving customer services etc. (Bishal, 2010).

Law, Leung & Wong (2004) opined that an opportunity to provide travel services and products online appeared with the advent of internet. Internet has resulted in a completely new communication and distribution channel and it work as an electronic intermediary between travelers and suppliers. Werthner & Ricci (2004) finds that this industry is service oriented business industry; companies are implementing various new techniques to satisfy consumer needs and providing information to them through web and different value generated strategies like value extraction, value capture, value addition, value creation etc. Bettman (1979) indicates that the main purpose of information search is for consumers to reduce risks and uncertainty brought by travel decisions. Users can search information that they need with personal preference (Park, Kwangsoo and Roehl, Wesley 2016). Hyde (2008) finds that there are three parameters in decision making by travel consumers, which are extensive information search for potential traveling needs, information search for specific travel plans and information search for reservation needs. These phases are closely linked to online information search (Park, Kwangsoo and Roehl, Wesley 2016).

Jun, Vogot & Kelly (2007) compared the online with offline information search as well as study the relationship between the two kinds of information search and consuming behaviors. They found that different travel products, experience and phases influence one's behaviors when it comes to information search and one's ability to make decisions when it comes to travel consumptions (Arsal 2008).

Gronroos (1984) defined perceived service quality as the outcome of an evaluation process, whereby the consumer compares his expectations with the service he perceives he has received. Andaleeb & Conway (2006) wrote that empathy has been found to be more suitable and important in enhancing service quality in industries where building relationships with customers and clients ensures the firm's survival as opposed to "transaction marketing". Shahin (2006) orated that service is an activity or series of activities of more or less intangible nature. It normally, but not necessarily, takes place in interactions between customers and service employees and/or physical resources or goods and/or systems of the service provider. Shahin (2011), estimation of customer dissatisfaction based on service quality gaps by correlation and regression analyses in a travel agency, this paper includes five major categories of service quality dimensions and is further subdivided in 15 dimensions and an additional question for measuring the overall dissatisfaction. The findings imply that maximum value gap is related to 'appealing accommodation facilities', which is a part of the dimension of tangibles. The minimum value gaps are also related to 'on time delivery' and 'reputation of service'. Regression analysis has proved and estimated liner correlation between the gaps of empathy and tangibles and the overall customer satisfaction.

Ali Faizen (2012), an assessment of the service quality using Gap analysis: A study conducted at Chitral, in this study the perceived quality of a given service is the outcome of an evaluation process during which customers compare their prior expectations of the service with that they have actually received i.e. having perceived service against the expected service. Overall satisfaction will have huge impact on service

quality dimensions of agents. Service organizations can achieve a strong reputation for quality service only when they consistently meet or exceed customer service expectations.

Objective

To find out the reliability service gap between online travel portals and Travel Agencies

Research Methodology

(a) *Research Design:* To have a better understanding about the issue, a descriptive research design was used. To get the primary data, close ended questionnaire was administrated on 5 point Likert Scale.

(b) *Sample Design:* 200 respondents (100 consumers of Travel agency and 100 consumers of online travel portals) were selected through convenience sampling.

(c) *Area of the Study:* Delhi and NCR

(d) *Analysis:* The data collected was analyzed with the help of statistical tools like Arithmetic mean and Frequency Distribution.

Analysis & Interpretations

There has been increase in the number of tourists travelling for both Outbound and Inbound and also for Domestic sectors. Travel bookings from online travel portals and travel agencies are increasing continuously but to have repeated clients is a big challenge, because it is observed that consumers feel gap between expected and perceived services. Travel is directly related to the traveler's feeling of excitement, joy and relaxation. They always look for the reliability factor from the service providers. So, to find out a reliability service gap between online travel portals and travel agencies and its impact on travel purchase decision, respondents were asked to indicate the level of reliability for various factors on 5 point scale from 1 to 5 (5 denotes the level of impact as 'Very Much, whereas, 1 is the 'Very Less'). Final result is obtained with the help of arithmetic mean and frequency distribution. The final scores for various factors are presented in the following table:

Table 2: Customers' Experience Concerning Reliability Dimension

Service Quality Dimension	Online Travel Portal		Travel Agency	
	Mean Score	Level of Agreement	Mean Score	Level of Agreement
On time Service delivery	4.25	Strongly Agree	3.98	Agree
Meeting the tour schedule	3.39	Neutral	4.21	Strongly Agree
Exact and precise service delivery	3.71	Agree	4.11	Agree
Understand what customers want	3.33	Neutral	4.21	Strongly Agree
The service provider offer in-time and accurate product information	3.65	Agree	3.79	Agree
The service provider could offer relevant service promptly	4.32	Strongly Agree	3.47	Agree
Overall Mean Score	3.68	Agree	4.06	Agree

As per the customers' views mentioned in Table 2, it shows that online travel portals pay more attention to on time service delivery (Mean Score =4.25). In addition to this, they also provide very prompt relevant services (Mean Score= 4.32). Customers are also in the opinion that online travel portals do provide exact and precise service delivery (Mean Score= 3.71) and also provides in- time and accurate product information (Mean Score=3.65). Customer's also believes that sometimes they are neutral in understanding their requisites (Mean Score= 3.33) and pay attention in meeting the tour schedule (Mean Score = 3.39). Whereas, as per the customers' opinion, the travel agencies very strongly understands the requirements of the customers (Mean Score= 4.21) and pay more attention in meeting the tour schedule (Mean Score = 4.21). Customers' also believes that travel agencies pay attention to on time service delivery (Mean Score =3.98) along with exact and precise service delivery (Mean Score= 4.11). In addition to this, they also offer in time and accurate product information (Mean score=3.79) and also offer relevant service promptly (Mean score=3.47). It can be observed and analyzed from the table that online travel portals are better than the travel agencies in context of on time Service delivery and offering relevant services promptly. On the other hand, travel agents are performing better than the online travel portals in understanding what customers want and pay attention in meeting the tour schedule. The overall mean score of online travel portal is (3.68) and the travel agency's mean score is (4.06) which is better

that online travel portal and clearly highlights that the reliability dimension of travel agencies is better than online travel portals. But there is no significant difference in reliability service gap between online travel portals and travel agencies.

Conclusion

From the above study it can be concluded that both online travel portals and traditional travel agencies play an important role in increasing the travel & tourism in Delhi & NCR. There has been increase of business with online travel portals. Traditional agencies are also in a continuous process of upgrading their technology and competing with online travel portals. They both are trying to have more of their repeated clients and increase their market share too. After analyzing the reliability factors table, it clearly highlights that the customers of online travel portals have shown positive response by indicating the level of agreement as both strongly agree, agree and neutral. They have emphasized more on the strongly agree and agree option which clearly highlights that they are satisfied with the reliability services of online travel portals. On the other hand, customers of travel agencies have also shown positive response by indicating the level of agreement as agree and strongly agree which clearly highlights that they are also satisfied with the reliability services of travel agencies. In some of the reliability dimensions, they are strong then the online travel portals and in some areas they need some more innovative ideas to match online travel portals

Recommendations

It has been clearly understood that travel agencies & online travel portals are providing various services which are very useful in promoting the tourism in Delhi & NCR. Having discussed the findings of table 2, the suggestions to improve the services of travel agents & online travel portals are presented hereunder:

1. It has been identified in the study that online portals offer more on-time service delivery and relevant service promptly as compared to the travel agents and that is why some travelers prefer more of online travel portals. So travel agencies are advised to work more on the time management along with the prioritization of services in accordance with the customers so that they can equally compete with the online travel portals.
2. It has been identified in the study that travel agencies understand the needs and wants of the customers in much better way as compared to online travel portals and that is why some travelers prefer more of travel agencies. So online travel portals are advised to work more on empathy element which will help them to understand the customers in much better way.

Therefore, it is very important that both travel agencies and online travel portals should continue to explore new innovative ideas and concepts which will generate maximum customer satisfaction. This will help them to retain not only their existing clients but will also increase their market share.

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